

D2.3 R&I strategies

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full name
CPME	Center for Project Management and Entrepreneurship
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CSRD	Corporate Social Responsibility Development
EC	European Commission
EI Centre	Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
ERA	European Research Area
ERA	European Research Area
ERC	European Research Council
ESG	Environmental, Social, Governance
EU	European Union
FEUN	Faculty of Economics University of Niš
FEUT	Faculty of Economics, University of Tirana
FEUSK	Faculty of Economics, St. Cyril & Methodius University in Skopje
FEUBL	Faculty of Economics, University of Banja Luka
FITD	Fund for Innovation and Technology Development
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GII	Global Innovation Index
HEIs	High Educational Institutions
ICT	Information Communication Technology
K&TT	Knowledge and Technology Transfer
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
NASRI	National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation
PC	Project Coordinator
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SMEs	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises
TT	Technology Transfer
UBL	University of Banja Luka
UEIC	University Entrepreneurship and Innovation Center
USK	St. Cyril & Methodius University in Skopje
UT	University of Tirana
WP	Work Package

R&I STRATEGY OF FEUN, SERBIA

1. Executive Summary: Purpose and scope of the R&I strategy

The primary purpose of the Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy is to establish a comprehensive framework for the advancement of entrepreneurship and innovation at the Faculty of Economics, University of Niš (FEUN). In addition, by introducing the culture of creativity, knowledge exchange, and practical application, this strategy has several other purposes. First, to contribute to the acceleration of the transformation of ideas into marketable solutions that contribute to economic growth (especially those ideas that come from students), to social development and to the sustainable progress of society in general. Second, to promote interdisciplinary research initiatives, capacity-building efforts, and the promotion of innovative entrepreneurship among students and other people; and third, to contribute to the alignment of the institutional goals with regional, national, and international innovation agendas, ensuring that research outputs translate into tangible economic and societal benefits.

At the centre of this strategy is establishing the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation (EI Centre) at FEUN, which will serve as the cornerstone for its successful implementation. The EI Centre will be designed to act as a dynamic hub that connects students, researchers, industry partners, and policymakers, facilitating collaboration, knowledge transfer, and the development of innovative ventures. It will serve as a supporting mechanism by providing training programmes, incubation and acceleration services, and mentoring to the students in their attempt to become the entrepreneurs. In addition, this centre will provide help in finding the appropriate funding opportunities for young entrepreneurs. In short, the R&I Strategy will position the EI Centre as the organisational platform to nurture entrepreneurial mindsets of students and other interested people, foster innovation ecosystems, and enable sustainable growth. Through this approach, this strategy will enhance FEUN's role as a catalyst for innovation-led development, research, entrepreneurship and technology transfer, while contributing to broader socio-economic objectives.

2. Introduction

Widening countries, which are EU member states and associated countries with lower levels of research and innovation performance, face significant structural challenges in building strong entrepreneurial ecosystems. These challenges include limited access to finance, underdeveloped innovation infrastructure, weak university-industry collaboration, low levels of research and innovation (R&I) investment, and fragmented support mechanisms. In such contexts, entrepreneurship is often necessity-driven rather than opportunity-driven, with limited scaling potential. However, widening countries possess some untapped potential: a growing number of educated young people, emerging innovation hubs, increasing digital literacy and connectivity. Yet, a developed, robust entrepreneurial ecosystem that will support start-ups and small and medium enterprises (SMEs), long-term investment in human capital and knowledge institutions, where knowledge can flow smoothly, innovations are commercialised, and cross-sectoral partnerships are often a form of business, is still missing. Such an entrepreneurial ecosystem, on the other hand, would be critical for narrowing the innovation gap between EU regions, including widening countries.

To enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Serbia, it is of significant importance that HEIs play a catalyst role in innovation-led development and knowledge transfer, while contributing to broader socio-economic objectives. The necessary step in that direction is that every HEIs in widening countries has an R&I Strategy. In that line, at the FEUN, such strategy is formulated.

2.1. The Importance of Research & Innovation for Ecosystem Development

R&I are crucial factors for the development, transformation and competitiveness of every entrepreneurial ecosystem. They enable the creation of innovative products and services, knowledge and technology transfer, and cross-sectoral collaboration, contributing to economic growth and competitiveness. R&I also plays a significant role in establishing innovative start-ups and creating smart, sustainable, and inclusive solutions.

For widening countries, among which is Serbia as well, it is of great importance to strengthen R&I capacities, not only for narrowing the gap with more advanced economies regarding the innovativeness and creation of marketable products or services but also for building resilience and autonomy in strategic areas such as energy, health, and digital technologies. Additionally, by incorporating R&I into the core of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, widening countries can, instead of being consumers of technology, become creators and exporters of innovation.

2.2. Strategic Alignment with EU and National Policies

R&I Strategy of FEUN is in line with key Serbian and European strategic frameworks regarding innovativeness, knowledge and technology transfer, sustainability and cross-border collaboration, providing coherence at both local and international levels.

In Serbia, special emphasis is placed on the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3), which guides the country's innovation-driven development by identifying areas with the greatest potential for competitive advantage. Among national S3 priorities, this strategy is especially focused on Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Food for the Future and Creative Industries, thus shaping research directions and institutional priorities.

The R&I Strategy also supports full alignment with broader European Union policy frameworks, such as:

- *Horizon Europe*, the EU's flagship programme for research and innovation, which fosters cross-border collaboration, supports the twin green and digital transitions, and promotes inclusive participation from all EU and associated countries.
- *The European Green Deal and the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans*, which highlight the critical role of innovation in achieving climate neutrality, sustainable energy, circular economy models, and environmental protection.
- *The EU Digital Strategy and the New European Innovation Agenda*, which aim is to enhance Europe's technological sovereignty and to accelerate the translation of research into market-ready solutions, especially by strengthening innovation ecosystems.

Through alignment with these policies, the R&I Strategy at FEUN put itself in the position to actively contribute to enhancing Serbia's entrepreneurial and R&I ecosystem and increasing integration into the European Research Area (ERA). Moreover, this alignment will enhance opportunities for accessing international funding and intensify the collaboration in R&I projects at the national and international level, thereby narrowing the innovation gap between EU regions.

2.3. The Role of Universities and Faculties in Implementing the Strategy

Universities and faculties are at the centre of the knowledge triangle – education, research, and innovation. They have a critical role in generating new knowledge through basic and applied research, educating and training future innovators and entrepreneurs, transferring the academic knowledge

into marketable products and services, and creating collaborative networks with public and private stakeholders.

However, to implement an R&I Strategy effectively, faculties must go beyond the implementation of traditional teaching and research methods. They must actively engage in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students, an orientation towards innovativeness and research, and interdisciplinary initiatives, as well as develop mechanisms to protect and commercialise intellectual property.

In this context, FEUN, through its programmes in business, economics, and management, is uniquely positioned to contribute to the R&I Strategy implementation by combining academic knowledge with practical tools for innovation and entrepreneurship.

2.4. The Role of the EI Centre in Sustaining the Strategy

The operational base for R&I Strategy realisation is the EI Centre. This centre will function as an organisational foundation for bringing together **educational programmes, institutional infrastructure, partnerships, promotion, and evaluation** into a unique framework. Its core objective is to develop entrepreneurial mindsets and behaviours among students, enhance their creativity, support innovation activities, upskill them in entrepreneurial skills, encourage academy-business cooperation, etc. Shortly, the EI Centre is designed to be a multifunctional hub that supports and sustains innovation activities through:

- *Start-up and Scale-up Support*, providing pre-incubation programmes, mentoring, coaching, and investment readiness.
- *Capacity Building*, offering training in entrepreneurial skills, innovation management, IP protection, business model development, and digital tools.
- *Collaboration Facilitation*, acting as a bridge between researchers, students, companies, public institutions, and international partners.
- *Innovation Infrastructure*, serving as a central point for technology transfer, prototyping, testing, and access to networks and markets.
- *Inclusivity and Diversity*, actively encouraging participation from under-represented groups - especially youth and women - in innovation and entrepreneurship.

By doing the above-listed activities, the Centre will contribute to the broader entrepreneurial ecosystem – **fostering collaboration among academia, the business sector, and innovation stakeholders** – while strengthening individuals’ capacity to develop and launch innovative ventures **with a strong emphasis on sustainability and social responsibility**. Additionally, the EI Centre ensures continuity, long-term institutional commitment, and impact monitoring of the strategy. It will also contribute to long-term competitiveness by enabling the FEUN to pursue future-orientated, innovation-driven, competitive, and resilient growth strategies. Shortly, the EI Centre will foster entrepreneurial thinking, skill development, and innovation within academia and the wider community, leading to real-world solutions, economic value, and societal impact.

3. Strategic Vision and Objectives

3.1. Vision, mission and objectives

The **VISION** of the EI Centre is that it will function as a **hub for sustainable entrepreneurial development**, integrating education, research, and industry collaboration under one roof. By doing so, the Centre will contribute to the broader entrepreneurial ecosystem – **fostering collaboration**

among academia, the business sector, and innovation stakeholders – while strengthening individuals' capacity to develop and launch innovative ventures **with a strong emphasis on sustainability and social responsibility.**

The Centre's **MISSION** is to **upskill researchers and young entrepreneurs** in sustainable innovation management, thereby acting as an engine for building a resilient, innovation-driven ecosystem that is aligned with global trends while responding to local needs. Such mission is especially vital for developing regions, as it creates the **knowledge infrastructure and support networks** needed to generate new jobs, attract investment, and boost competitiveness. At the same time, embedding sustainability as a core criterion ensures that innovative solutions will serve to broader social and economic progress beyond individual interests.

The Centre's operational framework is designed to seamlessly integrate within the organisational structure of FEUN, while extending its reach to industry and the wider community. Housed within the FEUN, the Centre will leverage academic resources (faculty's expertise, research facilities etc.) and link them with practical entrepreneurial support (mentors, incubator space, funding opportunities). This institutional integration means the Centre will serve as a bridge between **the academic environment and the market**, translating research and innovation into viable business opportunities. It will coordinate educational programmes (training courses, workshops), provide necessary infrastructure (co-working space, labs or innovation studios), establish partnership agreements, promote entrepreneurial culture, and continually evaluate its impact.

The EI Centre's activities will be organised into units or programmes corresponding to major focus areas (e.g., training and education unit, mentorship and incubation unit, and industry collaboration unit). This ensures each aspect of the Centre's mission – from delivering trainings to facilitating university-business partnerships – has a clear operational process. The Centre will integrate into the university's administrative framework for accreditation and quality assurance of its training, while maintaining the agility to involve external partners in program delivery.

3.2. Key training areas and proposed programs

The training programme titles (and their content) will be based **directly on the summarised results** of the studies, which will ensure they target the real demands of the entrepreneurial ecosystem. In that line, based on extensive focus groups, Delphi studies, and needs analysis conducted under the Horizon USE IPM project, the Centre will deliver training programmes grouped into four major thematic pillars, each with specific topics as follows:

- **Soft Skills Development:** This pillar focuses on the essential personal and interpersonal skills needed for entrepreneurial success. Key training modules include **Communication and Teamwork Skills, Problem-Solving Skills, Critical Thinking, Creative Thinking, Time Management, and Emotional Intelligence.** These soft skills were consistently highlighted as crucial in the focus group findings – for example, effective communication, teamwork, and adaptability were ranked among the most important competencies for young entrepreneurs and were seen as even **more important than hard technical skills for many roles.** Therefore, the Centre will offer targeted short courses or workshops to build these skills (e.g., a workshop on communication and active listening, a course on creative problem-solving and critical thinking for start-ups, etc.). By improving soft skills, participants will be better equipped to lead teams, network with stakeholders, resolve conflicts, and persevere in the entrepreneurial journey.
- **Sustainability and Sustainability Reporting:** In line with the project's emphasis on sustainable entrepreneurship, the Centre will provide trainings on **implementing sustainability practices and reporting standards in businesses.** Proposed program titles include **Sustainability Practices**

in **Business, Sustainable Entrepreneurship, Circular Economy Principles, Sustainability Reporting (ESG/CSR), and Environmental Protection Skills for Entrepreneurs**. These topics were derived from the second focus group and Delphi study, which underscored the importance of environmental, economic, and social sustainability aspects for modern enterprises. For example, participants highlighted that companies should integrate sustainable practices for long-term competitiveness and that knowledge of **sustainability reporting (e.g., ESG metrics)** is increasingly demanded. Training under this pillar might include a course on how to design **sustainable business models and value propositions**, a practical class on measuring and reporting sustainability performance (covering standards like GRI or the EU's CSRD requirements), and workshops on circular economy opportunities (such as recycling, waste management and resource efficiency strategies). By offering these, the Centre will respond to the identified need for **at least two to three training programs will be focused on sustainability practices, reporting, circular economy, and environmental protection**, ensuring that researchers and entrepreneurs can build ventures that are not only profitable but also environmentally and socially responsible.

- **Technology Transfer and Open Innovation:** This thematic area addresses the skills and knowledge required to convert research into market innovations and to manage technology partnerships. The training titles in this category include **Leadership for Open Innovation, Market Research as research and development (R&D) Support, Collaborative Research Projects, Collaboration for Technology Transfer, and Intellectual Property Rights Management**. These topics reflect the findings of the third focus group and Delphi study, which dealt with challenges in technology transfer and open innovation ecosystems. For instance, a lack of understanding of the technology transfer process and low awareness of IP protection were noted as challenges in the Western Balkan region. The Centre's programs will therefore teach participants how to navigate IP (patenting, licensing, etc.), how to conduct market research to align innovations with market needs, and how to lead open-innovation initiatives (e.g., engaging external partners or crowdsourcing ideas). A specific course might cover "From Lab to Market: Technology Transfer 101," including case studies on successful commercialisation of academic research, while another workshop could focus on **Intellectual Property Rights**, guiding researchers on patent applications and IP strategy (addressing the noted complexities and the need to raise IP awareness). By covering **open innovation leadership and collaborative project management**, the Centre enables entrepreneurs to collaborate across institutional boundaries – a need highlighted by experts who emphasised weak industry – research collaboration and the importance of public – private partnerships and innovation networks. These trainings ensure participants can effectively bring innovative ideas to market through cooperation and proper innovation management.
- **Responsible Innovation and Academia-Business Collaboration:** The fourth pillar is focused on managing innovation processes responsibly and strengthening the cooperation between academic institutions and enterprises. Training topics here include **Innovation Process Management Tools, Responsible Innovation (ethics and sustainability in innovation), A2B Collaborative Models, Understanding Innovation Ecosystems, and Innovation Ecosystem Supporting Institutions**. This set arises from the fourth focus group, which stressed the need for continuous training of employees in innovation and greater academia-industry synergy for sustainable innovation. Participants in the study recommended various **innovation management tools** – such as Design Thinking, Business Model Canvas, lean start-up methods, etc. – as very useful in guiding the innovation process. In response, the Centre will offer practical trainings on these tools (for example, an interactive **Design Thinking workshop** or a course on using the Business Model Canvas and Agile methodologies for product development). **Responsible innovation** training will cover how to evaluate the social and environmental

impacts of new ventures and incorporate ethics and sustainability in the innovation lifecycle. Additionally, since the studies revealed many ideas to improve academia - business collaboration (like involving industry experts in education, setting up joint innovation projects, etc.), the Centre will organise programmes on **collaborative models** – for instance, how to establish successful university-industry partnerships, how to create innovation networks or consortia, and how supporting institutions (e.g., funding agencies, chambers of commerce) can be leveraged. These trainings will help academics and entrepreneurs learn to work together effectively, thereby **bridging the gap between theory and practice**. By understanding the **innovation ecosystem and its key actors**, participants can better navigate resources like innovation funds, accelerators, and networks. Overall, this pillar’s programmes aim to cultivate an ecosystem mindset and collaboration skills so that innovations are not developed in isolation but with the support of a vibrant network.

4. Current State of the Entrepreneurial and R&I Ecosystem in Serbia

4.1. Research and Innovation Capacity

4.1.1. Status of Academic and Research Institutions

Serbian science competencies are strongly anchored in the legal framework, infrastructure, and human and financial resources available for this purpose. Currently, in Serbia, academic and research institutions are under the scope of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation. They must obey the following *regulations*:

- Law on Science and Research ("Official Gazette of RS", number 49/19),
- Law on the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia ("Official Gazette of the RS", No. 95/2018), and
- Law on Innovation Activities ("Official Gazette of RS", 129/21).

In terms of *infrastructure*, Serbia had, in 2023, 459 organisations in total engaged in R&D: 286 from the business sector, 61 from the state sector, 110 from the higher education sector and 2 from the non-profit sector. Their scientific field is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Number of organisations engaged in R&D by sectors and scientific fields in Serbia, 2023

Scientific field	Sector				
	Total	Business sector	State sector	Higher education sector	Non-profit sector
Total	459	286	61	110	2
Natural Sciences	141	110	14	16	1
Engineering & Technology	166	133	10	23	
Medical and Health Sciences	27	13	4	10	
Agricultural Sciences	32	14	12	6	
Social Sciences	67	15	10	41	1
Humanities	26	1	11	14	

Source: Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia (2025). Retrieved from: <https://data.stat.gov.rs/> (accessed on August 8, 2025).

When it is about the scientific research organisations in Serbia, according to the Register of Scientific Research Organisations (eNauka), in 2025 there are 208 research organisations in total. Their type, scientific field and ownership are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Research organisations in Serbia for 2025

Type	Number	Scientific field	Number	Ownership	Number
Faculty	114	Social	92	National	165
R&D institute	36	Engineering & Technology	64	Private	39
Scientific institute	31	Natural Sciences & Mathematics	45	Mixed	4
University	14	Humanities	41		
SANU – Institute	8	Biotechnology	32		
Innovation Centre	5	Medical	24		

Source: eNauka (2025). Retrieved from: <https://enauka.gov.rs/> (accessed on August 8, 2025).

The 2025 structure of Serbia’s 208 registered scientific research organizations reveals a system dominated by faculties and national institutions, with social sciences, engineering, and natural sciences as leading fields. While this concentration ensures stability and strong academic output, it also reflects limited diversification into private and mixed-ownership research environments, which are crucial for accelerating innovation and market-oriented research. Strategically, Serbia should leverage its strong academic base to develop multidisciplinary research clusters that integrate universities, R&D institutes, and innovation centres. Increasing the share and capacity of innovation centres - currently underrepresented - could strengthen technology transfer, foster start-up creation, and stimulate high-value sectors such as biotechnology and medical sciences. Furthermore, incentivising private sector participation and fostering public–private partnerships could help balance the current public sector dominance, improve commercialisation rates, and align research agendas with national economic priorities.

In addition to the infrastructure, *human resources* account significant part of research activity in Serbia. According to data from eNauka (2025), in Serbia there are 20,832 active researchers. This data confirm that Serbia’s research capacity is anchored in a substantial pool of human resources, predominantly employed in state-owned faculties and scientific institutes. This concentration within public institutions provides a strong foundation for coordinated national research strategies, yet also signals the need to diversify research environments through greater engagement of private and mixed-ownership organisations. Strategic priorities should focus on mobilising these talents towards high-impact research areas, enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration, and creating structured pathways for translating academic outputs into market-ready innovations. Strengthening innovation centres and fostering partnerships with industry could bridge the current gap between research potential and commercialisation outcomes, while targeted investments in under-represented fields, such as biotechnology, could position Serbia more competitively within emerging global sectors.

Despite the fact that Serbia has substantial pool of researchers, their distribution across the country reflects regional disparities, where Belgrade region even outperforms the Euro area average, while Šumadija and Western Serbia and Southern and Eastern Serbia remain well below both the national and EU benchmarks (Table 3).

Table 3: Researchers in all sectors by NUTS 2 region measured as a percentage of total employment - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE)

Area	Year				
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Euro area – 20 countries (from 2023)	0.97	1	1.04	1.07	1.09
Belgrade region	1.17	1.17	1.22	1.16	1.17
Region Vojvodina	0.44	0.42	0.42	0.46	0.5
Region Sumadija and Western Serbia	0.14	0.11	0.13	0.15	0.15
Region Southern and Eastern Serbia	0.3	0.3	0.29	0.31	0.32

Source: Eurostat (2025). Retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/> (accessed on August 7, 2025).

The regional imbalances in researchers' distribution in Serbia presented in Table 3 limits the potential for regionally balanced innovation-led growth and concentrates R&D activity in a single economic hub. Therefore, Serbia should adopt targeted measures to decentralise research capacity, including regional research hubs, incentives for relocating or establishing R&D units outside Belgrade, and stronger integration of local universities with industry. Strengthening human resource mobility, improving regional innovation infrastructure, and promoting smart specialisation in under-represented areas could help reduce disparities, stimulate local economies, and enhance Serbia's overall innovation competitiveness.

Lastly, *financial resources* for R&D in Serbia deserve special attention since, as the all investments are mostly limited. Their structure is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Investments in R&D in Serbia for the period 2019-2023

Indicator	Period				
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Total R&D resources/GDP [%]	0.89	0.91	0.99	0.97	0.95
Budget R&D resources/GDP [%]	0.40	0.46	0.42	0.39	0.39
Business sector/GDP [%]	0.35	0.36	0.45	0.42	0.41
Government sector/GDP [%]	0.23	0.27	0.26	0.25	0.25
Higher education/GDP [%]	0.31	0.29	0.28	0.29	0.29
Private non-profit sector/GDP [%]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Expenditures of private and public enterprises for R&D/Total expenditures for R&D [%]	39.50	39.00	45.20	43.70	43.50
Expenditures of the state and local administration for R&D/ total expenditures for R&D [%]	25.80	29.30	26.60	26.30	26.40
Expenditures of the higher education for RS/ total expenditures for R&D [%]	34.70	31.70	28.20	30.00	30.10
Expenditures from abroad for RD/Total expenditures for R&D [%]	19.70	9.60	15.90	17.50	30.30
Total expenditures for R&D/per capita in thous. RSD [thousand RSD]	6.92	7.23	9.12	10.29	11.69
Total expenditures for R&D/per researcher in thousands. RSD [thousand RSD]	2,931.50	2,991.70	3,674.71	3,915.80	4,204.50

Source: Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia (2025). Retrieved from: <https://data.stat.gov.rs/> (accessed on August 10, 2025).

The data shows that Serbia's total R&D expenditure as a percentage of GDP remained below 1% throughout 2019–2023, well under the EU average of around 2.3% in the same period, pointing to a persistent underfunding of research and innovation. While there is a slight upward fluctuation in total R&D resources (peaking at 0.99% in 2021), this was not sustained in the following years. The structure of funding reveals that the business sector's contribution to GDP in R&D (around 0.35–0.45%) is relatively low compared to innovation-driven economies, indicating limited private-sector engagement. The data also show that government funding remains stable but modest, while higher education consistently accounts for nearly one-third of R&D spending, suggesting a strong reliance on the academic sector for research output. It is also notable that the sharp increase in the share of funds from abroad in 2023 (30.3%) indicates growing external reliance, which may be both an opportunity for international cooperation and a vulnerability if such funding is unstable. The data from Table 4 also show the absence of contributions from the private non-profit sector, highlighting the missing source of diversification in R&D financing. Finally, data show steady growth in per capita and per researcher spending, which is a positive sign, but the absolute values remain low by international standards, potentially limiting Serbia's capacity to retain talent and stimulate high-impact research.

4.1.2. Innovation Performance and University-industry Collaboration

According to the European Innovation Scoreboard 2025 (European Commission, 2025), Serbia is classified as an Emerging Innovator, achieving 51.5% of the EU average innovation performance in 2025. This places it 31st among EU Member States and neighbouring countries, and slightly above the average for its peer group of Emerging Innovators. Since 2018, Serbia's innovation index has increased by 10.2 percentage points, mostly due to innovation activities driven by SMEs, especially in the ICT sector. However, this index still trails the EU's overall pace of growth.

The most significant *indicators* reflecting *innovation activities* in Serbia are as follows (European Commission, 2025):

- Serbia is ranked first among all EU and neighbouring countries for SMEs introducing product innovations.
- Human capital indicators are mixed as the share of the population with tertiary education and engagement in lifelong learning have improved (supported by education reforms and modernisation of vocational training), but the number of new doctorate graduates has declined, and digital skills remain weak.
- Research system attractiveness has grown (since 2018) through increased international scientific collaboration, but foreign doctorate student numbers have dropped.
- Investment levels are limited, with public R&D expenditure slightly falling since 2018.
- Venture capital availability are at low level.
- Non-R&D innovation expenditures have sharply decreased (between 2018 and 2025), signalling persistent business investment challenges.
- IT-related investments have surged, with exceptional growth in cloud computing adoption and ICT employment.
- Exports of medium and high-tech goods have declined slightly (between 2018 and 2025).
- Environmental performance is weak, with low resource productivity and poor CO₂ productivity, reflecting challenges in the green transition.
- GDP per capita is below half of the EU average, and demographic decline (-1.4% population growth) poses long-term risks.

- The scores in corruption perception and rule of law are at low level, affecting the institutional trust.

According to Global Innovation Index (GII), Serbia ranks 52nd out of 133 countries, an improvement compared to its 53rd position in 2023 (WIPO, 2024).¹

When it is about the distribution of different types of innovation implemented by enterprises classified as innovators in Serbia in 2022, data provides regional patterns of innovation activity, highlighting the disparity across various country's regions (Table 5).

Table 5: Types of innovation in enterprises-innovators, by territory [%] in 2022

Territory	Type of innovation				
	Innovators - total	Innovation of products / services	Process innovation	Abandoned or ongoing innovations	Non-innovators
REPUBLIC OF SERBIA	51.1	36.8	41.3	5.1	48.9
SRBIJA NORTH	52.8	38.0	42.2	5.9	47.2
Belgrade region	54.4	40.1	44.2	5.9	45.6
Region Vojvodina	50.0	34.3	38.7	5.9	50.0
SRBIJA SOUTH	47.3	34.3	39.1	3.2	52.7
Region Sumadija & Western Serbia	52.4	38.3	43.4	3.7	47.6
Region Southern and Eastern Serbia	38.3	27.2	31.6	2.3	61.7

Source: Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia (2025). Retrieved from: <https://data.stat.gov.rs/> (accessed on August 10, 2025).

The data show that slightly more than half of enterprises in Serbia were classified as innovators in 2022, with the highest share in the Belgrade region (54.4%) and the lowest in Southern and Eastern Serbia (38.3%). Product and process innovations are relatively balanced across most regions, though both types are significantly less prevalent in the south-east. The share of non-innovators is highest in Southern and Eastern Serbia (61.7%), indicating pronounced regional disparities in innovation activity and suggesting a need for targeted support measures in less developed areas.

Data from previous tables showed that Serbia's innovation performance has improved over recent years, driven by strong SMEs innovation capacity and rapid digital technology adoption. However, structural weaknesses in R&D investment, intellectual property creation, productivity, and green transition readiness must be addressed. To sustain progress, Serbia will need to expand funding opportunities, boost high-tech exports, and invest in skills, particularly in advanced research and digital competencies.

¹ The GI I comprises around 80 indicators that measure the innovation potential and achievements of countries through input and output parameters, offering a comprehensive overview of different dimensions of innovation. Among upper-middle-income countries, Serbia holds 7th place out of 34 economies, while in the European region, it ranks 31st out of 39 countries included in the report. Serbia moves to the top 50 with a strong performance in Domestic industry diversification (11th), ICT services exports (12th), Scientific and technical articles (13th) and Cultural and creative services exports (14th) (WIPO, 2024).

When it comes to **university-industry collaboration** in Serbia, it is supported mainly through the Innovation Fund and the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, both aiming to connect research organisations with businesses to stimulate innovation, commercialise research, and strengthen technological capacity.

According to the document Policy Answers (2025) key programmes and instruments of the university-industry collaboration in Serbia are:

- *Science–Business Collaboration Program*: Encourages joint R&D projects between research institutions and companies to develop market-ready products or services. Funding is grant-based with co-financing from partners, aiming to bridge scientific research and industrial application.
- *Technology Transfer Program*: Supports the commercialisation of research results that have reached at least TRL 4, offering financial aid (up to RSD 6 million) and mentorship for market analysis, IP strategy, and business model development.
- *Innovation Vouchers*: Provide SMEs with up to RSD 800,000 (covering 60% of service costs) to engage research institutions for product, process, or service development.
- *Green Science–Business Collaboration Program*: Focuses on applied research in environmental protection, sustainability, and climate change, funding projects up to EUR 200,000.

So far, some strengths and weaknesses regarding **university-industry collaboration** in Serbia, are identified. Some of them are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Strengths and weaknesses in university-industry collaboration in Serbia

Strengths	Weaknesses
Dedicated funding streams exist to foster science–industry partnerships.	Limited scope and number of collaboration programs compared to countries like Austria; fewer sector-specific initiatives.
Support mechanisms encourage SMEs to tap into research expertise.	Short-term funding cycles without sustained, structured platforms for long-term collaboration.
Programs target commercialization and market-oriented innovation	Focus is heavily on start-ups and SMEs, with less support for medium and large companies, which could drive larger-scale innovation projects.
	Lower funding ceilings than in comparable EU programs, limiting project scale.
	Capacity building for institutions is less developed, with no dedicated network like Austria’s ACR to strengthen institutional expertise.
	Limited integration into international research and industry networks, reducing opportunities for global cooperation and technology transfer.

Source: Policy answers - Paths Towards Strengthening and Transforming Academia-Industry Cooperation in the Western Balkans: Lessons from Austria and Serbia (2025). Retrieved from: https://westernbalkans-infohub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Output-fellowship-template_jan_2025.pdf (accessed on August 10, 2025).

In general, Serbia should strengthen university–industry collaboration by creating a dedicated, long-term network with stable funding and clear governance, expanding support to include medium and large enterprises, raising funding limits for higher-impact projects, investing in institutional capacity building for universities and research centres, and deepening integration into international innovation networks.

4.2. Key Challenges in Entrepreneurship and R&I Ecosystem in Serbia

Entrepreneurship and R&I are critical drivers of economic progress and societal development. However, fostering an environment conducive to entrepreneurial activities and innovation requires addressing several challenges Serbia is facing. These challenges could be classified into four groups: **soft skills, sustainability, technology transfer, and responsible innovation management.**

4.2.1. Soft Skills

In order to establish and run a successful entrepreneurial business, in addition to the hard skills, entrepreneurs should also possess certain soft skills, including a set of interpersonal skills such as communication, empathy, emotional intelligence, conflict resolution, and negotiation, as well as personal qualities, attitudes, motives, work ethic, etc. These skills enable people to interact successfully with other entities in the business sphere, recognise opportunities in the market, and be flexible and innovative. However, according to data from the focus group organised at FEUN, as well as the Delphi technique implemented by this faculty, it was found that key challenges regarding the essential soft skills that entrepreneurs should possess are as follows:

- *The Educational System does not Support Soft Skills Development.* In Serbia's educational system from the earliest ages, teaching on the importance of soft skills is not on an adequate level, nor is it orientated enough on their development. As a result, students as future entrepreneurs during the education are not sufficiently exposed to these skills.
- *Insufficient Development of Risk Management Skills.* Serbian people generally possess a high level of risk aversion (mostly due to cultural constraints). In most cases, they try to avoid risks rather than minimise them, which is essential in entrepreneurial business.
- *Insufficient Development of Time Management Skills.* People in Serbia are generally not aware of the importance of time management, which is crucial for successful business. In most cases, they lack the knowledge and skills on how to prioritise their activities, resulting in wasting valuable time.
- *Low Awareness of the Importance of Active Listening Skills.* Active listening skills, as a part of communication skills, are very important for the success of a business, as they help gain the trust of clients and allow for flexibility and adaptability in meeting their needs. However, these skills are often neglected.
- *Underestimated Importance of Emotional Intelligence.* In Serbia, educational system generally does not equip persons at an adequate level with this soft skill, which is essential for successfully running the business, successful relationship establishment, conflict resolution, stress management, etc.
- *Missing the Practical Experience Regarding the Soft Skill Development of Young People.* Trainings and workshops led by experts in soft skills are rarely organised at faculties, although they are highly valuable. As a result, some essential soft skills for business and entrepreneurial ventures of young people are not being developed at an adequate level.

4.2.2. Sustainability

An important part of entrepreneurial business should be orientated toward sustainability. However, according to the focus group results and the Delphi technique implemented by FEUN, several challenges were identified. The most important are:

- *Insufficient Awareness of the Companies of the Importance of Environmental Practices Regarding Sustainability.* In Serbia, many companies do not pay sufficient attention to their impact on the environment, as they pollute air and water, do not save energy, insufficiently implement the circular economy activities, and only a small number of companies use renewable energy sources, etc.
- *Lack of Alignment Between Economic Activities and Sustainable Practices.* Some of the examples of inappropriate alignment between economic activities and sustainable practices in Serbia are as follows: a certain number of companies avoid paying eco taxes, investments in environmental sustainability are considered as costs, irrational spending of resources, and bureaucratic obstacles in obtaining various permits.
- *Lack of Appropriate Recycling Infrastructure.* For many types of waste in Serbia, there is no appropriate recycling infrastructure. Some companies have to export the waste, which significantly increases the cost of the recycling process. In addition, the infrastructure for collecting the waste from households is not developed at a proper level.
- *Lack of Public Awareness and Engagement with Sustainability Practices.* In Serbia, there is generally low awareness among people about the importance of sustainability practices, as they do not select waste for selection in the area where infrastructure for this exists, irrationally use energy, etc.
- *Insufficient Implementation of IT Solutions to Support Sustainability-Based Practices.* The possibilities of applying IT to support sustainability-based practices are not well used. IT could be used for data reduction, waste sorting (especially in the field of e-recycling), optimisation of business processes for energy saving, etc.
- *Lack of Clear and Mandatory Legal Regulations for Sustainability Reporting.* In Serbia, only big companies have the obligation to report on sustainability, which causes medium and small companies to not be dedicated to this issue. On the other side, the legal regulations in this area are imprecise, i.e., the indicators that should be monitored are not specified.

The above challenges highlight the need for increased public awareness, improved infrastructure, and better regulatory enforcement to support sustainability efforts in Serbia.

4.2.3. Technology Transfer and Open Innovation

In order to establish a solid foundation for sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in the Republic of Serbia (RS), according to the focus group results and the Delphi technique implemented by FEUN, several challenges are identified.

- *Unsatisfactory Knowledge Transfer Between Actors in the Innovation Ecosystem.* In Serbia, there is no optimal collaboration between the actors in the innovation ecosystem. It is usually sporadic and based on a project basis. Innovations generated at faculties are, in most cases, not adapted to the needs of the economy, which limit the knowledge transfer between academia and business.
- *Gap Between State Support and Small Business Needs.* Small innovative businesses in Serbia, in addition to needing funding, often require more support in the process of commercialising their innovations. However, institutional support in this regard is lacking.
- *Improvement of Intellectual Property Protection.* In Serbia, although the legal regulations regarding intellectual property protection are well-developed, there is a need for further improvement and alignment with EU standards, which is crucial for technology transfer. In

addition, existing regulations should be better implemented. Finally, the long period for intellectual property protection should be overcome.

- *Inadequate Financial Support Mechanisms.* Regarding government incentives and policies that support innovative projects, the following issues are identified: a small portion of funds goes to the less-developed parts of the country, too much funding is dedicated to financing pilot projects and much less to supporting the commercialization of new products. Start-ups and small businesses need more mentoring support.
- *Constraints Regarding Innovative Mindset.* To improve the capacity of Serbian companies for innovation, it is important that managers change their mindset, i.e., think more innovatively and see innovation as a tool for market competition.
- *Absence of Tailored Educational Programs to Support Innovation.* To enhance innovativeness, it is important to encourage innovative thinking among students through tailored educational programs.

By overcoming the above challenges, Serbia can enhance its technology transfer processes, sustainable entrepreneurship and create a more innovative thereby more competitive economy.

4.2.4. Innovation Process Management

Regarding innovation process management finding from the implementation of focus group method, as well as Delphi technique at FEUN, imply that there are the following challenges in Serbian entrepreneurial and R&I ecosystem:

- *Unsatisfactory Cooperation Between Key Actors in the Open Innovation Ecosystem.* Although there are many actors in the innovation ecosystem in Serbia (universities and faculties, state institutions, hubs, start-up centres, coworking spaces, and corporations), cooperation between them is unsatisfactory, which constrains greater innovativeness in society.
- *Constraint in Mentality Regarding Innovations.* Many people in Serbia are reserved about innovations and new things. There are also managers who have a non-innovative mindset, which constrains the innovativeness of their companies.
- *Non-Supporting Organisational Culture Regarding Innovativeness.* In many Serbian companies, organisational cultures are not orientated toward innovation. Employees do not receive adequate training to support innovative activities and innovative ways of thinking. Both financial and non-financial support are missing to stimulate the innovativeness of employees.
- *Insufficient Support for Small Businesses Regarding Sustainable Innovations.* Small businesses in Serbia need more institutional support for green innovations due to their limited resources.
- *Inadequate Institutional Support for Sustainable and Responsible Innovation.* In Serbia, there is insufficient state support for the purchase of green energy, use of gas, and installation of solar panels, as well as incentives for wind farms and solar power plants. In addition, there is no obligation for entrepreneurs and small businesses to engage in green reporting, resulting in a lack of motivation to develop green innovations.
- *Unsatisfactory Cooperation Between the Academic Community and Business in the Context of Sustainable and Responsible Innovations.* Academic institutions often focus on theoretical and research-orientated innovations, while business need practical and market-orientated solutions in the area of sustainability.

By overcoming the above addressed challenges Serbia will enhance its overall R&I ecosystem, promote sustainable entrepreneurship, and create a more innovative economy.

5. Key Pillars of the R&I Strategy

Based on the analyses of the current state of entrepreneurial and R&I ecosystem in Serbia, the challenges with which it faces with, as well as having in mind the world's best practices in this area, R&I Strategy at FEUN is based on three key pillars: research excellence, technology transfer and exploitation and innovative entrepreneurship.

5.1. Research Excellence

To foster research excellence, continuous improvement of core facilities, spaces, and services is essential. These elements are imperative for researchers to work effectively and productively. The concept of research excellence is inspired by the Research Excellence Framework of Queen Mary University of London (Queen Mary University of London, 2019).

To support the researchers at every stage of their careers, we will:

- Support researchers to work across disciplinary, organisational and geographical boundaries.
- Lead innovation in doctoral education and support, developing and significantly increasing our PhD student population and welcoming funded full and part-time students from traditional and alternative routes from all over the world.
- Significantly increase our number of externally-funded Research Fellows and postdoctoral researchers and support them to develop a world-class research career.
- Ensure all our researchers are supported to be leaders in their fields, through investment in leadership, management and supervision training.

To create a world-class research environment, we will:

- Build upon our discipline strengths to attract and retain the best talent, train future researchers and shape the disciplines nationally and internationally. Based on these strengths we will significantly increase our interdisciplinary research to address future socioeconomic global challenges.
- Provide sustainable and accessible world-class research facilities and attract significant national and international external funding to support our physical and virtual research environment.
- Encourage our research community to collaborate across the world, maintaining an agile approach to individual and research group partnerships, and grow and invest in a small number of strategic international partnerships with leading institutions.
- Significantly increase our industrial partnerships, supporting funded collaborative research.
- Host Centres for Doctoral Training, and develop collaborative doctoral programmes with strategic partners, to support research in faculties and in research institutes.
- Mobilise alumni worldwide – our global family – to help develop new research and industry links.

To ensure that market and social impact are embedded in all research activities, we will:

- Nurture a world-class research culture for our entire community.
- Support innovation, development, entrepreneurship and impact to address global and national challenges, including those articulated in the national Industrial Strategy, and maintain our position as a leader in public-engaged research.

- Embed a culture where impact, innovation and engagement are an innate part of all research activity, and public our impact internally, nationally and internationally to enhance our global reputation.
- Build on our core values to further embed a culture of engaged research practice, creating an environment where research can be shaped, conducted, and results disseminated with the public as partners, at home and overseas.

Especially important is to foster the development of a research culture. Research culture includes the values, expectations, and behaviours of researchers - how they choose and conduct projects, review peers' work, mentor colleagues, collaborate with external partners, and share their findings effectively. It is especially important to further develop principles and practices that promote a collaborative and inclusive research environment supporting mentorship, scholarship, discovery, and creativity. Facing with societal challenges requires contributions from everyone, and diversity in perspectives and approaches are highly valuable (The University of British Columbia, 2021).

5.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

Creativity and motivation are essential for generating new business ideas, but they alone aren't enough to turn those ideas into impactful economic and social outcomes. Knowledge and technology transfer (K&TT) is a collaborative process that moves scientific discoveries and intellectual property from creators, like universities and research institutions, to public and private users, helping convert inventions into products and services that benefit society (WIPO, n.d.).

Technology transfer (TT) is the process of sharing knowledge and technology from one individual or organization to another. It involves efforts to exchange skills, technologies, and processes among various actors who can further develop and apply the technology in new products, services, or processes. Typically, TT occurs between universities, government, and businesses. Additionally, intermediary organizations, such as Technology Transfer Offices in universities, help bridge the gap between these actors, facilitating collaboration and the effective spread of innovation and knowledge (Battistella et al., 2023).

The process of transforming ideas into practical, market-ready solutions involves key elements like intellectual property and licensing, business model development, lean start-up and effectuation methods, and assessing technology readiness levels. The approach to sustainable TT has evolved from focusing mainly on pollution control and resource conservation to embracing integrated solutions that address environmental, economic, and social factors simultaneously (Fernandes, et al., 2021). Several studies report a general positive effect from sustainable TT on economic growth (Ferreira et al., 2020; Gomes et al, 2022).

5.3. Innovative Entrepreneurship

Innovative entrepreneurship is one of the key drivers of economic development particularly for less developed economies where the economic growth is at the forefront of policymakers' agenda (Amini Sedeh et al., 2022). The main contribution of ordinary entrepreneurship is job creation. Innovative entrepreneurship is more likely to lead to higher value-added jobs and wealth creation and firms with higher growth rates, the founders perhaps more compelled towards growth by the opportunity of the venture and its innovativeness. According to OSLO Manual (OECD, 2005), innovation is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product good or service, or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practice. On the other hand,

entrepreneurs are business owners who seek to generate value, through the creation or expansion of economic activity, by identifying and exploiting new products or processes (OECD, 2007). The combination of entrepreneurship and innovation results in innovative entrepreneurship: new firms based on new innovative ideas (Szabo & Herman, 2012).

Innovative entrepreneurship, defined as the creation of new products, services, production methods, or business models likely to spur firm growth, generate value-added jobs, and create individual, corporate, and societal wealth. Innovative entrepreneurship can also unleash solutions to unexpected social crises and breakthroughs for unresolved economic and societal issues related to poverty reduction, climate change, access to healthcare, and other (Bradley et al., 2021). Common measures of innovation, such as R&D investment or patent data, are not well-suited for small entrepreneurial firms, as they often underestimate their innovativeness. Therefore, in line with the literature, the proposal is composite measure that combines product and process innovation (Amini Sedeh et al., 2022).

The government policy in the areas of science, education, intellectual property and entrepreneurship can be instrumental in fostering the competitive market economy of the 21st century (UN, 2012). The study results indicate that differences in economic development levels can be explained by disparities in innovative entrepreneurship, which is essential for the sustainability of emerging market economies (Szabo & Herman, 2012).

Many factors at both micro- and macro-levels influence the cross-country differences in entrepreneurial activities in general and innovative new venture creation in particular (Amini Sedeh et al., 2022). The macro approach to promoting innovative entrepreneurship focuses on building an institutional environment - such as secure property rights, efficient legal systems, open markets, and access to capital - rather than directly supporting specific firms or technologies. However, institutional change is slow, making it difficult to translate this knowledge into quick policy actions. Also, designing public policies to support innovative entrepreneurship is challenging because entrepreneurs face high uncertainty and complexity while creating new products and markets. Policies that try to "pick winners" by favouring certain firms or sectors often fail and may promote "crony capitalism," where success relies on political ties rather than market merit (Bradley et al., 2021). On the micro level, policies often include funding, training, incubators, or accelerators, but their effectiveness depends on careful firm selection and appropriate support. Instead of picking winners, an emerging strategy emphasizes supporting firms with demonstrated market potential (Bradley et al., 2021).

6. Implementation Framework

A strong and resilient research and innovation (R&I) system requires not only strategic vision but also the enabling conditions and initiatives that turn that vision into practice. Serbia's innovation ecosystem depends on coordinated governance, a clear national strategic framework, the active role of universities, and a culture that embraces innovation, digitalization, sustainability, and international cooperation. The following overview highlights the key enablers and initiatives that will shape the future development of Serbia's R&I system.

Governance

For the successful implementation of the R&I Strategy, it is essential to establish an adequate and efficient governance system. In the Republic of Serbia, the institutional framework responsible for innovation governance comprises several entities. The most significant governing body is the **Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation**, whose mandate is defined by law. The Ministry performs a range of functions that directly support innovation, including: development and enhancement of the R&D system as a driver of scientific, technological, and economic

advancement; formulation and implementation of science and technology policy and strategy; design and execution of scientific, technological, and developmental research programs; support for young talents and the professional development of researchers; formulation and implementation of innovation policy; development and implementation of policies and programs in the field of artificial intelligence; promotion of techno-entrepreneurship, knowledge and technology transfer in the economy; development and improvement of the innovation system in the Republic of Serbia; advancement of scientific and technological information systems and development of related infrastructure; creation of conditions for access to and implementation of projects under the Ministry's remit funded through EU pre-accession funds, international donations, and other forms of development assistance.² The quality assurance of scientific research and the development of research activities in the Republic of Serbia are overseen by the following bodies and committees:

- National Council for Scientific and Technological Development,
- Committee for the Accreditation of Research Organizations,
- Commission for the Acquisition of Scientific Titles,
- Sectoral Scientific Committees.³

The backbone of the science, technology, and innovation system consists of the Innovation Fund and the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia. The **Innovation Fund**, established in 2011, aims to strengthen the linkages between science, technology, and industry, and to support the development of innovative entrepreneurship.⁴ The **Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia** is a government institution established in March 2019 with the aim of supporting and advancing scientific research and technological development in Serbia. Its mission is to create conditions for the continuous progress of science and development as a foundation for building a knowledge-based society. The Fund carries out its activities through various scientific, technological, and development programs aligned with the strategic goals of the Republic of Serbia in the fields of science and technology. Through public calls, the Fund finances projects characterized by high scientific quality, innovation, international competitiveness, and relevance for addressing societal challenges.⁵

The Development Agency of Serbia is a government agency established by the Government of the Republic of Serbia to perform developmental, professional, and operational tasks related to the promotion and implementation of direct investments, export promotion and growth, enhancement of the competitiveness of business entities, and the reputation and economic development of the Republic of Serbia, particularly in the areas of economy and regional development.⁶

The policies, strategies, and actions of the aforementioned bodies and institutions are aimed not only at research organizations and universities, but also at innovation organizations, including science and technology parks (in Belgrade, Niš, Čačak, and Novi Sad), business incubators, startup centres, and clusters.

The scope of activities and composition of their governing bodies are defined by the regulatory framework of the Republic of Serbia in this field: the Law on Innovation Activity, the Law on Science and Research, and the Law on the Science Fund. This legal framework is aligned with EU standards, enabling access to funding from programs such as Horizon Europe and EUREKA.

National Research & Innovation Strategy

² <https://nitra.gov.rs/en/ministarstvo/o-nama>

³ <https://nitra.gov.rs/cir/nauka/nauka-i-istrazivanje-u-srbiji>

⁴ <https://www.inovacionifond.rs/lat/o-fondu/o-fondu>

⁵ <https://fondzanauku.gov.rs/>

⁶ <https://ras.gov.rs/>

Between 2020 and 2021, the Republic of Serbia adopted several strategic documents that together form a comprehensive national framework for research and innovation. The first strategy, valid until 2025, is titled the Strategy for the Scientific and Technological Development of Serbia 2021–2025: „The Power of Knowledge". It was adopted by the Government of the Republic of Serbia in February 2021 as a strategic document aimed at enhancing the science, research, and innovation system. The main objectives included strengthening research institutions, developing infrastructure, and fostering international integration, particularly through the European Research Area (ERA). The Strategy was accompanied by an Action Plan for the period 2021–2023. Encouragingly, a new Strategy for Scientific and Technological Development 2025–2029 is currently being prepared, representing a continuation and further development of the previous „Power of Knowledge" strategy. The first meeting of the Working Group for drafting the new strategy was held in September 2025.⁷ The goal of the Strategy is to create a favorable environment for researchers and talents, and to enable more effective application of scientific results in addressing economic and societal challenges. The strategic framework includes strengthening the research workforce, supporting spin-off companies, and fostering closer collaboration between science and industry.

The currently valid strategy that supports research activities and innovation is the Smart Specialisation Strategy for 2020–2027, adopted in February 2020. The Strategy focuses on the following priority areas for entrepreneurial discovery: Information and Communication Technologies (Big Data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing, Internet of Things, Software Development, Embedded Systems); Food Industry (High-Tech Agriculture, Value-Added Food, Sustainable Agriculture and Food Production); Creative Industries (Creative Digital Audiovisual Production, Video Game Industry, Smart and Active Packaging); Future Machines and Manufacturing Systems (Special Purpose Machines, Information for Smart Control – Industry 4.0, Premium Tools and Components for the Automotive, Railway and Aviation Industries, Combustion Devices Using Eco-Friendly and Sustainable Fuels, Smart Environmental Solutions); Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) and Emerging Technologies (Photonics, Advanced Materials, Advanced Production Technologies and Electronics, Biotechnology, Blockchain Technologies, Autonomous Driving, Aircraft Systems and Engineering); Energy-Efficient and Eco-Smart Solutions (Eco-Smart Energy Sources).⁸

Universities

Universities are key stakeholders in the implementation of the R&I Strategy. In the Republic of Serbia, there are eight public universities, operating in accordance with the laws governing education and science. The University of Niš comprises 13 faculties and serves as a strong research base in southern Serbia. Through the development of modern curricula, an interdisciplinary approach, and the promotion of entrepreneurship, the University of Niš educates young professionals who will become the main drivers of R&I development. The importance and role of universities as key implementers of the R&I Strategy can be viewed through several dimensions, the most significant being the following:

Universities are centres for generating new knowledge. They form the foundation of scientific research and, through academic research and projects, produce new knowledge. In doing so, they foster a favorable environment for innovation within the economy.

⁷ <https://www.ai.gov.rs/vest/1395/put-ka-naucnoj-izvrsnosti-i-inovacijama-odrzan-prvi-sastanak-radne-grupe-za-strategiju-naucnog-i-tehnoloskog-razvoja-2025-2029.php>

⁸ Smart Specialisation strategy of the Republic of Serbia: for the period 2020 to 2027 (p. 143). Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia (2021). p. 66 Available at: https://pametnaspecijalizacija.mpn.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Strategija-pametne-specijalizacije_EN_WEB.pdf

Another important role of universities is connecting with the industry and facilitating the transfer of knowledge and technology. The most common and well-known mechanisms for cooperation with the private sector are technology parks and business incubators, as well as involving companies in research projects aimed at the commercialization of research results. This contributes to the direct application of research in the real economy.

Through participation in European and international R&I programs (such as Horizon Europe), universities enable the transfer of best practices to Serbia, enhance scientific excellence, and open doors for international collaboration and investment in science and innovation.

One of the most crucial contributions universities make is in supporting strategic planning and policy-making. The academic community possesses the expertise and capacity to aid in developing public policies by actively engaging in drafting and overseeing the implementation of the national R&I Strategy, as well as recommending necessary measures and reforms in this sector.

The successful execution of the R&I Strategy cannot be achieved without the proactive role of universities. They serve as the cornerstone of the innovation ecosystem by bridging knowledge, people, institutions, and the business sector into an integrated network that drives sustainable progress in science, technology, and the economy.

Cultural Change

For the R&I Strategy to be effectively implemented, it is essential to embed it into the cultural patterns of society. Changes must be made at the level of universities, business entities, and macroeconomic policy makers.

Involving students in activities that encourage creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurship across all levels of study plays a vital role in cultivating an innovation culture. Promoting both existing initiatives and launching new ones, such as university business and innovation competitions, hackathons, conferences, and workshops, will help reinforce the startup ecosystem and inspire entrepreneurial mindset. At the university level, it is crucial to formalize knowledge transfer as a fundamental mission. This requires removing regulatory and institutional obstacles and establishing incentive systems that motivate faculty, researchers, and students to actively engage in projects and entrepreneurial ventures, including startup development. Businesses need to acknowledge the strategic value of innovation and knowledge transfer and deepen their collaboration with academia. Simultaneously, companies should receive systematic support aimed at boosting their innovation capabilities. The government and public sector have a pivotal role in fostering and expanding an innovation-driven culture. Their responsibilities extend beyond generating and sharing knowledge to also adopting and using products and services derived from that knowledge. Enhancing the innovation capacity of the public sector demands the systematic elimination of barriers and the creation of incentives that encourage all parties to participate actively in collaborative research and innovation efforts.

Building public awareness of the importance of innovation should be a core component of development strategies in both the medium and long term. This can be achieved through well-designed communication campaigns and educational initiatives aimed at different segments of society. To speed up this process, it is essential to develop a robust and resilient national research and innovation ecosystem where all relevant actors (universities, businesses, government institutions, and civil society) are actively connected and collaborating. Moreover, showcasing and celebrating successful local innovation stories is a powerful way to increase public trust in innovation and to inspire a stronger entrepreneurial culture across the country.

International Orientation

In the contemporary context of knowledge globalization, and in light of limited market and resource capacities, Serbia faces the need to further strengthen the international dimension of its national R&I system. Focusing on the development of international partnerships and cooperation with relevant institutions and countries abroad contributes to improving the quality of research work and increasing the critical mass of research capacities. The approach represents one of the key steps toward the long-term sustainability of the national R&I system.

The international orientation of the Faculty of Economics represents a key direction of development within the modern higher education landscape and aligns with global trends in higher education, scientific research, and innovation. In the context of increasing globalization of knowledge, the need for international mobility, and limited local resources, it is essential to intensify the international dimension of the faculty's activities at all levels.

Establishing and maintaining cooperation with higher education and research institutions abroad directly contributes to enhancing the quality of teaching and research, enables access to up-to-date knowledge and technologies, and strengthens the international expertise. It is particularly important to encourage strategic partnerships with universities and institutions from the EU and beyond, including countries with well-developed education and innovation systems.

The EI Centre plays a significant role in this process, acting as a bridge between the academic community and the business sector, as well as a generator of new knowledge, startup initiatives, and multidisciplinary projects. Through connections with international partners and participation in global innovation networks, the Centre further contributes to the development of an entrepreneurial culture and the innovation capacity of the faculty, especially among students and young researchers.

The active participation of the Faculty of Economics in international projects and programs (such as Erasmus+, Horizon Europe, and other EU programs) should be further strengthened through organized support for professors, researchers, and students. This would increase the faculty's presence in international academic networks and provide additional funding for development activities. In this context, the EI Centre can play a key role in identifying project opportunities, developing applications, and managing international partnerships.

Attracting foreign students, lecturers, and researchers significantly contributes to knowledge exchange, international visibility, and the development of intercultural competencies within the faculty community. In this regard, it is necessary to further develop the offer of study programs in English and ensure institutional support for incoming and outgoing mobility.

Encouraging the international orientation of students and young researchers, including preparing them to "think and act globally" from the very beginning of their studies, is crucial for their future competitiveness in both the job market and the academic environment. Through participation in international competitions, conferences, internships, and exchange programs, students gain valuable experience, contacts, and knowledge. In this context, the EI Centre has the potential to serve as a platform for international student networking, as well as their development through mentorship programs, entrepreneurship idea competitions, and cooperation with international start-ups.

In order to strengthen the long-term international position of the Faculty of Economics, it is necessary to develop stable institutional mechanisms for international cooperation, including an office for international projects, systematic support for project applications and management, as well as the engagement of staff with experience in international educational and research environments. Cooperation with the EI Centre further reinforces these efforts, making the faculty a recognized actor within the European higher education and innovation space.

Stakeholder Communication

Given contemporary challenges and changes shaping both global and national contexts, defining the future directions of smart specialisation development will become crucial for enhancing Serbia's innovation and education systems. New circumstances will influence the redefinition of

priorities within the existing strategy and the upcoming action plan, as well as within the broader framework of government development policies related to science, education, and technological advancement.

The continuation of the entrepreneurial discovery process, as outlined in the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3), will ensure ongoing communication with all relevant stakeholders, while taking into account local, regional, and global trends, so that shared needs and goals can be directed toward further development and adaptation of the innovation ecosystem to modern changes.

Promoting awareness of the importance and impact of R&I at national and international levels is a key priority of the Faculty of Economics. It is essential to communicate clearly and strategically the vision and reform of the research and innovation management system, as well as the goals of the strategy, defined policies, planned activities, and achieved results.

To highlight the benefits of R&I, their impact on economic and social development, and their role in addressing contemporary challenges in national and global contexts, it will be necessary to develop and implement a comprehensive branding and communication strategy. This strategy will target various groups: the academic community, business sector, decision-makers, students, and the general public, with the goal of strengthening their engagement, recognizing the value of R&I, and fostering a sense of shared responsibility for its development.

The branding and communication strategy will be professionally designed, with the possibility of engaging external experts, and will include a wide range of promotional activities, such as traditional and digital communication channels, public events, visual identity, and media visibility of research and innovation initiatives.

The EI Centre at the Faculty of Economics will play an important role in implementing this strategy by bringing together researchers, students, business partners, and international organizations. Through the Centre's initiatives, further efforts will be made to strengthen innovation culture, promote the faculty's scientific achievements, and connect academic knowledge with market needs.

At the international level, the implementation of targeted communication campaigns is planned to help position the Faculty of Economics as a prominent regional player in the fields of economic sciences, entrepreneurship, and innovation. By leveraging educational and scientific diplomacy, together with the support of international partnerships and the alumni network, the faculty will further strengthen its international reputation and presence.

Finally, all activities within this strategy will be planned and implemented in accordance with the principles of participatory decision-making, through open consultations and collaboration with internal and external stakeholders, to ensure alignment with actual needs and to achieve the greatest possible social and economic impact.

Digital Transformation

For a successful digital transformation of the economy, it is essential that strategies, technologies, infrastructure, and skills are aligned with the R&I system. Such alignment enables efficient knowledge exchange and fosters the development of new solutions. Within this context, Serbia's ICT sector plays a key role on two levels: first, through its continuous growth and the export of IT products and services to global markets; second, by leading the digital transformation of the entire economy and society. Building on the previous successes of Serbia's ICT sector, it is possible to stimulate the development of the natural market and accelerate digital modernization, which are strategic goals also recognized in the Economic Development Plan and the SWOT analysis of the ICT sector.

Digital transformation represents a fundamental change in how companies, institutions, the public sector, and society use technology, people, and processes to radically improve performance. This transformation is not merely about digitalizing existing processes, but about shifting mindsets

and embedding a digital environment into all products and services, both online and offline. Digital transformation is not only a key driver but also, in many cases, a prerequisite for innovation. It also plays a significant role in strengthening communication and knowledge exchange among actors within the research and innovation community.

Particular importance is given to the digitalization of public administration and the development of electronic services (e-government), which contribute to reducing bureaucracy, increasing transparency, improving service quality for citizens and businesses, and lowering the operational costs of the public sector.

In Serbia, key initiatives supporting these goals include:

- The strategy for the development of the digital economy and society of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2022-2027, which outlines the directions for developing digital infrastructure, skills, and services in the country.
- The national strategy for the development of artificial intelligence (AI) in the Republic of Serbia 2022-2027, which lays the foundation for the application of AI technologies in industry, the public sector, and research institutions.
- Programs and projects implemented by the Ministry of education, science and technological development, including support for research infrastructure and international cooperation.
- Serbia's digital agenda, as part of the broader EU digital policy, aimed at connecting Serbia with European research and innovation networks.
- E-government initiatives implemented through the establishment of a unified digital market and services for citizens and businesses
- Within the academic sector, the Faculty of Economics and the EI Centre play a key role in:
 - Supporting the development of digital competencies through teaching and research,
 - Developing innovation and entrepreneurial skills needed to quickly adapt to changes in the digital economy,
 - Connecting with domestic and international research and business partners,
 - Participating in international programs and projects (e.g., Erasmus+, Horizon Europe),
 - Promoting digital transformation through innovative projects and support for startups and small enterprises.

All these initiatives and activities contribute to creating conditions for strengthening the digital economy in Serbia, as well as increasing the global competitiveness of students and researchers at the Faculty of Economics.

Green Transformation

The green transformation entails a fundamental change in how resources are used, products are made, and services are delivered, with the goal of reducing environmental impact and achieving sustainable growth. This includes a shift toward renewable energy sources, the circular economy, improved energy efficiency, and the development of green technologies and innovations that support climate goals and enhance quality of life. The green transformation is essential for boosting the competitiveness of the economy and society as a whole, while encouraging innovation and sustainable business models.

Environmental protection has been the subject of research in Serbia for decades, but the green technology industry, including water and land treatment and recycling, remains underdeveloped. The EU recognizes ecology as a key investment area for helping Serbia meet European standards. Projects related to water treatment and protection are particularly important in countries of the Danube

region. European programs such as IPA Cross-Border Cooperation and Green Innovation Vouchers support collaboration between researchers and companies for sustainable development. Although the economic results in renewable energy, recycling, and emissions reduction are not yet substantial, ecological innovations remain a priority for sustainable development.

In Serbia, several important initiatives and strategies support this process:

- The National plan for energy efficiency and renewable energy, which sets targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and increasing the share of renewables in the energy mix,
- The Strategy for the development of the circular economy in the Republic of Serbia, which promotes more efficient use of resources, recycling, and waste reduction.
- Green development programs and projects led by the Ministry of environmental protection, aimed at supporting ecological innovations and preserving natural resources.
- Serbia's participation in international initiatives and climate funding mechanisms, such as the EU Green Deal and climate change-related funds.

The Faculty of Economics and the EI Centre actively contribute to the green transformation through:

- Educational programs and research focused on sustainable development, the green economy, and innovative business models,
- Support for entrepreneurs and start-ups developing environmentally friendly products and services,
- Collaboration with government institutions, businesses, and international partners on projects that promote sustainability,
- Organizing workshops, conferences, and educational programs on green technologies and responsible business practices.

7. Expected outcomes and impact

The FEUN's R&I Strategy is designed to advance knowledge, promote innovation, attract top talent, secure external funding, and build strong partnerships to address societal challenges and support economic development. Specifically, the strategy will deliver:

- **Generation of new knowledge** that enhances the understanding of the world and opens new avenues of research, grounded in rigorous, ethical, and high-quality research.
- **Research-informed education** that strengthens teaching and learning by integrating research insights into academic programmes.
- **Innovation and practical application** of research through the development of new products, services, and processes that address real-world problems and improve societal outcomes.
- **Attraction of funding and talent** by securing competitive national and international research grants, while fostering skills in entrepreneurship and innovation.
- **Public engagement** that communicates research effectively to diverse audiences, improves accessibility, and builds public confidence in science and innovation.
- **Collaborative partnerships** with local, national, and international stakeholders to expand the reach and relevance of research and enhance community impact.

As a key pillar of this strategy, the EI Centre will play a central role in its execution. The Centre will play a critical role in delivering the intended outcomes and ensuring that the strategy's impact is tangible and far-reaching. It will contribute to long-term competitiveness by enabling the FEUN to pursue future-oriented, innovation-driven, competitive, and resilient growth strategies. The EI Centre will foster entrepreneurial thinking, skill development, and innovation within academia and the wider

community. Its core objective is to develop entrepreneurial mindsets and behaviours among students, faculty, and external stakeholders. This, in turn, supports new venture creation, drives innovation, and contributes to economic and social development. The EI Centre will deliver a range of outcomes and generate meaningful long-term impact in the following areas:

- **Strengthening entrepreneurial mindset and culture.** The EI Centre will enhance entrepreneurial intentions among students and aspiring entrepreneurs by offering a dynamic, supportive, and stimulating environment, along with practical support. By nurturing confidence and competence, it will foster a culture that embraces risk-taking, innovation, and proactive value creation within academic institutions.
- **Developing entrepreneurial skills.** Through training, workshops, and mentorship, the EI Centre will equip participants with vital competencies such as problem-solving, critical thinking, adaptability, networking, business planning, marketing, and financial management. These skills will prepare individuals to identify and pursue business opportunities and adapt to dynamic market environments.
- **Enhancing career readiness.** The EI Centre will embed entrepreneurial learning into interdisciplinary education, preparing students for a broad range of careers and promoting entrepreneurship as a prospective career path. Even for those not starting their own ventures, the entrepreneurial mindset - characterised by initiative, creativity, and opportunity recognition - is highly valuable in the evolving job market.
- **Enabling new venture creation.** By building a talent pipeline with the right skills and mindset, the EI Centre will support the successful launch and growth of new enterprises. Structured support - including access to mentorship, funding, and business networks - will improve the quality and viability of start-ups.
- **Supporting economic growth and job creation.** The EI Centre will actively contribute to economic development by fostering start-ups and supporting existing entrepreneurs. This will generate employment opportunities, internships within the innovation ecosystem, encourage self-employment, and reduce graduate and overall unemployment. Structured and tailored support will improve start-up survival and growth rates, ensuring lasting economic impact.
- **Strengthening industry and community engagement.** Functioning as a hub, the EI Centre will bridge academia with industry and society. It will facilitate collaboration between students, start-ups, SMEs, and innovation teams, translating research into commercial and social value. This will strengthen the university's engagement with external stakeholders and improve the practical impact of academic research.
- **Building innovation ecosystems.** The EI Centre will enable knowledge exchange across sectors, driving the development of new products, services, and technologies. It will promote open innovation by fostering networks and partnerships that accelerate the commercialization of ideas and research outputs.
- **Addressing societal and environmental challenges.** Aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals, the EI Centre will encourage ventures that provide innovative solutions to pressing social and environmental problems. This focus will enhance community wellbeing and support inclusive, sustainable development.
- **Enhancing institutional visibility and competitiveness.** The presence of a high-performing EI Centre will strengthen the university's profile and reputation as an innovation leader. This will improve its visibility in international rankings and attract partnerships, funding, and top-tier talent.
- **Driving educational innovation.** The EI Centre will support experiential learning models that enhance student engagement and skill application. It will help integrate entrepreneurship into

curricula across various disciplines. Moreover, it will support curriculum development that aligns with industry trends and future skill needs.

- **Informing policy and strategic development.** The EI Centre will generate data and insights to inform innovation and entrepreneurship policy at the institutional and national levels. This evidence base will support strategic decision-making around funding, talent development, and ecosystem gaps.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1. Summary of Key Strategic Priorities

This strategy is built upon key challenges within the area of entrepreneurial and R&I ecosystems in Serbia, such as insufficient investment in R&I, a low level of soft-skill development among young people (future entrepreneurs), unsatisfactory knowledge transfer between actors in the innovation ecosystem, insufficient awareness among the companies of the importance of environmental practices regarding sustainability, insufficient financial support mechanisms, unsatisfactory cooperation between the academic community and business, etc., thereby providing a comprehensive framework for their overcoming.

Based on the key challenges, the R&I Strategy addressed several **strategic priorities**, such as:

- Developing entrepreneurial mindsets and behaviours among students, especially in the area of sustainability,
- Developing soft skills among researchers and young entrepreneurs, crucial for successful entrepreneurial business and collaboration in the modern world,
- Promoting enhancing the sustainable business practices, as well as encouraging sustainable entrepreneurship,
- Enhancement of technology transfer between the actors in the entrepreneurial ecosystem, enabling entrepreneurs to collaborate more effectively with academia and various industries and effectively bring innovative ideas to market,
- Enhancement of the collaborative partnerships with education, research, and industry.
- Stimulating innovation and practical application of research through the development of new products, services, and processes that address real-world problems and improve societal outcomes.

The above strategic priorities of the R&I Strategy are in the function of developing an integrated and sustainable innovation ecosystem in which education, research and economy are connected. Special emphasis is placed on developing an entrepreneurial mindset and soft skills among students and researchers, as well as encouraging sustainable business practices and entrepreneurship. In addition, this strategy is aimed at strengthening technology transfer and cooperation between the academic and economic sectors, thus creating conditions for a more efficient transfer of innovations into practice, with special emphasis being placed on innovations that are a function of sustainability. In this way, the strategy contributes to economic and overall social development through sustainable solutions and practical application of research.

8.2. Next Steps for Implementation and Policy Adoption

After a draft of R&I Strategy is presented on the round table “Driving Corporate Responsibility and Entrepreneurship: R&I Strategy and Action Plan”, the supporting partners of the USE IPM project in RS will be introduced with this strategy with the opportunity for making suggestions in the attempt this strategy being more effective. In addition, this strategy will be communicated with all relevant

actors in the entrepreneurial and R&I ecosystem, as well as with all other interested actors. The relevant bodies of the FEUN will also discuss this strategy. After a wide debate on this strategy and being formally adopted by certain bodies of the FEUN, it will be published at the USE IPM project web page, as well as at the web page of the FEUN.

In order to realise strategic priorities and other objectives settled in the R&I Strategy, certain activities will be carried out specified in the R&I Action Plan. According to it all activities will be carried out through a clearly defined timeline structured in five key phases, covering the period from Q1 2026 to Q4 2028. Each phase will include specific initiatives coordinated by the EI Centre in collaboration with academic staff, students, business partners, and international institutions. Phases of implementation include Capacity Building (Q1–Q2 2026), Institutionalization (Q3–Q4 2026), Initial Implementation (Q4 2026 – Q2 2027), Scale-up and Consolidation (Q3 2027 – Q2 2028), and Evaluation and Strategy Revision (Q3 – Q4 2028).

For the purpose of measuring the effectiveness of R&I Strategy at FEUN, some Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be formulated. In accordance with the R&I Strategy objectives, some of the crucial ones are: number of start-ups created, amount of funding raised by start-ups, number of patents filed and technologies commercialised, jobs created in innovative sectors, partnerships formed between academia and industry (number of signed contracts), R&D expenditure relative to GDP, etc.

8.3. Recommendations for Long-term Sustainability and EU Integration

As the key challenges in the entrepreneurship and R&I ecosystem in Serbia have been identified in the area of sustainability, the R&I Strategy is largely focused on encouraging entrepreneurs, and especially students with an entrepreneurial orientation, to create innovative solutions that are a function of sustainability, but also, in general, on encouraging sustainable business practices. In this regard, some of the key recommendations for long-term sustainability promoted by the R&I Strategy are:

- Educating students and other people to implement sustainable business practices,
- Incorporating the principles of sustainability into the business strategies of all economic entities, as well as institutions,
- Reducing the negative impact of business practices on the environment,
- Rationally using the natural resources and energy,
- Developing innovative and technologically advanced solutions that contribute to sustainability, etc.

Since the future of Serbia in the EU, besides the above-listed measures for improving the sustainability framework in RS, for successful integration in the EU some additional measures should be taken. Some of them are as follows:

- Harmonising regulations in the field of environmental protection, energy and climate change with EU regulations,
- Developing green and circular economy,
- Encouraging investment in renewable energy sources to reduce dependence on fossil fuels.
- Strengthening institutional capacities and coordination in the implementation of sustainability policies,
- Further development of sustainability reporting and responsible business systems,
- Creating funds, accelerators and tax incentives for projects that contribute to sustainability, etc.

The achievement of the strategic priorities of the R&I Strategy and implementation of the above-mentioned activities in the area of sustainability, the position of the FEUN as a catalyst for

innovation-led development and sustainably developing the business and society will be reinforced. In other words, this faculty will give significant contribution in enhancing the overall entrepreneurial and R&I ecosystem in RS, as well as the sustainability framework in this country on its EU integration agenda.

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R&I STRATEGY OF FEUT, ALBANIA

1. Executive Summary: Purpose and scope of the R&I strategy

This document is prepared under the umbrella of the Development Strategy of University of Tirana (2023-2028) with the core focus on the chapter of Research and Innovation. It is designed as a guiding framework for advancing sustainable entrepreneurship and innovation within the FEUT. In a context of rapid digital, economic, and societal transformation, FEUT recognises that universities must act not only as providers of knowledge, but also as generators of solutions, incubators of ideas, and active partners in the wider innovation ecosystem.

The primary purpose of this document is to establish a comprehensive framework for the advancement of sustainable entrepreneurship and research & innovation. By fostering a culture of creativity, knowledge exchange, and practical application, it pursues several interrelated aims. First, it seeks to accelerate the transformation of ideas—particularly those originating from students—into marketable solutions that contribute to economic growth, social development, and the sustainable progress of society at large. Second, it aims to promote interdisciplinary research initiatives, capacity-building efforts, and the development of innovative entrepreneurship among students, academic staff, and external collaborators. Third, it supports the alignment of FEUT's institutional goals with regional, national, and international innovation agendas, ensuring that research outputs translate into tangible economic and societal benefits.

FEUT aspires to strengthen its role as an active actor in Albania's emerging innovation ecosystem. By integrating research excellence with entrepreneurial mindsets and collaborative partnerships, the document provides a coherent direction for future initiatives, programmes, and projects across departments and study cycles. In doing so, it lays the foundation for a more dynamic, connected, and impact-oriented academic environment, capable of responding to contemporary challenges and contributing meaningfully to the country's sustainable development and European integration.

2. Introduction

Albania's transition toward a knowledge-based economy requires coordinated and sustained action across academia, industry, government and civil society. As a *widening country*, Albania shares a set of structural challenges and in this context, entrepreneurship is still frequently necessity-driven rather than opportunity-driven, and only a small share of entrepreneurial initiatives manages to scale or internationalise.

At the same time, Albania and other widening countries possess important, yet underutilised assets: an expanding pool of educated young people, emerging innovation hubs, and steadily improving digital literacy and connectivity. What is still largely missing is a robust, well-connected entrepreneurial ecosystem that provides long-term investment in human capital and knowledge institutions, facilitates unhindered knowledge flows between actors, supports systematic commercialisation of research, and normalises cross-sector partnerships as a routine mode of doing business. Building such an ecosystem is essential to narrowing the innovation gap between EU regions and to progressing toward a more cohesive European Research Area, one of the cores aims of the Widening and ERA agendas.

In order to strengthen the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Albania, higher education institutions must enhance their role as catalysts for innovation-led development and knowledge transfer, while contributing directly to broader socio-economic goals. A necessary step in this direction is that every HEI in widening countries articulates a clear Research and Innovation Strategy that aligns institutional

priorities with national, regional and European innovation agendas. In this spirit, University of Tirana (UT) has formulated its Development Strategy 2023-2028 with core focus on R&I as a structured framework to modernise its research and innovation activities and to position its faculties as key drivers of sustainable development, knowledge-based entrepreneurship, and evidence-informed policy in Albania and beyond. This contribution on further activities and actions of its strategy will enable FEUT to contribute further to this aim.

2.1. The Importance of Research & Innovation for Ecosystem Development

Research and innovation are fundamental engines of economic growth, productivity, and long-term competitiveness. For Albania, strengthening R&I capacity is not simply a technical objective, but a strategic necessity for transforming its economic model and positioning itself within the European knowledge economy. By investing in research and innovation, the country can better support the dual digital and green transitions, respond to technological change, and open new pathways for value creation.

In this context, R&I becomes a key instrument for reducing skills gaps in priority sectors, particularly by equipping graduates and professionals with advanced, future-oriented competencies. It also underpins the development of innovative entrepreneurship, enabling new ventures and SMEs to emerge, grow, and compete in regional and international markets. At the same time, stronger research and innovation capacity encourages closer collaboration between academia and the private sector, making it easier to co-create solutions, transfer knowledge, and address real socio-economic challenges. Ultimately, enhancing R&I performance contributes directly to Albania's progress toward EU integration, by aligning national developments with the principles and priorities of the European Research Area (ERA).

2.2. Strategic Alignment with EU and National Policies

The Development Strategy of University of Tirana 2023-2028, is conceived in close alignment with both EU-level frameworks and national policy priorities. It reflects the objectives of the:

- European Research Area (ERA) and is informed by the thematic pillars of Horizon Europe, ensuring that institutional actions are compatible with European standards,
- The European Green Agenda for the Western Balkans, which highlights the critical role of innovation in achieving sustainable energy, circular economy, environmental protection, and climate neutrality,
- New European Innovation Agenda, which aims to enhance Europe's technological sovereignty and to accelerate strengthening innovation ecosystems.

At the national level, Albania's Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy (2023- 2030) is shaped by the country's long-term development goals, EU integration agenda, and the need to modernize its scientific, technological, and institutional capacities. The strategy operates within a national context marked by limited research infrastructure, fragmented coordination, low levels of private-sector engagement, and the need for stronger international cooperation. commitments under EU accession negotiations. The R&I Strategy seeks to build a modern, interconnected system where universities, research institutions, government bodies, industry, and civil society collaborate through the Quadruple Helix Model. It highlights the need to strengthen regulatory frameworks, improve research quality and ethical standards, enhance human capital, and promote excellence in scientific output. Investments in digitalization, innovation infrastructure, and skills development are considered

essential to elevating Albania's research performance and fostering a culture of innovation. At the core of the strategic framework are three overarching policy goals:

1. Enhancing the regulatory, ethical, and infrastructural environment for scientific research, ensuring greater quality, modern institutional governance, and improved access to national and international funding.
2. Fostering cross-sectoral collaboration among academia, private sector, public administration, and civil society, promoting technology transfer, applied research, and innovation-driven growth.
3. Strengthening STEM education, digital competencies, and research skills to prepare a new generation of researchers and innovators who can contribute to Albania's sustainable development.

Within this national framework, the University of Tirana (UT) positions scientific research as a fundamental mission. Aligned with the country's R&I priorities, the Development Strategy of the University of Tirana 2023–2028 places Research, Innovation, and Sustainability at the central of its institutional transformation. This strategic commitment underscores the importance of research excellence, innovation ecosystems, and sustainable practices across all teaching and research activities. It also reflects a broader vision for cultivating a dynamic research culture characterized by academic integrity, autonomy, and international collaboration. UT seeks to expand its capacity to produce and disseminate high-quality scientific knowledge, participate more effectively in international programmes such as Horizon Europe, and contribute to national policymaking, sustainable economic development, and cultural advancement.

These institutional ambitions are fully aligned as well as with national priorities Albania's 2025–2030 Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3), which identifies priority domains for innovation and economic transformation to raise research standards, improve regulatory and infrastructural conditions, and foster a stronger innovation ecosystem across Albania.

The components of the strategy support the university's objectives to improve research quality, increase publication output in indexed journals, strengthen international partnerships, and promote collaboration with the private sector. Some of the Specific Objectives of the strategy includes:

- Increase funding for scientific research from national, regional, international, and internal university sources.
- Strengthen cooperation between the academic community and the private sector.
- Support innovation initiatives, technology transfer, and the establishment of innovation hubs.
- Advance the quality and impact of scientific research and promote academic staff with strong publication profiles.

2.3. The Role of Universities and Faculties in Implementing the Strategy

Within this framework, universities occupy a central position as generators of knowledge, innovation, and human capital. The Faculty of Economy and its departments play a pivotal role in advancing high-quality research that is academically rigorous and societally relevant. Through bachelor, master's, and doctoral programmes, they contribute to the development of skilled graduates and researchers who can drive change in both public and private sectors.

Beyond teaching and research, the Faculty serves as a bridge between academia and the wider economy by facilitating collaboration with businesses, public institutions, and civil society organisations. It contributes to evidence-based policymaking, including through policy briefs, applied research projects, and expert engagement in national and regional initiatives. At the same time, the

Faculty provides a fertile environment for experimentation and innovation—whether through project-based learning, student-led initiatives, or participation in international networks.

Faculties, as core academic units, are therefore crucial for nurturing interdisciplinary skills and attitudes. By embedding entrepreneurship, digital competencies, and sustainability perspectives across curricula and research agendas, they help shape a new generation of professionals and entrepreneurs who are capable of operating in complex, rapidly changing environments and contributing to the development of a resilient innovation ecosystem in Albania.

3. Strategic Vision and Objectives

3.1. Vision

The Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana (FEUT) aspires to become a key driver of a functional research, innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystem in Albania. This vision is based on gradual, realistic, and sustainable development: better use of existing human, institutional and financial resources; stronger and more genuine links between academia and the private and public sectors; and practical innovations that respond to local and national challenges, rather than only chasing “world-changing” ideas.

The strategy is grounded in the principles of sustainable development, digital transformation and inclusiveness. It seeks to strengthen institutional capacities, invest in research infrastructure and human capital, and deepen cooperation between universities, industry, government and society, in line with European and global agendas such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

3.2. Mission

The mission of FEUT’s R&I Strategy on Sustainable Entrepreneurship is to actively foster an innovative entrepreneurial environment within and around the university, by engaging key stakeholders in joint activities in research, education, training and knowledge transfer. Through this collaborative ecosystem, FEUT aims to promote economic growth and competitiveness, support new and existing enterprises, and contribute to Albania’s transition toward a knowledge-based society.

3.3. Strategic Objectives

3.3.1. Strengthen FEUT as a Catalyst for Social and Economic Progress

Position FEUT as an active actor in the national and regional innovation system. This includes:

- Upgrading basic research and teaching infrastructure (labs, IT equipment, digital tools).
- Creating or revitalising development units, labs and centres within departments.
- Supporting student-led initiatives, incubator-type activities and early-stage start-ups through mentoring and practical guidance.
- Encouraging applied research projects that address priority sectors for Albania (e.g. tourism, services, digital economy, green transition).

3.3.2. Promote Open and Collaborative Innovation

Foster structured interaction between the academic community, private sector, public institutions and civil society to co-create solutions for social and market needs. Key directions include:

- Facilitating joint projects and EU-funded applications between FEUT and businesses or public bodies.
- Encouraging the creation of university spin-off and start-up initiatives involving students and staff, within the existing legal framework.
- Supporting SMEs and start-ups through training, advisory services and access to networks, rather than relying solely on large-scale funding schemes.

3.3.3. Build Capacities for Knowledge and Technology Transfer

Develop instruments and platforms that make knowledge flows and innovation transfer more systematic and visible, such as:

- Innovation laboratories, project labs and pilot “living lab” initiatives.
- Knowledge transfer and liaison mechanisms (e.g. project offices, partnership platforms).
- Collaborative research spaces where students, academics and practitioners work together on real-life problems.

3.3.4. Develop Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Mindsets

Equip students and staff with transversal competencies needed in a modern innovation ecosystem, with particular attention to youth, women and under-represented groups. This involves:

- Integrating practical skills (digital literacy, financial literacy, data skills, communication and teamwork) into curricula and training.
- Promoting entrepreneurship education with concrete, hands-on activities (workshops on how to launch and manage a business, not only inspirational talks).
- Supporting both traditional and innovative business ideas that can generate sustainable local impact.

3.3.5. Enhance Regional and International Cooperation

Embed FEUT within a broader Western Balkans and European innovation space by:

- Preparing and implementing joint projects with universities and institutions in neighbouring countries and EU member states.
- Engaging the Albanian diaspora as mentors, guest lecturers, partners and advisors in specific R&I and entrepreneurship initiatives.
- Using regional and European cooperation to upgrade standards, attract resources and increase the international visibility of FEUT’s research and innovation outcomes.

Together, this strategic vision and these objectives provide a coherent roadmap for FEUT to gradually build a vibrant, inclusive and impact-oriented research and innovation ecosystem that supports Albania’s sustainable development and European integration.

4. Current State of the Entrepreneurial and R&I Ecosystem in Albania

4.1. Research and Innovation Capacity

4.1.1. Status of Academic and Research Institutions

Albania's research and innovation (R&I) system is primarily anchored in its higher education institutions. The country currently has 40 higher education institutions (HEIs) – 14 public and 26 private – dispersed across Tirana and the main regions, all operating under the framework of Law 80/2015 on Higher Education and Scientific Research⁹. Public universities such as the University of Tirana, the Polytechnic University of Tirana, and the Agricultural University of Tirana remain the main providers of research, postgraduate education, and doctoral training, while private institutions increasingly contribute to niche fields and international partnerships.¹⁰

Despite this institutional density, Albania is classified as an “Emerging Innovator,” with overall innovation performance at around 42% of the EU average and particularly weak scores in the “Human capital and research” dimension of the Global Innovation Index (rank 99 globally)¹¹. According to the European Commission's latest report on the expansion in the “Science and research” chapter, Albania increased funding for scientific research to 0.08% of GDP in 2023, from 0.05% in 2022 and 0.04% in 2021, however this is still far below the 1% of GDP target by 2030.

At the same time, important reforms are under way. The National Strategy for Research, Technology and Innovation 2023–2030 seeks to shift funding toward competitive schemes, introduce performance-based institutional funding, and establish a national system (U-CRIS/ACRIS) for systematically tracking research outputs and ranking universities based on their scientific performance. These reforms aim to counter long-standing challenges identified in European Research Area (ERA) assessments, including fragmented governance, weak links between research and the labour market, and insufficient performance incentives for academic staff.

In terms of internationalisation, Albanian HEIs have gradually increased their participation in EU framework programmes. In May 2023, a new centre for innovation called the Pyramid of Tirana was opened to the public. The centre hosts a TUMO Centre for Creative Technologies, providing educational programmes for young people in the region in areas such as robotics, animation, game development, music, and film. A good-practice example of regional research co-collaboration is NanoALB, which launched activities in 2020 under the auspices of the Academy of Sciences of Albania. It is a virtual centre that coordinates research activities in nanoscience and nanotechnologies across HEIs in the region. Overall, the academic and research landscape in Albania is characterised by a relatively dense network of HEIs operating within a modern legal framework, but constrained by chronic underinvestment, limited research infrastructure, and modest international competitiveness (OECD Competitive Outlook, 2024). For the Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana (FEUT), this context presents both a challenge and an opportunity: FEUT can act as a leading institution in strengthening applied research, improving Horizon Europe participation, and building structured partnerships with business and public institutions, thereby contributing to the gradual upgrading of Albania's R&I system.

⁹ European Education and Culture Executive Agency. (2025, September 15). *Albania – Overview of the education system (Eurydice country page)*

¹⁰ European Commission. (2023). *An overview of the RDI of higher education institutions in Albania (EU4Innovation report)*. European Union.

¹¹ European Commission. (2023). *European Research Area (ERA) country report: Albania (ERA Albania report)*. Regional Cooperation Council / European Commission.

4.1.2. Innovation Performance and University-industry Collaboration

Albania is ranked as an Emerging Innovator in the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS). In 2023 its innovation performance was about 41% of the EU average, below the Emerging Innovator group average, with relatively modest growth since 2016. Preliminary data for EIS 2025 confirm that Albania remains in the same performance group, with its score around 38–42% of the EU average, indicating that the innovation gap with the EU is narrowing only slowly.

The EIS profiles and recent analytical work on Albania's ecosystem highlight a mixed innovation performance:

- **Relative strengths** include:
 - Environment-related technologies and low-carbon solutions;
 - Sales of innovative products and a growing share of product innovators;
 - Rising levels of tertiary education and participation in lifelong learning;
 - Gradual improvement in citation impact of scientific publications.
- **Structural weaknesses** persist in:
 - Very low R&D expenditure in both the public and business sectors;
 - Below-EU levels of digital skills in the population;
 - Limited exports of medium- and high-tech goods, and modest knowledge-intensive services exports;
 - Weak “linkages” indicators, including public–private co-publications and the share of innovative SMEs collaborating with others, which have even deteriorated since 2016.

In the Global Innovation Index (GII) 2024, Albania ranked 84th of 133 economies, improving to around 67th place in the 2025 edition, and is considered to perform at expectations for its level of development.

The GI shows comparatively strong scores in Institutions, Infrastructure and Business sophistication, but very weak results in Human capital and research, Knowledge & technology outputs, Creative outputs and overall market sophistication, confirming that Albania invests in framework conditions yet struggles to translate these into high-value innovation outcomes.

Enterprise-level data from INSTAT's innovation survey 2020–2022 indicate that only a minority of enterprises are innovation-active, with participation concentrated among larger firms and knowledge-intensive services. Product, process and organisational innovations are present but unevenly distributed across sectors, and many firms report aborted or ongoing innovations rather than fully implemented ones, reflecting financial and capability constraints.

Recent studies on university–industry relations in Albania show that cooperation exists and is widely perceived as important, but it remains fragmented, personalised and weakly institutionalised.

A national study following the Triple Helix framework found that both university leaders and large companies overwhelmingly affirm that collaboration is taking place and should be expanded. However, cooperation is still dominated by “embedded” relationships based on personal contacts, internships and ad-hoc teaching activities, rather than structured, long-term innovation partnerships or systematic technology transfer (UET,2022).

Key findings from these studies include:

- Universities are seen by both sides as the main initiator of collaboration, while firms are less proactive and research centres and intermediary organisations play a limited role.
- Collaboration is strongest around education-related activities (internships, guest lectures, curriculum inputs) and to a lesser extent around research projects, consultancy and joint problem-solving, with very few examples of spin-offs, patenting or structured technology transfer.

- Senior university managers identify major challenges: limited funding, weak incentives for academic entrepreneurship, low internal capacity for project management and technology transfer, and the need to transform universities into more dynamic, entrepreneurial institutions that respond to market demands.

At policy level, an emerging framework is being built to strengthen these linkages:

- Law 80/2015 on Higher Education and Scientific Research gives departments more autonomy and explicitly recognises universities’ “third mission” – including income-generating research, innovation activities and cooperation with business.
- The National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation (NASRI) has, since 2022–2023, launched specific calls that finance joint academia–industry projects in technology and innovation, representing the first dedicated national instrument for such collaboration.
- The Business and Investment Development Strategy 2021–2027 and the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) stress the importance of innovation in SMEs and of stronger university–industry linkages in priority domains (e.g. tourism, agri-food, ICT, energy).
- Regional instruments, such as the Western Balkans Innovation Vouchers Scheme and the newly established EIT Community Hub Albania in Tirana, support collaboration by funding SMEs to purchase services from research organisations and by connecting Albanian universities and firms to European Knowledge and Innovation Communities.

Despite these developments, the overall assessment of recent analyses is that Albania’s university–industry collaboration remains in an early, evolving stage:

- Funding volumes are modest and project durations short;
- Support programmes are often pilot-based and donor-driven, with limited continuity;
- Governance of the innovation system is fragmented among several ministries and agencies, which complicates coordination and reduces visibility for firms;
- Data on collaboration outcomes (co-publications, patents, licenses, spin-offs) are still scarce, making monitoring difficult.

So far, some strengths and weaknesses regarding university–industry collaboration in Serbia, are identified. Some of them are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Strengths and weaknesses in university–industry collaboration in Albania

Strengths	Weaknesses
Growing awareness among universities and businesses of the importance of collaboration; the majority of surveyed leaders on both sides report existing cooperation.	Collaboration is mostly ad-hoc and based on personal contacts; few formal, long-term partnership frameworks or technology-transfer arrangements.
Legal framework (Law 80/2015) explicitly supports universities’ third mission and allows income-generating cooperation with industry.	Very low R&D intensity and limited dedicated funding for joint projects restrict the scale and continuity of collaborations.
Creation of NASRI calls for academia–industry projects and launch of regional instruments (Innovation Vouchers, EIT Hub) that promote joint activities.	Fragmented governance across multiple ministries and agencies, leading to overlapping measures and unclear responsibilities.
Emerging start-up and innovation scene in Tirana and other urban centres, with accelerators and mentorship programmes connecting students, researchers and entrepreneurs.	Limited institutional capacity in universities (few technology transfer offices, weak IP management, scarce professional staff for industry liaison).
Alignment with EU and regional agendas (ERA, S3, Western Balkans innovation initiatives) creates	SMEs often lack awareness, time and skills to engage in collaborative R&I, and many

opportunities for cross-border projects and knowledge exchange.	operate in low-technology sectors with limited innovation demand.
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Source: Author's compilation based on European Innovation Scoreboard country profiles, Global Innovation Index data, and recent analyses on Albania's innovation ecosystem and university–industry cooperation.

4.2. Key Challenges in Entrepreneurship and R&I Ecosystem in Albania

Entrepreneurship and research & innovation (R&I) are essential engines of Albania's economic transformation and social development. However, creating a truly supportive environment for innovative start-ups, SMEs and research-driven initiatives still faces important constraints. In the Albanian context, these challenges can be addressed to : Soft skills ; sustainability, technology transfer, and responsible innovation management.

4.2.1. Soft Skills

Entrepreneurial success requires a careful balance between technical and soft skills. While technical skills provide the necessary expertise, soft skills are crucial for problem-solving, teamwork, and effective communication. In Albania, several challenges hinder the development of soft skills:

- *Lack of Integration in Education Programs.* The Albanian education system does not include dedicated modules for soft skills development. As a result, graduates enter the workforce with technical knowledge but without essential interpersonal and professional skills.
- *Deficiencies in the Workforce.* Many employees lack soft skills such as resilience, problem-solving, and adaptability. Companies struggle to find professionals who can effectively communicate, network, and demonstrate business ethics.
- *HR Challenges in Talent Acquisition.* Managers and HR professionals seek employees with a strong mix of soft and technical skills. In an evolving business environment, resilience and adaptability are crucial for navigating uncertainty.
- *Barriers to Youth Employment.* Many young job seekers struggle with self-presentation and communication. Their job applications often lack clarity and direction, making it harder for them to secure employment.
- *Delayed Development of Soft Skills.* In other countries, soft skills training begins in high school through structured learning activities and practical assignments. Albanian students do not receive similar opportunities, delaying their ability to work collaboratively and handle real-world challenges.
- *Need for Government and Policy Support.* There is a lack of national programs or policies aimed at fostering soft skills development. The government should support initiatives such as specialized training programs to enhance these skills in both students and professionals.
- *Weak Link Between Education and Work Experience.* Students graduate with little to no practical work experience. Internships and hands-on learning should be integrated into educational programs to help students develop workplace-relevant soft skills.
- *Individualistic Mindset and Lack of Teamwork.* Many young Albanians struggle with teamwork and group collaboration. The absence of team-based learning experiences in their education contributes to this issue.

To address these challenges, Albania must prioritize soft skills training across all levels of education and professional development. Encouraging hands-on learning, mentorship programs, and

government-supported initiatives can help bridge the current gap and better prepare the workforce for future demands.

4.2.2. Sustainability

Sustainability is increasingly recognised as a core dimension of Albania’s economic transformation and EU integration, but it is not yet fully embedded in business models, innovation activities, or local development strategies. Albania has committed to the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans and to carbon neutrality by 2050, and has adopted key documents such as the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), the National Strategy on Waste Management and Action Plan 2020–2035, and the Roadmap towards a Circular Economy. Despite this progress, several structural challenges limit the integration of sustainability into entrepreneurship and R&I:

- *Limited uptake of sustainable practices by enterprises*- Although Albania has reduced municipal waste per capita and slightly increased its recycling rate (from 18.1% in 2020 to 18.9% in 2022), waste is still predominantly landfilled and a high share is mismanaged. Many SMEs—who represent almost the entire firm population—continue to treat environmental compliance as a cost rather than a source of competitive advantage or innovation. Circular business models, eco-design, energy efficiency and sustainable supply-chain practices remain at an early stage of adoption, especially outside larger urban centres and export-oriented firms.
- *Misalignment between economic growth and sustainable resource use*. The circular economy roadmap notes that, even though resource productivity in Albania has improved since 2016, the economy still uses a relatively high volume of physical resources per unit of GDP and faces persistent challenges in waste management, illegal landfills and marine litter. Transport remains a major CO₂ emitter, and investment in diversified renewables (beyond hydropower) and energy efficiency is still insufficient to fully align with EU climate ambitions.
- *Gaps in waste and recycling infrastructure*. The National Strategy on Waste Management aims for a 50% recycling rate for key household fractions by 2035, yet current infrastructure and collection systems are not sufficient to reach this target. Waste management services are more developed in urban areas, while rural municipalities often rely on basic dumping sites. A recent EU–OECD factsheet highlights that around 73% of total municipal waste is discharged untreated into the Mediterranean basin, including significant plastic leakage, underlining the lack of adequate separation, recycling and enforcement. These gaps limit the emergence of recycling, repair and reuse businesses and reduce opportunities for green entrepreneurship.
- *Low public awareness and uneven engagement with sustainability*. Albania “needs a cohesive approach” that includes raising awareness of circular economy concepts among authorities, businesses and households. While environmental topics have gained visibility, day-to-day behaviours such as waste separation, rational energy use and sustainable consumption remain inconsistent, particularly in rural areas and among low-income groups. This weakens demand for green products and services and reduces incentives for firms to invest in sustainable innovation.
- *Limited use of digital and data-driven solutions for green transition*. Digitalisation could significantly support energy savings, optimisation of logistics, monitoring of emissions and waste flows, and new green business models. However, OECD and EU analysis for Western Balkans SMEs indicates that many Albanian firms face funding constraints and capacity gaps that prevent them from investing in advanced digital and green technologies. This slows down the diffusion of smart meters, environmental management systems, and data-driven circular practices in the private sector.

Taken together, these challenges show that Albania's entrepreneurial and R&I ecosystem is still in the early stages of integrating sustainability as a core driver of competitiveness and innovation. For FEUT, this creates both responsibility and opportunity:

- to **embed sustainability and circular economy principles** in curricula, student projects and research agendas;
- to **support SMEs and local governments** through applied research, advisory services and living labs focused on waste, energy and resource efficiency;
- and to **contribute evidence** for better-designed economic instruments and policies that can accelerate the country's green and circular transition.

4.2.3. Technology Transfer and Open Innovation

In order to build a solid foundation for sustainable entrepreneurship within an open innovation ecosystem in Albania, several structural challenges still need to be addressed. Although important steps have been taken, technology transfer (TT) and open innovation remain at an early stage of development. Drawing on recent analyses, several key challenges can be identified.

- *Unsatisfactory Knowledge Transfer Between Actors in the Innovation Ecosystem.* Despite the existence of the National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation (NASRI), which is mandated to finance R&I projects and connect businesses with academic staff, collaboration between universities, research institutes and firms is still largely fragmented and project-based. Recent assessments underline that applied research contracts with companies remain limited, and that only a few universities have experience in supporting spin-offs or structured industry partnerships. As a result, research outcomes are only partially translated into market-oriented solutions or productivity gains.
- *New but Underdeveloped Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) and Support Structures.* Several universities in Albania have created specialised offices for technology and intellectual property transfer, as well as incubator and entrepreneurship programmes (for example, multi-university initiatives such as *Tirana Inc.*). However, these TTOs are relatively new, often understaffed, and still building expertise in IP management, licensing, and contract negotiation. They also face shortages of equipment and prototyping facilities, which limits their ability to support early-stage innovation projects.
- *Cultural and Skills Barriers to Open Innovation.* Studies on technology and knowledge transfer in Albania point to cultural resistance to change, limited managerial experience with innovation, and weak cooperation culture across sectors. Many companies, especially in traditional sectors, still compete primarily on cost rather than innovation, and managers often lack the skills – and time – to engage in collaborative R&D, experiment with new technologies, or build long-term partnerships with universities and start-ups. Brain drain and intense competition for skilled workers further reduce the availability of talent for innovative enterprises and spin-offs.
- *Limited Practice-based Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education.* Although entrepreneurship is increasingly present in university curricula and various projects (including EIT-supported initiatives) aim to build entrepreneurial skills among students and academic staff, practice-oriented learning – such as innovation projects with companies, challenge-based courses, and structured support for student start-ups – is still not systematically integrated across higher education. This limits the pipeline of graduates capable of operating at the interface between research, business, and society, and slows the emergence of an “open innovation mindset” that sees collaboration, experimentation and risk-taking as normal parts of academic and business life.

4.2.4. Innovation Process Management

In Albania, key challenges can be summarised as follows:

- *Fragmented cooperation between actors in the ecosystem.* Collaboration among universities, public institutions, business associations, incubators, and hubs is often short term and project-based, which limits continuity and learning across initiatives.
- *Limited strategic innovation mindset in firms.* Many enterprises, especially SMEs, still compete mainly on low costs and informal networks; managers often view innovation as risky and expensive, rather than a systematic tool for competitiveness.
- *Weak innovation-oriented organisational cultures.* Few companies have internal mechanisms for idea generation, experimentation, or employee-driven improvement, and staff rarely receive training or incentives related to innovation.
- *Insufficient support for sustainable and circular innovation in SMEs.* Although policies stress green and circular transition, support instruments remain fragmented and mostly pilot-based, so only a limited number of firms can test and scale sustainable innovations.
- *Gaps between academic research and business needs.* Universities work on sustainability and innovation topics, but companies often need faster, highly practical solutions; intermediary structures to translate research into market-ready innovations are still underdeveloped.

5. Key Pillars of the R&I Strategy

The R&I document is built around three mutually reinforcing pillars:

- Strengthening research excellence and international visibility,
- Enhancing technology transfer and exploitation of knowledge,
- Fostering innovative and sustainable entrepreneurship.

These pillars are fully aligned with the Development Strategy of the University of Tirana 2023–2028, in particular with the chapter on research and innovation, and are designed to support the university's overall vision of becoming a leading research-intensive institution in Albania and the region. They aim to align FEUT with European standards, support Albania's transition toward a knowledge-based economy, and generate tangible benefits for society and the business community.

5.1. Research Excellence

This pillar focuses on improving the quality, relevance and impact of research at FEUT, in line with the University of Tirana's strategic objectives for research and innovation. Key directions include:

- Consolidating research groups and thematic priorities in line with national, regional and EU agendas (e.g., green transition, digital economy, inclusive growth),
- Increasing the volume and quality of scientific publications in indexed journals and reputable conferences,
- Strengthening participation and leadership in Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, COST and other international research programmes,
- Supporting early-career researchers and PhD candidates through mentoring, training and access to international networks,
- Promoting open science practices, including data sharing, open access publishing and transparent research methodologies,
- Encouraging policy-relevant and practice-oriented research that informs public policy and business decision-making in Albania.

5.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

This pillar aims to translate FEUT's knowledge and research results into practical solutions, services and innovations for the economy and society, supporting the University of Tirana's goal of strengthening its "third mission" and societal impact. Priority actions include:

- Strengthening structures for technology and knowledge transfer (e.g. liaison units, project offices, increase capacities)
- Promoting collaborative research and consulting projects with businesses, public institutions and civil society organisations
- Supporting the creation of start-up initiatives based on research results or staff/student expertise
- Using living labs, pilot projects and demonstration cases to test and validate innovative solutions with real users and stakeholders
- Facilitating access to European and national innovation funding schemes through joint proposals with companies and other universities
- Tracking and showcasing successful cases of technology transfer, innovation projects and policy impact generated by FEUT.

5.3. Innovative Entrepreneurship

This pillar focuses on developing entrepreneurial mindsets, skills and ventures within FEUT and its wider ecosystem, in coherence with the University of Tirana's strategic commitment to entrepreneurship and societal engagement. Main components include:

- Integrating entrepreneurship, innovation management and digital skills across bachelor, master's and doctoral programmes
- Providing students and staff with hands-on opportunities to work on real business and societal challenges (e.g. project-based courses, hackathons, case competitions)
- Supporting student and alumni start-ups through mentoring, networking and access to professional services
- Building partnerships with incubators, accelerators, chambers of commerce, financial institutions and business associations in Albania and the region
- Promoting green, social and digital entrepreneurship aligned with the SDGs, the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans and Albania's Smart Specialisation priorities
- Encouraging inclusive entrepreneurship, with targeted support for women, youth and under-represented groups
- Organising regular events (entrepreneurship days, investor meetups, demo days, guest lectures) to connect the FEUT community with the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem

6. Implementation Framework

Developing research and innovation at the Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana (FEUT), requires not only clear goals but also the enabling conditions that make progress possible. These include effective governance, alignment with national and EU policies, and strong support systems for academic staff and students.

This chapter outlines:

- how UT and FEUT are governed and linked to national strategies,
- the role of universities in Albania's innovation system, and

- key areas of action – cultural change, international cooperation, stakeholder communication, digital transformation and the green transition.

Together, these elements contribute to a more open, collaborative and competitive research and innovation environment that supports Albania’s development and EU integration.

Governance

Research and innovation in Albania are shaped by the Ministry of Education and Sports (MES), the legal framework for higher education and scientific research, and the National Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) 2023–2030. MES defines policy priorities, aligns them with the European Research Area, and supports reforms related to EU accession.

The National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation (NASRI) serves as the central funding and implementation body. It evaluates and finances research projects and infrastructures, supports innovation programmes, and acts as a national contact point for Horizon Europe, COST and other schemes. Additional institutions involved in smart specialisation, statistics, industrial property and digitalisation also contribute to shaping the R&I landscape.

Within this system, UT—and FEUT in particular—plays a pivotal role. UT is the country’s largest public university and holder of the “HR Excellence in Research” award, demonstrating its commitment to strengthening research careers. FEUT contributes to national priorities through doctoral programmes, academic research and EU-funded projects in economics, business, governance and sustainable development, collaborating closely with NASRI, ministries and international partners.

National R&I Strategy

Albania’s strategic direction for research and innovation is defined by the STI Strategy 2023–2030, which focuses on strengthening institutions, modernising infrastructure, expanding international cooperation and increasing the societal and economic benefits of research. The strategy emphasises closer alignment with the European Research Area, higher participation in Horizon Europe and wider uptake of research results in public policy and the private sector.

A second key pillar is the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) 2025–2030, which identifies three priority domains: renewable energy and natural resources, sustainable and diversified tourism, and a healthy and sustainable food chain. These are supported by cross-cutting measures in digitalisation, human capital and a more innovation-friendly business environment.

These frameworks guide the development of UT’s and FEUT’s institutional agendas. FEUT’s focus on the green transition, digital economy, entrepreneurship and inclusive growth supports national R&I priorities. Through interdisciplinary research, doctoral training, knowledge-transfer initiatives and collaboration with businesses and public institutions, FEUT translates national strategic goals into concrete projects and partnerships.

Universities

Albania’s higher education system includes public and private institutions, with the University of Tirana as the largest and most comprehensive. Albania’s research performance has gradually improved: the European Innovation Scoreboard 2024 notes growth in the “attractiveness of research systems,” including an increase in highly cited publications.

UT and FEUT are among the country’s most active participants in international programmes. UT has received over €1.6 million from Horizon 2020 and Erasmus+, and participation in Horizon Europe has grown significantly in recent years, with more institutions and larger project budgets involved.

Universities—and UT/FEUT in particular—contribute to Albania’s R&I system in several ways:

- **Knowledge production.** They generate fundamental and applied research in economics, business, digitalisation and sustainability, providing evidence for innovation and policymaking.

- **Bridging academia with industry and society.** FEUT collaborates with ministries, municipalities, banks and enterprises through joint projects, internships and advisory activities that transfer knowledge into practice.
- **Gateways to Europe.** Participation in Horizon Europe, Erasmus+ and COST raises research quality, strengthens networks and aligns Albania with European standards.
- **Support for policymaking.** FEUT experts contribute to national strategies such as STI 2023–2030 and S3 by providing data, analysis and policy recommendations.

Cultural change

Albania's innovation ecosystem is still considered “nascent,” with limited innovation capacity and entrepreneurial skills, particularly among youth. Strengthening innovation culture requires coordinated action among universities, businesses, government and civil society.

Recent legislation, including the Start-Up Law (2022) and its amendments, demonstrates increasing policy recognition of entrepreneurship. These measures establish incentives, support services and clearer procedures for start-ups. Programmes such as “EU for Innovation” and activities of the EIT Community Hub further support ecosystem development by mentoring young founders and linking Albania to European innovation networks.

Universities are increasingly integrating entrepreneurship into curricula and student activities through competitions, hackathons, incubator collaborations and project-based learning. More systematic recognition of knowledge-transfer activities and incentives for staff and students would strengthen engagement with the private and public sectors.

For companies and institutions, cultural change means viewing innovation as a long-term investment. Co-financed R&I schemes, municipal innovation programmes and innovation-oriented public procurement all reinforce this shift. Highlighting successful Albanian start-ups, researchers and youth-led initiatives can help build public trust and promote an entrepreneurial mindset.

International orientation

International orientation aims to enhance the university's global profile and cooperation in sustainable entrepreneurship and R&I. Key actions include expanding participation in Horizon Europe, Erasmus+ and COST projects, introducing Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL) modules, and engaging diaspora experts as mentors and partners.

Expected outcomes include a higher number of international projects with a sustainability component, more joint international activities per academic year and increased involvement of diaspora experts providing new perspectives and best practices.

Stakeholders' communication

To strengthen FEUT's role within Albania's innovation ecosystem, effective communication with internal and external stakeholders is essential. FEUT already promotes project results and activities through its website, where information on projects, partners, courses and key indicators is regularly presented.

This will be complemented by targeted communication activities under “Sustainable Entrepreneurship at FEUT,” using social media, podcasts and similar platforms to highlight achievements and share best practices. Progress will be monitored through regular updates of the online dashboard, the number and reach of communication products, and stakeholder engagement in forums and events.

7. Expected outcomes and impact

At the national level, the R&I Strategy aims to reshape Albania's research environment and fostering strong collaborative networks between academia, industry, government, and civil society. By expanding access to international programmes such as Horizon Europe and aligning national policy with the European Research Area, the strategy lays the groundwork for a more competitive and internationally integrated research community. The University of Tirana's Development Strategy reinforces this national vision. The expected impact at the university level includes a significant rise in research excellence, and the creation of an academic environment where innovation is embedded across disciplines. Through enhanced cooperation with the private sector, the establishment of innovation-oriented research hubs, and the integration of sustainability principles in teaching and research, UT is expected to become a key driver of Albania's innovation ecosystem. Together, these two strategies converge on a shared impact: the strengthening of Albania's entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem. Their combined impact is expected to stimulate new forms of university–industry cooperation, expand opportunities for technology transfer and bring outcomes as follows:

- Increased research quality and visibility - Higher number of publications in indexed journals and reputable conferences, and stronger international recognition of FEUT as a research-oriented faculty.
- Stronger alignment with EU and national priority areas- Research groups working on themes such as green transition, digital economy and inclusive growth, in line with Albanian strategies and EU R&I agendas.
- Enhanced participation in international programmes – Greater involvement and leadership of FEUT staff in Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, COST and other international research and innovation projects.
- Improved research infrastructure and capacity – Better access to data, digital tools, specialised software and labs, along with stronger support for PhD candidates and early-career researchers.
- More effective technology transfer and societal impact – Increased number of collaborative projects with business and public institutions, clearer IP management practices, and more visible cases of research informing policy and practice.
- A more entrepreneurial and skills-oriented learning environment – Systematic integration of entrepreneurship, innovation management and digital skills into study programmes, with students regularly engaged in real-life business and societal challenges.
- Stronger innovation ecosystem linkages and contribution to Albania's development– Deeper partnerships with incubators, accelerators, business associations and financial institutions, reinforcing FEUT's role—aligned with the University of Tirana Strategy 2023–2028—in supporting a competitive, sustainable and knowledge-based Albanian economy.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1. Strategic Priorities

- Improving pathways for knowledge and technology exchange between universities, businesses, and public institutions, helping research outcomes transition more smoothly into practical use and commercialisation.
- Cultivating a proactive and innovative mindset among students and researchers, with an emphasis on designing solutions that integrate sustainability from the outset.

- Supporting the growth of responsible and sustainability-oriented business initiatives, encouraging researchers and students to embed environmental and social considerations into their entrepreneurial ideas.
- Strengthening the interpersonal and professional competencies of academics and emerging entrepreneurs, ensuring they possess the communication, leadership, and collaborative skills needed to thrive in contemporary innovation environments.
- Expanding cooperation across academic disciplines and external sectors, creating stronger links between education, research, industry, and community actors to reinforce a vibrant innovation ecosystem.
- Encouraging the transformation of research findings into real-world applications, motivating the creation of new services, solutions, and technologies that address societal needs and contribute to national development.
- Nurturing an environment where experimentation, co-creation, and continuous improvement are integral, empowering students and researchers to engage meaningfully with external stakeholders and actively participate in shaping innovation processes.

8.2. Next Steps for Policy Implementation

- Develop clear operational guidelines to support the rollout of strategic actions at institutional and national levels.
- Strengthen coordination mechanisms between institutions, universities, businesses and research agencies to ensure consistent implementation.
- Allocate targeted funding to priority areas, especially those related to research capacity, innovation support, and sustainability initiatives.
- Introduce monitoring tools and performance indicators to track progress and adjust actions when necessary.
- Expand training and capacity-building activities for researchers, administrators, and decision-makers to support policy adoption.
- Enhance collaboration with industry, civil society, and international partners to accelerate research commercialisation and innovation uptake.
- Conduct periodic assessments and stakeholder consultations to refine implementation strategies based on feedback.
- Integrate digital solutions to streamline administrative processes, reporting, and communication across institutions.
- Encourage universities to align internal strategies and action plans with national policy objectives for research and innovation.

8.3. Recommendations for Long-term Sustainability and EU Integration

- Diversify funding for research and innovation – Advocate for increased national R&I funding and systematically combine it with EU, regional and private funds, prioritising multiannual, competitive schemes.
- Prioritise EU-aligned thematic focus areas – Concentrate research and innovation efforts on priority domains from Horizon Europe, Smart Specialisation, the Green Agenda and the Digital Agenda for the Western Balkans.

- Professionalise project development and management – Build permanent internal capacity (units/teams) for Horizon Europe and other EU programmes: project design, administration, impact reporting, etc.
- Strengthen technology transfer and IP ecosystems – Focus on tech-transfer services and partnerships with regional innovation hubs to support commercialisation, spin-offs and licensing.
- Deepen university–industry–government–civil society collaboration
 - Formalise long-term partnerships (framework agreements, living labs, advisory councils) to jointly design research agendas, teaching content and innovation projects.
- Invest in human capital and reduce brain drain – Offer attractive career paths, mentoring and international mobility for young researchers and entrepreneurs, linked to clear conditions for return and reintegration.
- Mainstream sustainability and responsible research
 - Systematically integrate SDGs, ESG criteria and ethics (RRI) into research design, teaching, technology transfer and entrepreneurship support.
- Enhance data, monitoring and evaluation
 - Develop simple indicators and an internal R&I dashboard to track outputs, outcomes and EU alignment, using results to adjust priorities and resource allocation.
- Position FEUT and UT as regional R&I partners
 - Proactively seek Western Balkans and EU consortia leadership roles, promoting FEUT and the University of Tirana as reliable partners for long-term EU integration in research and innovation.

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R&I STRATEGY OF FEUSK, NORTH MACEDONIA

1. Executive Summary: Purpose and scope of the R&I strategy

This Research & Innovation (R&I) Strategy defines how the University Entrepreneurship and Innovation Center (UEIC) will operationalize the Entrepreneurial University model by acting as the central connector and “one-stop shop” of the university R&I ecosystem, linking internal university capacities (faculties, institutes, laboratories, TTOs, incubators/accelerators) with government, industry, investors and society, and translating national priorities into functional pathways (projects → prototypes → spin-offs → market impact). The scope covers the full “knowledge-to-impact” chain: research excellence and infrastructure, talent development, EU project participation (“grant-to-impact”), technology transfer and IP, start-ups/spin-offs and commercialization finance, multi-level networking, and transparent impact measurement supported by CoARA principles. The Strategy is designed for a widening/low R&I intensity context and aligns tightly with EU integration pathways and national policy frameworks. It is anchored in the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) 2024–2027, using S3 priority domains to structure thematic platforms, human-capital pipelines, infrastructure upgrades, and TT/IP frameworks. It also strengthens participation in EU programmes and networks: Horizon Europe, COST and EUREKA, as a route to competitive funding, partnerships, and mission-oriented collaboration that can offset domestic constraints. Finally, it links the university pipeline to national innovation and SME instruments, including INOVA and the SME-oriented funding mix (credit guarantees, venture/hybrid funds, green finance) to enable proof/validation and scale-up. Implementation is expected to deliver: stronger S3-aligned research excellence; upgraded shared infrastructure (“labs-as-a-service”); a stronger talent pipeline; a professional “grant-to-impact” pathway with higher EU participation; institutionalized Quadruple-Helix partnerships; a functional TT and commercialization system (contract research, licensing, spin-offs) with clear incentives; easier IP support and stronger commercialization readiness; a clearer finance pathway (concept→seed→scale); and CoARA-aligned performance measurement with annual public impact reporting.

2. Introduction

Entrepreneurial ecosystems are increasingly recognized as catalysts for innovation, economic growth, and regional development. An entrepreneurial ecosystem represents “a set of interdependent actors and factors that are governed in such a way that they enable productive entrepreneurship” (Stam, 2015). These actors and factors include start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), universities and research institutes, investors and funding sources, supportive government policies, infrastructure, and cultural elements that together foster innovation and new venture creation (Huang et al., 2023). In a vibrant ecosystem, entrepreneurs do not operate in isolation. Moreover, they draw on networks of talent, knowledge, finance, and institutions that help turn ideas into commercial products and services. Importantly, research and innovation (R&I) are at the heart of such ecosystems: scientific research generates new knowledge and technologies, while innovation applies these insights to create economic and societal value. Investing in R&I is therefore key to growth and job creation, as it increases productivity and competitiveness through new products, processes, and businesses (WeBalkans, n.d.).

Conversely, regions that neglect R&I risk stagnation, as innovation gaps directly hamper economic performance (Owen et al., 2021). In recent years, global policy discourse has emphasized building innovation-driven ecosystems to spur sustainable development. The European Union (EU), for example, launched programs under Horizon 2020 and now Horizon Europe specifically to “widen”

participation in R&I, thus helping less R&D-intensive countries strengthen their ecosystems and bridge the innovation gap with leading economies (Pollex & Lenschow, 2018). Notably, the Western Balkans, consisting of Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia and Serbia, fall into this category and have been designated as Associated Widening Countries under Horizon Europe (Radovanovic et al., 2023). All have ambitions to integrate into the European Research Area and eventually the EU, making the development of robust entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystems a strategic priority.

This R&I Strategy was developed through an evidence-informed and participatory process designed for a widening / low-resource context, where fragmentation, low R&D intensity, and weak academia–industry linkages directly constrain the “research-to-impact” pathway. The work started with desk research and document analysis, synthesizing the current state of the national R&I and entrepreneurship ecosystem, with a specific focus on structural bottlenecks (funding, human capital, research infrastructure, IP barriers, and technology transfer constraints). Second, the team conducted a policy-alignment to ensure that proposed priorities, programs, and KPIs are implementable and “fundable” through national instruments and EU mechanisms—especially the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3), EU integration pathways, and participation channels such as Horizon Europe, COST, and EUREKA. Third, the Strategy integrates benchmarking and lessons learned from EU partner institutions, and it also draws on a dedicated set of guidelines for local and regional policymakers developed to specify recommendations for upgrading entrepreneurial ecosystems in North Macedonia. These recommendations were produced as part of the USE IPM project through a rigorous mixed-method research process, combining focus groups, the Delphi method, and a needs analysis survey, conducted across the four countries between September 2023 and November 2024.

The following section provides an overview of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in the Republic of North Macedonia, situated within the broader group of widening countries, examines the importance of R&I for its development, outlines alignment with EU and national strategies, and discusses the crucial role of universities in implementing and sustaining these efforts.

2.1 Overview of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem in North Macedonia

North Macedonia, like other Western Balkan countries such as Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia, shares the context of a transitional economy with a nascent yet growing entrepreneurial ecosystem. Over the past decade, innovation performance in North Macedonia and the wider Western Balkans has improved, but the region still lags behind the European average on most indicators (WeBalkans, n.d.). These countries exhibit strong potential with a young and educated talent pool (including a substantial diaspora), and emerging tech start-up communities, yet they face significant structural challenges.

One fundamental issue is underinvestment in research and development (R&D). All Western Balkan economies remain far below the EU’s target of 3% of GDP investment in R&D. In fact, R&D expenditure ranges from 0.2% to 0.9% of GDP, compared to an OECD/EU average of about 2.4% (OECD, 2024a). In the case of North Macedonia, R&D intensity remains below 0.4% of GDP, confirming that the country is also significantly under both the EU target and the EU/OECD average (GNM – Government of North Macedonia, 2023; OECD, 2024a). Such figures illustrate the innovation gap where despite huge growth prospects, North Macedonia and the Western Balkan region as a whole still lack sufficient research infrastructure and human capital (partly due to brain drain, too) to fully exploit their innovation potential.

Another major challenge in these ecosystems is the weak linkage between academia and industry, leading to poor commercialization of research. Traditionally, universities and public research institutes in the Western Balkans have operated in silos, with few incentives or mechanisms to collaborate with the business sector. In North Macedonia, similar patterns are evident, with

universities carrying out most research but university–industry collaboration and structured technology transfer mechanisms still at an early stage, resulting in relatively few joint R&D projects, spin-offs and commercialization cases compared to the country’s scientific potential (GNM, 2023). Indeed, “co-creation between R&D institutes and industry remains the weakest link across the region’s Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) systems”, and this lack of collaboration has “hampered the commercialization of research”, meaning the region is not fully capitalizing on its scientific capabilities (OECD, 2024a). Indicators of technology transfer and innovation uptake are correspondingly low. For instance, the income that Western Balkan institutions receive from licensing patents or other intellectual property (a proxy for research commercialization) is negligible, while receipts from foreign use of domestic IP are largely stagnant at less than 0.1% of GDP (OECD, 2024a). In North Macedonia, balance-of-payments statistics and OECD assessments likewise show that receipts from royalties, licence fees and other intellectual property–related services remain very small relative to GDP, indicating that the commercialization of domestic research outputs and export of knowledge-intensive services are still at an early stage (OECD, 2024b; NBRNM, 2023).

Similarly, relatively few firms introduce new products or processes, considering innovative activity in the private sector is limited, especially among SMEs that dominate these economies. Many SMEs lack the resources and know-how to engage in R&I, and there is a shortage of entrepreneurial support services and mentorship in advanced technologies (Gashi Ahmeti & Fetaj, 2021).

Access to funding is another critical bottleneck in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. Domestic venture capital and angel investor networks remain embryonic in the Western Balkans. Aside from a few exceptions (such as an EU-supported regional venture fund and occasional cross-border investors), the region has a scarcity of “smart money” (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), 2021). This scarcity of seed and early-stage capital makes it difficult for start-ups to scale up or for research spin-offs to reach the market. Local banks are often reluctant to lend to innovation-driven businesses deemed too risky, and public funding for start-up incubation is limited (Cingolani, 2025). Consequently, promising entrepreneurs frequently relocate to larger markets to seek investment or rely on donor-funded grant programs (Cingolani, 2025).

All these factors, related to low R&D spending, few researchers, weak academia–industry links, and limited financing, form an ecosystem that is still developing rather than mature. However, the foundation is being laid for improvement as innovation hubs, tech parks and incubators have been established in cities like Skopje, Belgrade, Sarajevo and Tirana, a growing number of tech start-ups (especially in ICT and software outsourcing) are gaining traction, and governments have begun adopting reforms to nurture entrepreneurship. The potential and talent are there, as the EU notes (WeBalkans, n.d.), but substantial efforts are needed to unlock it.

2.2. The Importance of Research and Innovation for Ecosystem Development

Strengthening R&I is crucial for developing the entrepreneurial ecosystem in North Macedonia. This priority is reflected in national strategic documents, which frame research and innovation as key levers for higher value added, export competitiveness and retaining skilled labour (GNM, 2023; Ministry of Economy and Labour, 2024). Globally, R&I drives economic growth, productivity, and job creation. Closing the innovation gap is not just technical but a socio-economic priority, as stronger innovation performance can diversify economies, move industries up the value chain, and create high-quality jobs, which are vital for sustainable development and for preventing the outflow of talent (Fayyaz & Bartha, 2025).

This requires fostering knowledge-based activities and leveraging research to produce new products, services, and processes competitive in European and global markets. Equally important is enhancing mechanisms that translate research into market applications, such as effective intellectual

property (IP) rights, technology transfer offices, incubators, and industry partnerships. Robust IP protection ensures inventors and investors can benefit from innovation, which is particularly crucial in emerging ecosystems where private R&D involves higher risks (Burrell et al., 2023).

Technology transfer bridges the gap between research and commercialization, enabling universities and research institutes to license inventions to businesses or support spin-offs. This “third mission” of universities, going beyond teaching and research, is central to creating economic impact from scientific discoveries (Rubens et al., 2017). Successful innovation ecosystems, like those in Western Europe or the US, show how supportive policies, such as the Bayh-Dole Act, empower universities to patent and commercialize research outputs, serving as a model for North Macedonia.

Improving IP management and strengthening academia-industry collaboration through joint projects, contract research, and innovation hubs can enhance commercialization outcomes, yielding new enterprises, licensing revenues, and innovative solutions to regional challenges. A vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem grounded in R&I also requires diverse funding pathways – from public research grants and incubator support to venture capital and bank financing to help ideas progress from labs to markets. Expanding these financial structures will enable more innovations to survive the critical transition between research and commercialization.

Finally, integrating digital and green transformations into the R&I agenda is both necessary and strategic for North Macedonia. The world faces twin transitions: the digital revolution, driving widespread adoption of technologies like AI, IoT, and Industry 4.0, and the green transition, which restructures energy, transport, and industry toward sustainability and climate neutrality (Bianchini et al., 2023). R&I is pivotal for advancing both transitions, from renewable energy and clean mobility to digital infrastructure and skills development.

Aligning with these trends is essential for the country, both to tackle pressing societal challenges and to integrate into EU frameworks. The EU’s Green Deal targets climate neutrality by 2050, with the Western Balkans committed through the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans (Ignjatović et al., 2024). As an EU candidate country, North Macedonia has endorsed this agenda and is progressively aligning its energy, climate and environmental policies with EU Green Deal objectives (GNM, 2023). Similarly, the EU’s Digital Agenda and Digital Decade initiatives promote digital innovation and infrastructure development across member and partner countries by 2030 (Eckert, 2024). Embracing these transitions will position North Macedonia as competitive and future-ready within the European innovation landscape.

2.3. Strategic Alignment with EU and National Policies

As the Republic of North Macedonia progresses toward EU membership, aligning its R&I efforts with EU and national policy frameworks is essential for maximizing impact, accessing support and partnerships, and most importantly, ensuring comparability and generalizability. Central to this alignment are Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3), Horizon Europe, the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans, and national innovation plans, which frame North Macedonia’s integration into the European Research Area alongside other widening countries in the Western Balkans.

Smart Specialisation (S3) has emerged as one of the crucial tools for directing R&I investments into priority sectors where each country has competitive strengths. For North Macedonia, the Smart Specialisation Strategy, finalised in 2023, defines priority domains for the 2024–2027 period and provides a strategic framework for orienting public and private R&I investments (GNM, 2023; OECD, 2024b). There are four vertical and two horizontal priority domains: Smart agriculture and food with higher added value; Information and communication technologies (ICT); Electro-mechanical Industry – Industry 4.0; Sustainable materials and smart buildings; Energy for future and Tourism, as horizontal domains, have interrelatedness and cross-innovation with vertical ones. For North Macedonia’s

universities, this provides a clear basis for aligning curricula, research agendas and collaboration projects with S3 priority domains and EU policy directions.

Participation in Horizon Europe (2021–2027) is another key pillar of North Macedonia’s R&I alignment with the EU. Through its association to Horizon Europe, North Macedonia can join EU research networks, access competitive funding and strengthen scientific excellence in areas such as climate, energy, health and digital innovation (Western Balkans Info Hub, 2023; GNM, 2023). At the same time, Horizon Europe’s dedicated Widening Participation measures (e.g. Twinning, Teaming and Excellence Hubs) are particularly relevant for North Macedonia and its Western Balkan peers, as they build capacity, upgrade research management practices and link local institutions with top EU partners (Western Balkans Info Hub, 2023). National R&I strategies increasingly seek to leverage these instruments by encouraging HEIs and firms to participate in calls, setting co-funding mechanisms and strengthening support structures for project development and implementation.

The Green Agenda for the Western Balkans (GAWB) mirrors the EU’s Green Deal, committing the region to carbon neutrality by 2050 and focusing on decarbonization, circular economy, sustainable agriculture, pollution reduction, and biodiversity (Ignjatović et al., 2024). North Macedonia has endorsed the Green Agenda and is gradually aligning its energy, climate and environmental policies with EU Green Deal objectives, creating demand for innovation in renewable energy, energy efficiency, low-carbon materials and sustainable technologies (GNM, 2023). This alignment also prepares Macedonian companies for EU markets by meeting environmental standards and opens pathways to EU initiatives such as Horizon Europe’s Climate cluster and the Innovation Fund. Digital transformation is similarly integrated through regional efforts like the Western Balkan Digital Agenda, enhancing connectivity, e-governance and support for ICT start-ups, **with North Macedonia using these frameworks to guide investments in digital infrastructure and skills in line with the EU’s Digital Decade goals (GNM, 2023).**

Each country also has national strategies aimed at boosting innovation, and in North Macedonia the innovation policy framework focuses on improving the business climate, digital infrastructure and research excellence through instruments such as the Fund for Innovation and Technological Development (FITD), which as of 2025 is being reorganised into the Agency for Innovation, Scientific and Technological Development and Entrepreneurship (INOVA), and reforms in science, higher education and enterprise support (Fund for Innovation and Technological Development of North Macedonia, 2021; GNM, 2023). Complementary policy documents, including the SME Strategy 2025–2030 and the Growth Acceleration Plan 2022–2026, propose instruments such as credit guarantees, venture and hybrid funds, green finance and better access to EU facilities to crowd in private capital and diversify funding beyond grants (Ministry of Economy and Labour, 2024). Regional cooperation frameworks like the Berlin Process and the EU’s Economic and Investment Plan (EIP) further support these efforts, with the EIP allocating €9 billion to stimulate connectivity, human capital and innovation across the Western Balkans, from which North Macedonia is a direct beneficiary (Kaca, 2021).

To sum up, strategic alignment with EU and national policies ensures policy coherence, resource efficiency, and deeper integration of North Macedonia’s R&I system into European networks, greatly enhancing the prospects for building a robust entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem in the country while situating it within the broader group of widening Western Balkan economies.

2.4. The Role of Universities in Implementation and Sustainability of the Strategy

Universities are central to research and innovation ecosystems, particularly in emerging economies like North Macedonia. Beyond their traditional missions of teaching and research, modern universities play a crucial “third mission” of economic and societal engagement, encompassing entrepreneurship, technology transfer, and regional development (Rubens et al., 2017).

First, universities must strengthen their role as knowledge hubs, producing research that translates into marketable products and services. Many universities in the region are establishing technology transfer offices, incubators, and innovation centres to facilitate this process (Radosavljevic et al., 2024; Chichevaliev et al., 2023). Pilot programs, such as start-up accelerators, demonstrate growing momentum (Ćudić et al., 2021), though broader scaling is needed. Encouraging faculty entrepreneurship, integrating entrepreneurship training into curricula, and promoting industry-sponsored research are vital steps for universities to function as engines of innovation and economic development (Chichevaliev et al., 2023; Ramadani et al., 2023).

Second, universities are key to building human capital for the innovation economy. They train the next generation of entrepreneurs, engineers, and scientists. To support digital and green transitions, universities must equip students with skills in areas like information, communication and technology, artificial intelligence, climate science, and innovation management (Ordóñez de Pablos et al., 2023). However, gaps remain in aligning higher education programs with Smart Specialisation priorities and evolving market needs. Updating curricula, creating interdisciplinary programs in fields such as renewable energy or data science, and fostering partnerships with industry are crucial to ensure graduates are innovation ready. Additionally, universities should expand lifelong learning and reskilling programs to support workforce adaptation to technological change (Biney, 2023).

Third, universities serve as connectors within the innovation ecosystem, acting as anchors for collaboration between academia, industry, government, and civil society. In the Western Balkans, universities are increasingly participating in public-private innovation councils, EU-funded joint projects, and events like hackathons (Ramadani et al., 2023; Tekin et al., 2021). This shift from linear knowledge transfer to co-creation enables stakeholders to collaboratively define challenges and develop solutions. Universities also provide critical research infrastructure, such as labs, equipment and testing facilities, that start-ups and SMEs might otherwise lack (Cao et al., 2024; Ramadani et al., 2023). By opening these resources and facilitating partnerships, universities elevate technological capabilities across the ecosystem. Over time, such collaborations should evolve into permanent structures like joint R&D centres and innovation clusters.

Finally, ensuring the sustainability of the innovation strategy depends on embedding entrepreneurial activities into universities' core missions. Successful initiatives, like incubators or technology parks, can become lasting assets, attracting ongoing funding and talent. Universities that adopt supportive policies like rewarding innovation activities and integrating entrepreneurship into their institutional culture can drive continuous renewal and innovation (Cao et al., 2024). This cultural shift, already visible in growing student competitions and innovation labs, will help cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset among graduates.

Undisputedly, universities in North Macedonia are pillars for building sustainable innovation ecosystems. Their contributions to research, talent development, and ecosystem connectivity are vital. With adequate support, funding, and strategic alignment to EU and national priorities, these institutions can become powerful engines of innovation, ensuring the entrepreneurial ecosystem's success and resilience in North Macedonia and the wider Western Balkans.

3. Strategic Vision and Objectives

3.1. Strategic positioning

In this context, the Center for Entrepreneurship and Innovation at the Faculty of Economics-Skopje at the University of St. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje is positioned as one of the key connectors of the university R&I ecosystem—connecting the internal capacities of the University (faculties, institutes, laboratories, technology transfer offices, incubators/accelerators) with the government, industry,

investors and society—and as a "one-stop-shop" that converts the priorities of national R&I strategic documents into functional paths (projects → prototypes → spinoff companies → market impact) (Figure 1). Practically, the Center for Entrepreneurship and Innovation ensures the operationalization of this transformation, while CoARA provides the culture and rules that make the transformation sustainable (a system of incentives that values the valorization of knowledge, not just publication indicators).

Figure 1: University Research and Innovation (R&I) Ecosystem

3.2. Vision

To develop a university research and innovation ecosystem—recognized nationally and internationally as the central connector that accelerates research excellence aligned with the Smart Specialization Strategy, transforms knowledge into innovation and enterprise, and delivers measurable economic, social, and environmental impact—supported by the CoARA principles—a consistent, fair, and transparent system of research evaluation that recognizes diverse academic and innovation outcomes.

3.3. Mission

To coordinate research, innovation and entrepreneurship at the University through integrated services and platforms for: development of research excellence, technology transfer and intellectual property (IP) management, development of innovations and their commercialization, creation and growth of start-ups and spinoffs companies.

This is done through the application of mechanisms of: Continuous multi-layered networking (government-industry-society-international partners) and Reform of assessment and incentives according to CoARA indicators for research quality, with recognition of diverse results (publications,

data/software, prototypes, patents/licenses, research contracts, mentoring/team contribution, societal impact).

3.3. Strategic Objectives

The objectives directly respond to the challenges of the research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem (fragmentation, low level of knowledge and technology transfer, administrative barriers in intellectual property protection, weak support structures) and add CoARA quality indicators as an institutional mechanism that accelerates the transition to an entrepreneurial university and university research and innovation ecosystem.

SO1: Research excellence

Aligned with the Strategy for smart specialization, research excellence and relevance (green/digital transformation), assessed with qualitative assessment and accountable indicators (CoARA).

SO2: Upgrading the research infrastructure

Upgrading and open access to research infrastructure through laboratories and other research centers as a service to companies for research, validation of concepts and demonstration of prototypes.

SO3: Development of young researchers, innovators and entrepreneurs

Integrating research and innovation competencies into teaching, research and extracurricular activities at all faculties in order to prepare young researchers, innovators and entrepreneurs.

SO4: Project support “from grant to impact”

Professionalizing the process “from grant to impact” for participation in Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA), through strong project support (from idea and application for funding, through project management, up to concrete research results)

SO5: Systemic and long-term networking and partnerships

To establish a permanent structured system of partnerships and networking at local, national, regional, EU and global levels with the aim of continuous flow of knowledge, resources and opportunities for joint projects, commercialization and societal impact.

SO6: Integrated system for technology transfer and commercialization

To establish a functional and integrated system for technology transfer and commercialization with clear rules, transparent processes and appropriate incentives that will motivate researchers to actively participate in the valorization of knowledge.

SO7: Support in intellectual property (IP) management

To provide easy, understandable and reliable support for the protection of intellectual property through awareness-raising, expert advice and simplified procedures.

SO8: Establishing a financial path for commercialization

To establish a clear financial path from initial concept to growth (seed → scale) through appropriate instruments and partnerships that will support research, prototyping, market entry and preparation for investments in order to accelerate the commercialization of university innovations.

SO9: System for measuring and publicly reporting results and impact

To establish a transparent and CoARA-compliant system for monitoring, measuring and communicating results and impact, which will include balanced indicators for research excellence, open science, collaboration with industry, launched start-ups and spinoff companies, and publishes an annual public report on achievements.

4. Current State of the Entrepreneurial and R&I Ecosystem in North Macedonia

4.1. Research and Innovation Capacity

4.1.1. Status of Academic and Research Institutions

The higher education sector is the principal performer of research nationally, confirming universities' pivotal role in knowledge creation and talent development (GNM, 2023). The system comprises 34 HEIs (end-2024), among which 13 public, 1 public-private, and 20 private universities. While private providers broaden access and program variety, public universities and the Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts (MASA) remain the core holders of research capacity and international scientific cooperation (GNM, 2023).

In recent years, internationalization has strengthened, with EU framework programs becoming an increasingly important channel for cooperation and funding. North Macedonia's association to Horizon Europe has expanded opportunities for collaborative projects, mobility, and alignment with EU missions. A concrete ecosystem milestone is the EIT Community RIS Hub (2023) at the UKIM Business Accelerator, designed to connect universities, firms and public actors with Europe's largest innovation network and to catalyze knowledge transfer (GNM, 2023).

At the same time, the institutional base faces structural constraints typical of widening contexts: fragmented and limited funding, uneven availability of modern laboratories, and a small research workforce relative to EU peers (GNM, 2023). The policy response set out in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of RNM 2024-2027 translates these challenges into concrete priorities, namely competitive research funding, upgrades of university laboratories, stronger researcher pipelines (PhDs, Industrial PhDs, PostDoc and researcher positions), and professionalized project-support offices, alongside clearer technology-transfer and IPR frameworks (GNM, 2023; OECD, 2024b). Complementary SME policy also emphasizes an enabling entrepreneurial ecosystem that can absorb and commercialize university-generated knowledge.

These conditions translate directly into priorities for a university-level R&I strategy: (i) consolidate disciplinary strengths within public universities; (ii) professionalize international project offices; (iii) leverage the EIT Hub and Horizon Europe for partnerships; and (iv) prioritize S3-aligned investments in people, laboratories and technology transfer (technology transfer offices (TTOs), incubation, and future science-and-technology-park linkages) to deepen HEIs' role as orchestrators of the national entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem (GNM, 2023).

4.1.2. R&D Funding and Infrastructure

Public investment remains the backbone of North Macedonia's R&D system, with relatively low overall R&D intensity and a funding mix dominated by government and higher education, while business R&D is comparatively weak (GNM, 2023). According to the latest European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) 2025, North Macedonia is classified as an Emerging Innovator, scoring 40% of the EU average and ranking 34th among the EU and neighbouring countries, below the Emerging Innovators' mean of 46% (European Commission, 2025a). This structure constrains scale, continuity, and equipment renewal, and places universities at the center of grant capture and research infrastructure upgrading.

International programs partly offset domestic constraints by providing access to networks, infrastructure and thematic calls that are not available nationally. North Macedonia's association to Horizon Europe has opened broader consortia and thematic opportunities, with early participation improving relative to Horizon 2020. Complementary mechanisms - COST, EUREKA, CERN/IAEA

cooperation, and EuroHPC (EuroCC/CASTIEL) access, strengthen research networks and provide routes to advanced facilities and e-infrastructure (GNM, 2023).

Nationally, the Fund for Innovation and Technology Development (FITD), established in 2013, was the pivotal innovation financier, anchoring grant and co-investment schemes for start-ups and firms. From 2025, FITD's functions will transition to the newly established Agency for Innovation, Scientific and Technological Development and Entrepreneurship (INOVA), implying a consolidation and upgrading of the institutional framework for innovation support.

The SME Strategy 2025-2030 and the Growth Acceleration Plan (2022–2026) propose complementary instruments, such as credit guarantees, venture and hybrid funds, green finance, and better access to EU facilities, to crowd in private capital and diversify funding beyond grants (Ministry of Economy and Labour, 2024). These policy lines matter for universities because they define co-funding levers for applied research, proof-of-concept, and spin-out growth.

Research infrastructure has seen incremental upgrades (competitive MES calls, laboratory and equipment funding), yet large gaps persist in modern labs, shared core facilities, and service-oriented RI that industry can use. The Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) prioritizes upgrading university laboratories, establishing centers of excellence, a national technology transfer office, and science & technology park(s), and deploying innovation vouchers, competitive collaborative grants, and tax incentives to stimulate company R&D and academia–industry projects (GNM, 2023).

4.1.3. Innovation Performance and University–Industry Collaboration

North Macedonia remains an Emerging Innovator with gradual improvement in recent years. The EIS 2025 shows performance still below the EU average, with relative strengths in foreign doctorate students (as % of all), non-R&D innovation expenditures, and exports of medium- and high-tech products, and relative weaknesses in direct and indirect government support of business R&D, design applications, and venture capital expenditures (European Commission, 2025a). In parallel, the Global Innovation Index (GII) 2024 presents a mixed profile, comparatively stronger in infrastructure and business sophistication, weaker in human capital & research and creative outputs, underscoring the need to boost research excellence and knowledge valorization (WIPO, 2024). The OECD SME Policy Index 2022 recognizes advances in innovation policy instruments and internationalization, but stresses the need for a more systematic, targeted approach to business–academia collaboration and to entrepreneurial skills (OECD, 2022).

Commercialization and knowledge transfer remain nascent. Universities' TTO functions and spin-off pipelines are emerging but small-scale. National policy now prioritizes concrete enablers: the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) introduces a policy mix to (i) professionalize technology transfer (including a National Technology Transfer Office), (ii) finance centers of excellence, innovation hubs and science & technology park(s), and (iii) expand collaborative R&D instruments (competitive academia–industry grants, innovation vouchers, and tax incentives for firm–university projects), alongside industrial PhD pathways. The EIT Community RIS Hub at UKIM's Business Accelerator further strengthens links to European KICs and networks, creating a channel for market-oriented projects and talent circulation.

Implications for a university-level R&I strategy. (i) Prioritize S3-aligned collaboration platforms (innovation vouchers, collaborative R&D calls, industrial PhDs) and professionalized TTO/IP processes; (ii) set KPIs for contract research, spin-offs and patents; (iii) leverage the EIT Hub for EU-value-chain access; and (iv) integrate INOVA/SME-finance instruments to build proof-of-concept → seed → scale pathways for research-based ventures (GNM, 2023; Ministry of Economy and Labour, 2024).

4.1.4. Insights from USE IPM targeted EU partners' HEI R&I Strategy

Below are the key **lessons learned from the project partners** regarding effective Research & Innovation and entrepreneurship systems and strategies:

Ethics-by-design innovation pipeline (ALDA, France). Embed ethics, human rights, inclusion, and eco-friendly practice as default criteria from ideation to scale-up. Use programme rules and mentoring to make responsible innovation a practical routine, not a slogan. This strengthens legitimacy with communities and improves real-world uptake of solutions.

Operational excellence for R&I delivery (PMO approach) (OCom, Italy). Manage R&I support as a portfolio with standard workplans, risk management, and quality assurance checkpoints. Combine governance toolkits with digital enablement and continuous improvement to reduce fragmentation. The result is more predictable execution, better learning loops, and scalable support capacity.

Structured IP and technology transfer “playbooks” (SME4, Belgium). Strengthen technology transfer through clear, repeatable processes: disclosure → screening → protection → licensing. Add practical templates and guidance so researchers and partners know exactly how to progress each case. This increases speed, consistency, and confidence in commercialization pathways.

Place-based innovation clusters with strong Academy-to-Business interfaces (ISPIM, United Kingdom). Build collaboration through clusters that provide shared labs/testbeds and brokerage between academia and industry. Use clear A2B interfaces (contract research, industrial MSc/PhD, joint facilities) to turn needs into projects fast. This accelerates adoption and supports responsible/value-based regional innovation.

Systematic capacity-building and peer learning across the institution (IIE, Croatia). Invest continuously in skills for proposal writing, project control, IP, and R&I operations for staff and researchers. Institutionalise peer-to-peer exchange so know-how moves across faculties and with external partners. This raises overall R&I maturity and reduces dependence on a few individuals.

R&I strategy anchored in openness and partnerships (UnivPM, Italy). Make “open university” a research strategy by expanding national/international collaboration at institutional and researcher levels. Use partnerships to drive mobility, projects, and stronger positioning/visibility for the university. This widens opportunity pipelines while keeping research aligned to external needs.

Excellence + integration + responsibility as one R&I system (UnivPM, Italy). Raise research quality through targeted incentives/investments while explicitly enabling interdisciplinary integration. Treat responsibility, sustainability, and ethics as an R&I performance dimension—alongside excellence. This creates coherence where quality, collaboration, and societal relevance reinforce each other.

End-to-end “knowledge-to-impact” architecture (UAlg, Portugal). Link research capacity to impact by connecting research units, research support, and a strong transfer/entrepreneurship interface. Position the interface as the route from results to IP, partnerships, startups, and application outcomes. This makes commercialization and regional impact a designed pathway, not an ad-hoc event.

Entrepreneurship as an ecosystem (not a single program) (UAlg, Portugal). Build entrepreneurship through multiple layers (infrastructure + programs + initiatives) so teams progress step-by-step. Combine incubation/acceleration with training and community activities to sustain deal flow and capability-building. This improves conversion from ideas to viable ventures and strengthens the innovation community.

4.2. Key Challenges in North Macedonia

North Macedonia must first overcome several deeply embedded, systemic obstacles in order to create a contemporary, competitive economy. These obstacles, which were found through the research based on focused groups, the Delphi method, and needs analysis conducted in North Macedonia between September 2023 and November 2024 within the USE IPM project.

4.2.1. *Soft Skills for Entrepreneurial Business*

For young entrepreneurs entering a dynamic and fiercely competitive labour market, developing strong soft skills is crucial. People's ability to exhibit resilience, adaptability, and productive teamwork is still restricted by a number of interconnected problems.

- ***Soft skills are not sufficiently incorporated into formal education.*** There is little room for real-world communication exercises, emotional intelligence training, networking simulations, or conflict-resolution workshops in schools and universities because instruction is still very theoretical. Consequently, students graduate with domain knowledge but lack the interpersonal skills necessary for success in actual business settings.
- ***Inadequate leadership, problem-solving, and managerial skills.*** Many young professionals don't have practical experience setting priorities, managing teams, and making decisions. Interdisciplinary modules that reflect actual organizational challenges or link managerial skills with innovative thinking are uncommon in vocational and professional training programs.
- ***Limited critical thinking and risk-management culture.*** The education system does not consistently encourage analytical reasoning, scenario planning, or reflective evaluation. In workplaces, companies often avoid structured risk-assessment practices, discouraging employees from thinking critically or proposing creative alternatives.
- ***Innovation and creativity are still underappreciated.*** Instead of rewarding experimentation, traditional organizational cultures often mitigate and correct failure. This tests the entrepreneurial spirit required to investigate unique concepts, carry out iterative testing, and react quickly to shifts in the market.

4.2.2. *Sustainability and Sustainability Reporting (ESG)*

Companies in North Macedonia are unable to unlock the competitive advantages of sustainability due to a complex web of structural, financial, and cultural barriers that hinder the integration of ESG principles. The following issues highlight the crucial gaps.

- ***Inconsistent regulations and poor application of ESG standards.*** ESG adoption is still low, particularly in SMEs. Enforcement mechanisms are inadequate, and current national legislation only partially complies with EU directives. Instead of using domestic regulatory incentives, larger companies typically only comply when mandated by foreign parent companies.
- ***There are few awareness and knowledge gaps in the business sector.*** Instead of seeing sustainability reporting as a chance to boost resource efficiency, increase competitiveness, and build stakeholder trust, many businesses still see it as a financial or administrative burden. Transparency and accountability are hampered by this ignorance, which increases the possibility of greenwashing.
- ***Perceptions of high costs and financial obstacles.*** Digital reporting tools, green certification procedures, and sustainable technologies are frequently regarded as costly. It is particularly

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difficult for smaller businesses to set aside funds for data collection, environmental enhancements, and ESG reporting.

- **Issues with governance and cultural resistance.** Many organizations still put short-term financial results ahead of long-term sustainability objectives. Adoption is slowed down by organizational resistance to change and a lack of knowledge about the advantages of sustainability.
- **Weak digital infrastructure and technological constraints.** Businesses don't have access to digital systems and contemporary tools that could simplify ESG reporting and increase accuracy, like artificial intelligence (AI), data analytics, or automated reporting platforms.

4.2.3. Technology Transfer and Open Innovation

There is currently a significant gap between research and the market that threatens North Macedonia's potential for a dynamic innovation economy. Technology transfer is the exception rather than the rule in this fragmented ecosystem because the key players—businesses, governments, and universities—operate in silos. Key actors' lack of coordination and synergy. Universities, SMEs, corporations, and public institutions are all present, but interaction is still irregular and unstructured.

- **The government's role is unclear, and public services are not fully digitalized.** Stakeholders frequently believe that the government's support for innovation is erratic. Slow adoption of digital tools, corruption risks, and bureaucratic hold-ups erode trust and diminish the efficacy of support programs.
- **Limited market orientation and inadequate technology transfer mechanisms.** Companies hardly ever interact with research institutions, and a lot of innovations fail because they are not sufficiently tailored to the demands of the market. Businesses frequently prioritise local over international opportunities, which lowers the likelihood of technology commercialisation.
- **Intellectual property (IP) processes are slow, expensive, and complicated.** Rarely do entrepreneurs seek patents; instead, they rely on NDAs or trademarks. Innovators are deterred from formally protecting their ideas by a lack of knowledge, high administrative costs, and drawn-out legal procedures.
- **Limited support for innovation, both financial and non-financial.** Bureaucracy, inadequate distribution, or a lack of follow-up assistance frequently impede grants, tax incentives, and mentoring services. R&D advisory services and digital literacy are not routinely offered.

4.2.4. Innovation Process Management

Promising concepts frequently fail at critical stages, from funding and prototyping to market entry and scaling, not because they are unoriginal but rather due to structural inefficiencies that prevent implementation and growth. The following challenges hinder the entire process, from ideation to commercialization.

- **Slow administrative processes and inefficient bureaucracy.** Project implementation is delayed by complicated documentation requirements and sluggish decision-making procedures. Local governments frequently lack the resources to properly support innovation initiatives, which leads to dispersed strategies.
- **Restricted availability of various financial products.** Banks provide standardised products that don't meet the needs of impact-driven businesses or early-stage innovators. This limits market validation, prototyping, and experimentation.

- **Cultural resistance and low public awareness.** The general public, investors, and some policymakers continue to have a poor understanding of sustainable and socially responsible innovation. This slows the adoption of new solutions and diminishes support for mission-driven endeavours.
- **Stakeholder collaboration is fragmented.** There is a lack of coordination between businesses, accelerators, local government, and academia, which leads to redundant projects and wasteful resource use. Expert networks and university labs are still underutilized.
- **Obstacles to commercialization and knowledge transfer.** Lack of support for testing, proof-of-concept development, and market entry frequently prevents innovations from moving past the prototype stage. Industry partnerships and organized mentorship are often absent from academic spin-offs.
- **An imbalance in ecosystem support.** Hardware and manufacturing innovations lack sufficient incubation or scaling support because ecosystem actors typically concentrate on software start-ups.

4.3. Upgraded and/or drafted national or HEI R&I Strategy

The implementation and success of North Macedonia's strategic objectives, including Smart Specialisation, are directly threatened by the systemic problems that the country's entrepreneurship ecosystem is currently facing. A comprehensive and coordinated approach that concurrently addresses funding, human capital, business competitiveness, regulatory modernisation, and the fundamental governance required to direct the strategy is necessary to build a cohesive ecosystem.

The ensuing sections describe this vicious cycle in detail, dissecting the interrelated problems of an outdated funding model, crucial underinvestment in R&D, structural obstacles for researchers, and a disjointed innovation environment that together impede North Macedonia's potential for intelligent and sustainable economic growth.

- **A Fragmented and Underfunded R&I Ecosystem.** A fundamental disconnect is created by the extremely low R&D investment (0.38% of GDP) and the absence of systematic cooperation between businesses, research institutions, and academia (the "triple helix"). The Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP), the foundation of S3, is directly hampered by this. Academic research is not informed by the practical needs of businesses, and valuable knowledge from universities fails to transfer to the market in the absence of strong linkages. Potential areas of smart specialisation are underdeveloped because promising ideas and research lack the institutional support to be commercialised due to the lack of efficient technology transfer offices and innovation hubs.
- **An Obsolete and Counterproductive Funding Model for Higher Education and R&I.** A severely underfunded and misaligned incentive structure is at the heart of the issue. It is commonly acknowledged that the current higher education funding model is "outdated, overly rigid, and ineffective in incentivizing innovation or long-term planning" (Republic of North Macedonia, 2023). The national R&D expenditure of less than 0.4% of GDP, which is significantly lower than the EU average of 2.3% (Eurostat, 2024; as also highlighted in the S3-MK document), exacerbates this. The business sector's contribution to R&D (BERD) is extremely low and declining, and universities lack the resources for strategic research as a result of this ongoing underinvestment (Republic of North Macedonia, 2024). The S3-MK confirms that the restrictive, performance-based allocation system fails to drive quality, necessitating a comprehensive reform towards a results-oriented and transparent model to foster a dynamic R&I ecosystem.

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- **Systemic Barriers for Researchers and the Academic "Brain Drain"** Human capital is directly impacted by the funding crisis. Academic staff members' engagement in research is severely limited by their heavy teaching and administrative workloads, as well as their lack of training in scientific writing and project development (Republic of North Macedonia, 2018). This is confirmed by the S3-MK, which highlights the absence of institutional mechanisms to ensure dedicated research time, which are typical in European systems. This environment stifles scientific productivity and erodes international cooperation, especially when combined with restricted access to databases, modern research infrastructure, and committed funding. The emigration of professional employees, or "brain drain," is a direct result that is specifically mentioned in the S3-MK. This depletes the nation's core of highly qualified researchers and innovators, further undermining the R&I base.
- **A Disconnected Innovation Ecosystem and Lagging Performance.** Poor national innovation outcomes are a direct result of the shortcomings in the research and higher education systems. North Macedonia is classified as a "Emerging Innovator" on the European Innovation Scoreboard due to its performance being only 40% of the EU average (European Commission, 2025a). This lag is especially noticeable in low patent activity, low business R&D spending, and poor new technology commercialization (Ibid.). A detailed picture of this problem is given by the S3-MK, which emphasizes a serious lack of organized collaboration and knowledge sharing between academic institutions, research centres, and the commercial sector. Due to this disjointed "triple helix," businesses do not profit from academic expertise and research is rarely commercialized, which causes the nation to lag behind regional rivals.
- **Low Innovation Capacity of SMEs and an Unsupportive Environment.** The last issue appears in the business sector, especially in SMEs. According to the S3-MK analysis, SMEs lack the scale, expertise, and financial resources necessary to invest in R&D and adopt new technologies. Instead of creating innovative, branded products, they frequently concentrate on low-value production and outsourcing. An antiquated and complicated regulatory framework that does not promote innovation, circular economy principles, or green growth makes this worse. Businesses are further cut off from the information and resources required to innovate and compete globally due to the absence of strong institutional support platforms, such as technology transfer offices and innovation hubs (as mentioned in the S3-MK).

5. Key Pillars of the R&I Strategy

A comprehensive approach to research and innovation excellence, designed to strengthen the ecosystem through focused strategic priorities and cross-cutting reforms (Figure 2).

5.1. Research Excellence

Purpose: Strengthening excellence in the domains of the Smart Specialisation Strategy, Research Human Resource Development, Research Centres and Internationalisation.

CoARA integration: "excellence" is demonstrated through qualitative assessment and narrative evidence of contribution/impact, supported by qualitative indicators.

Programmes/actions:

- **Development of human resources for research and development:** support for PhDs, Industrial PhDs and Postdoctoral positions (PostDoc), with organised stays and cooperation with companies/public sector for practical experience in priority S3 areas. Industrial PhDs and postdoctoral positions are developed with joint supervision of academic and industrial

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supervisors, and doctoral schools include modules on innovation, entrepreneurship and research project management to strengthen the career and employability of researchers.

Figure 2: Strategic Framework: Five pillars of the R&I strategy

- **Modernization of research infrastructure and open access:** upgrading laboratories and equipment and establishing “common access” to the infrastructure through a clear service model and a catalogue of services for SMEs, start-ups and large companies. Laboratories and e-infrastructure are organized as shared services with transparent access rules and clearly defined Service-Level Agreements (SLAs), so that both university teams and SMEs can count on predictable conditions for the use of equipment, data and expertise.
- **Applied research for green and digital transformation:** development of research and development projects oriented towards practical solutions, prototypes, testing and pilot demonstrations in areas related to energy efficiency, sustainability, digitalization and technological modernization. In each selected priority area, lighthouse research programmes are established, co-defined with external partners and updated annually through thematic challenges (challenge briefs), ensuring that the topics remain demand-oriented and aligned with market and policy priorities. The portfolio is balanced between basic, applied and interdisciplinary projects.
- **Internationalisation of research and integration into European networks:** systemic support for participation in Horizon Europe, COST and EUREKA and involvement in European research infrastructures and consortia through partnerships, mobility and joint projects.
- **CoARA-compliant tools for assessing and stimulating research:** introduction of narrative CV, discipline-specific criteria and recognition of open science results such as; data, software, open innovation, mentoring, knowledge and technology transfer, innovation, commercialisation and societal impact.

5.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

Purpose: Strengthening commercialization by professionalizing processes and reducing IP barriers (Figure 3).

CoARA integration: patents/licenses, prototypes, standards, industrial contracts are treated as legitimate results in the assessment (not "second tier" to papers).

Programs/actions:

- **Technology Transfer Office within:** establishing a "one-stop-shop" through which companies, researchers and investors will receive information, guidance and full support for collaboration, contractual research, IP procedures, licensing and spin-off formation. Technology Transfer Offices function as the main entry point ("front door") for all valorization activities, offering IP clinics, model contracts (NDA, MTA, license and option agreements) and standard rules for revenue sharing and equity participation for founders and faculties. A Standing IP Committee makes decisions on protection, ownership and path to market within set deadlines and manages potential conflicts of interest.
- **Simplifying intellectual property management:** providing practical advice and step-by-step support for the protection and management of intellectual property, with ready-made templates, as well as measures to reduce costs and duration of procedures. The valorisation path starts with a formal notification of the result by the researcher, followed by a rapid assessment of novelty and freedom-to-operate, combined with a short market screening for potential users and value paths. On this basis, an IP decision is made – whether to protect the result (patent/utility model), treat it as know-how or follow open access – and the appropriate path to market (license or spin-off) is defined.
- **Instruments for encouraging academia-industry cooperation:** activating and using measures such as innovation vouchers, collaborative grants and industrial PhDs for joint R&I projects, and accelerated commercialization of solutions.

Figure 3: "Research-to-market" pathway

5.3. Innovative entrepreneurship

Purpose: creating a pipeline for knowledge-based companies that attract funding and scale to global markets.

CoARA integration: mentoring, entrepreneurial education, team development and the creation of spinoffs and start-ups are recognized as academic/institutional contributions.

Programs/actions:

- **Entrepreneurial path from idea to growth:** establishing a clear process with phases of idea generation and verification → pre-incubation and concept development → incubation and product/service development → acceleration and market entry → scaling and internationalization with specific criteria and support at each stage.
- **Mentoring system and programs with alumni and diaspora:** establishing a base of mentors (entrepreneurs, industry experts, investors), organized mentoring sessions as well as a structured “bridge with the diaspora” for access to international markets, knowledge and contacts. Clearly defined cohorts, milestones and criteria for team advancement are established. Partnerships are established with regional accelerators and relevant EIT Knowledge & Innovation Communities (KICs) to help validated teams refine their business model, secure early customers and prepare for investor presentations.
- **Investment readiness and connection to financial instruments:** development of an investment readiness program and systematic connection to grants, banks, business angels and VR funds. Co-investment frameworks are established with angel networks, VC funds and international financial institutions, using standard instruments (e.g. convertible notes) and structured “investment-readiness coaching”.
- **SME Academy (executive education),** offers micro-credentials in areas such as finance, export, digital and green skills, and conducts applied clinics through which the most promising SME initiatives are directed towards lab vouchers and PoC calls.

5.4. Pilar 4 – Ecosystem Networking and Internationalization

Purpose: The Center for Entrepreneurship and Innovation is permanently connected at all levels and becomes a practical coordination node.

CoARA integration: cooperation and social engagement are recognized as results with clear evidence and criteria.

Programs/actions:

- **Advisory Board with the quadruple helix system:** establishment of a council composed of representatives of the University, the business sector, public institutions and civil society, which will co-define priorities, propose thematic challenges and monitor the progress of the Center through regular meetings and clear recommendations.
- **Formal partnerships with key institutions and intermediaries:** conclusion of memoranda and operational protocols for cooperation with ministries/agencies, municipalities and regional bodies, as well as with chambers of commerce and industrial clusters, for the implementation of joint projects, pilot solutions, contract research and programs to support innovation in companies.
- **EU integration through European programs: systemic:** support for participation in Horizon Europe and use of the EIT (European Institute of Innovation and Technology) and its communities/accelerator networks. access to partnerships, expertise, funding and faster development of market-oriented innovation projects.

5.5. Pilar 5 – CoARA reform for qualitative assessment and indicators for measuring the impact of the Center

Purpose: To ensure that all priorities work in practice, the University establishes a **CoARA-compliant assessment system** that combines **qualitative evidence + responsible metrics**, recognizing diverse R&I contributions and measuring UEIC impact transparently.

- **CoARA assessment policy + rubrics:** Adopt UEIC-wide evaluation rules that prioritize **quality, integrity, openness, collaboration and impact** (not “where published”), with **discipline-sensitive rubrics** for research, TT/IP, entrepreneurship and societal engagement.
- **Narrative evidence:** Introduce standardized short formats—**Impact Case, Innovation Case, Collaboration Case**—with **contribution statements** (team roles) and supporting evidence (links, prototypes, partner proof).
- **Balanced CoARA KPI set:** Implement a scorecard that tracks **capacity → process quality → outputs → outcomes/impact** (e.g., PoCs/prototypes, datasets/software, disclosures/licenses, adoption, jobs, policy uptake), while **avoiding JIF/h-index as decision rules**.
- **Open Science & integrity integration:** Make DMPs, open access, data/code sharing (where feasible), ethics and governance checks part of the evidence base and **value open outputs as first-class results**.
- **Stakeholder-validated impact:** Collect external validation (partner letters, pilots, adoption evidence) and run an annual **partner value/satisfaction survey**, using a Quadruple-Helix lens for selected flagship cases.
- **Incentives + digital dashboard + annual reporting:** Align internal rewards with CoARA (mini-grants/recognition for mentoring, TT and engagement), support evidence collection via a **digital dashboard/evidence hub**, and publish an **annual UEIC Impact Report** combining KPIs and verified impact stories.

6. Implementation Framework

In a widening/low-resource context—characterised by fragmented financing, limited modern infrastructure, and a relatively small research workforce—these enablers are not “add-ons”, but the core conditions for delivery at scale.

Governance

A robust governance set-up ensures decisions are fast, transparent, and aligned with national priorities and stakeholder needs, while protecting academic integrity and public value. The governance model should be built around three complementary layers:

(1) Strategic steering. The Center for Entrepreneurship and Innovation is positioned as a key connector of the university R&I ecosystem, linking internal capacities (faculties, institutes, labs, TTOs, incubators/accelerators) with government, industry, investors and society, and converting national priorities into implementable pathways.

(2) Ecosystem accountability. A Quadruple-helix Advisory Board composed of the university, business sector, public institutions and civil society should co-define priorities, propose thematic challenges and review progress through regular meetings and recommendations.

(3) Operational governance. To reduce fragmentation and bureaucracy, operations should be managed as a portfolio (PMO logic) and supported through clear “playbooks” for technology transfer and IP—disclosure → screening → protection → licensing/spin-off—backed by templates and set decision deadlines.

National R&I Strategy Alignment

The Strategy must remain tightly aligned with the **Smart Specialisation Strategy 2024–2027**, national innovation instruments, and EU integration pathways. This alignment is an implementation enabler because it: Creates a **clear investment logic** (priority domains, infrastructure upgrades, human capital pipelines, technology transfer frameworks); Improves access to **EU programmes and Widening instruments** (e.g., Horizon Europe, COST, EUREKA) and strengthens international networks and mobility; and Enables “blended finance” pathways by linking university projects to national instruments and reforms (e.g., the transition from FITD functions to the new INOVA agency; and SME-oriented instruments such as credit guarantees, venture/hybrid funds, and green finance).

Figure 4: University-Level R&I ecosystem (internal ecosystem)

Universities

Universities are the primary national performers of research and therefore the key delivery platform for this Strategy (Figure 4). The university-level enablers focus on *institutional capacity*, not only individual excellence: **Professionalized project support (“grant-to-impact”)**. A strengthened project support function is essential for increasing participation and success in Horizon Europe and similar programmes; **Open and service-oriented research infrastructure**. Upgrading labs and equipment and organizing them as shared services (catalogue of services, clear access rules, service-level agreements) makes infrastructure usable for SMEs and partners and accelerates validation and prototyping; **Functional technology transfer interface**. The Strategy’s “one-stop-shop” logic—support for collaboration, contract research, IP procedures, licensing, and spin-off formation—reduces barriers and increases conversion from research to impact; **Human capital pipelines (PhDs/Industrial PhDs/PostDocs) linked to S3 needs**. Joint supervision with industry and modules on innovation/entrepreneurship/project management increase employability and strengthen academia–industry linkages.

Cultural Change

In widening contexts, “culture” is often the hidden constraint that prevents good initiatives from scaling. Implementation therefore requires intentional cultural change, anchored in incentives and routines: **CoARA-based incentives** that treat prototypes, patents, licenses, data/software

outputs, mentoring, and societal engagement as legitimate outcomes—reducing the “publication-only” logic and making valorisation a normal academic behaviour; **Institutionalised peer learning and capacity building** across faculties (proposal writing, project control, IP, R&I operations), so know-how spreads beyond a few individuals and becomes a shared capability; **Ethics-by-design and responsibility** embedded as default criteria in the innovation pipeline (inclusion, eco-friendly practice, legitimacy with communities).

International Orientation

International orientation is a practical enabler—bringing partnerships, funding, benchmarks, and talent circulation that compensate for limited domestic resources. Key mechanisms include: **Systemic support for Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA participation** and structured partnership building at institutional and researcher levels; Leveraging concrete ecosystem assets such as the **EIT Community RIS Hub at UKIM’s Business Accelerator** to connect with Europe’s innovation networks and catalyse knowledge transfer; **Diaspora and alumni bridges** for mentoring, market access, and investor networks, linked to the idea-to-growth entrepreneurial pathway.

Stakeholder Communication

Strategic communication should therefore: Use the **Advisory Board** as a permanent feedback loop and legitimacy mechanism; Translate strategy into **clear “front door” entry points** (TTO services, IP clinics, model contracts, innovation vouchers/collaborative calls) that external stakeholders can easily use; Publish an **annual public report on achievements and impact**, based on transparent KPIs (projects, PoCs/prototypes, start-ups/spin-offs), strengthening accountability and stakeholder confidence.

Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is both a strategic priority and a delivery method. The implementation framework should include: Digitised workflows for **project pipeline management**, partner onboarding, and portfolio oversight (PMO approach), reducing administrative burden and enabling quality assurance and learning loops; Digital enablement of **open science and CoARA evidence** (narrative CVs, repositories for data/software, dashboards for KPIs and outcomes); Support for S3-aligned digital innovation domains (e.g., ICT, Industry 4.0), while ensuring the Center functions as the operational node that turns priorities into implementable projects and services.

Green Transformation

Green transformation must be embedded across research priorities, commercialization pathways, and stakeholder engagement, especially given the region’s commitment to decarbonisation and the need for innovation in energy efficiency, sustainable materials, and circular solutions. Implementation should: Prioritize applied R&D and pilot demonstrations in sustainability-relevant areas and maintain demand-oriented portfolios updated through thematic challenges co-defined with external partners; Strengthen green finance and other instruments that support proof-of-concept and scale-up pathways, linked to national SME policy instruments; Treat sustainability, responsibility, and ethics as performance dimensions in R&I, reinforcing legitimacy and long-term impact.

7. Expected Outcomes and Impact

The R&I strategy is designed to deliver measurable change in a *low-to-moderate R&I intensity (“widening”)* context, where North Macedonia remains below the EU target for R&D investment and

faces systemic constraints in funding continuity, infrastructure renewal, and commercialization pathways.

In this setting, **the University and its R&I centers are positioned as the “anchor” and central connector of the national ecosystem**, bridging internal capacities (faculties, institutes, laboratories, TTOs, incubators/accelerators) with government, industry, investors, and society—operationalized through the UEIC as a one-stop shop translating national priorities into “projects → prototypes → spin-offs → market impact.”

7.1. Expected outcomes

Outcome 1: Stronger S3-aligned research excellence and relevance (green/digital focus). UEIC-supported thematic platforms will increase the quality and usefulness of research in **Smart Specialisation (S3) priority domains**, including green and digital transformation topics. This shifts the system from fragmented project activity to a portfolio that is strategically coherent, internationally benchmarked, and aligned with EU missions and market needs.

Outcome 2: Upgraded, shared research infrastructure (“labs-as-a-service”). Improved laboratories and research centers—opened through shared access and service models—will directly address uneven infrastructure availability and enable validation/demonstration of prototypes with companies. This also strengthens the University’s role as a national infrastructure provider, particularly relevant where public and higher education funding dominates R&D and business R&D remains comparatively weak.

Outcome 3: A stronger talent pipeline of researchers, innovators, and entrepreneurs. By integrating R&I competencies across teaching, research, and extracurricular tracks, UEIC will grow a university-wide “pipeline” of young researchers and founders, including stronger links to S3 priorities and intersectoral exposure. This responds to constraints in human capital formation within widening contexts and supports retention of skilled labour through higher-value opportunities.

Outcome 4: A professional “grant-to-impact” pathway and higher participation in EU programs. UEIC will professionalize the end-to-end process from opportunity identification and proposal development to delivery and exploitation of results, increasing participation in **Horizon Europe / COST / EUREKA** and improving implementation quality. This is crucial because international programs can partially offset domestic constraints by providing networks, infrastructure access, and mission-oriented calls.

Outcome 5: Institutionalized multi-level networking and durable partnerships (Quadruple Helix). UEIC will build a permanent partnership system across local–national–regional–EU–global levels, enabling continuous flows of knowledge, resources, and collaboration opportunities. The expected result is a shift from ad-hoc cooperation to structured co-creation—addressing the recognized weakness of academia–industry links and enabling ecosystem-wide learning loops.

Outcome 6: A functional technology transfer and commercialization system (TTO + clear incentives). UEIC will implement an integrated framework for technology transfer and commercialization (including contract research, licensing, and spin-offs), supported by transparent rules and incentives that motivate researchers to engage in knowledge valorisation. This directly targets a core regional bottleneck: weak co-creation with industry and low commercialization outcomes.

Outcome 7: Easier, more reliable IP support and stronger “commercialization readiness.” Through awareness, expert advice, and simplified procedures, UEIC will reduce perceived barriers to IP protection and strengthen the bridge from research outputs to market applications. This aligns with the strategic need to improve mechanisms that translate research into applications (IP rights, TTOs, incubators, industry partnerships).

Outcome 8: A clearer finance pathway: concept → seed → scale. UEIC will establish a structured financial path—from early proof/validation toward growth—through instruments and partnerships that support prototyping, market entry, and investment readiness. This directly mitigates the ecosystem bottleneck of limited early-stage capital and weak “smart money” availability for scaling innovations.

Outcome 9: CoARA-aligned performance and impact measurement with annual public reporting. UEIC will implement a transparent system for monitoring and communicating results, using balanced indicators that recognize diverse outputs (including prototypes, data/software, patents/licenses, contracts, mentoring, and societal impact)—and publish an annual public impact report.

7.2. Expected impact

Economic impact. Stronger R&I capacity, better technology transfer, and more spin-offs translate into productivity, competitiveness, and job creation—consistent with the role of R&I as a driver of growth in entrepreneurial ecosystems. The University’s “labs-as-a-service” and contract research pipelines also expand SMEs’ innovation capabilities, helping firms move up the value chain.

Societal impact. UEIC’s partnership model enables challenge-driven R&I with government, civil society, and communities, turning research into solutions for national priorities and improving talent retention by creating higher-value opportunities domestically.

Environmental and digital transformation impact. With green and digital transitions embedded in priorities, UEIC will catalyze applied research and innovation that supports decarbonization and digital modernization aligned with EU frameworks and regional agendas.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1. Summary of key strategic priorities

This Strategy positions the University Entrepreneurship and Innovation Center (UEIC) as the *central connector* of the university R&I ecosystem—linking internal capacities (faculties, institutes, labs, TTOs, incubators/accelerators) with government, industry, investors and society, and converting national priorities into implementable pathways.

In a widening/low-resource context, where fragmented financing, limited modern infrastructure and a relatively small research workforce constrain continuity and scaling, the Strategy treats implementation enablers as “core conditions”, not add-ons. Across the Strategy, five priority directions define how UEIC operationalizes the “entrepreneurial university” model:

- **Governance and portfolio delivery:** a three-layer governance model - strategic steering, ecosystem accountability via a Quadruple-Helix Advisory Board, and operational governance using PMO logic and playbooks for TT/IP processes with templates and deadlines—reduces fragmentation and accelerates decisions while protecting public value.
- **Tight national and EU alignment:** the Strategy remains anchored in the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) and EU integration pathways, using them to structure investment logic (domains, infrastructure, human-capital pipelines, TT frameworks), widen access to EU programmes (Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA), and enable blended finance routes by linking university projects to national reforms and instruments (including the transition from FITD functions to INOVA and SME-oriented finance instruments).

- **University capacity that converts research to impact:** professionalized “grant-to-impact” project support, open/service-oriented labs (“labs-as-a-service”), a functional technology transfer interface (“one-stop-shop”), and human capital pipelines (PhD/Industrial PhD/PostDoc) linked to S3 needs.
- **Networking and international orientation as a permanent capability:** structured partnership-building and systemic participation in EU instruments (Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA), leveraging ecosystem assets like the EIT Community RIS Hub at UKIM’s Business Accelerator, and activating diaspora/alumni bridges for mentoring, market access and investor networks.
- **CoARA-aligned performance and impact measurement:** balanced indicators that recognize diverse outputs (prototypes, data/software, patents/licenses, mentoring and societal engagement) and annual public impact reporting to strengthen accountability, trust and learning loops.

8.2. Next steps for implementation and policy adoption

To move from strategy to routine practice, implementation should progress in three reinforcing tracks:

(A) Institutional adoption and governance activation. First, formalize UEIC’s coordinating mandate through the governance layers: deploy the Strategic Steering function to translate S3 priorities into annual portfolios; convene the Quadruple-Helix Advisory Board as a standing mechanism to co-define thematic challenges and review progress; and implement PMO-style operational management supported by TT/IP playbooks and templates (e.g., disclosure → screening → protection → licensing/spin-off) with defined decision deadlines.

(B) Operational “front door” services for stakeholders. In parallel, convert the Strategy into a clear, usable service offer for external partners. Strategic communication should create recognizable entry points (TTO services, IP clinics, model contracts, innovation vouchers/collaborative calls), while the Advisory Board provides a permanent feedback loop and legitimacy mechanism.

This “front door” approach is critical for making the University’s ecosystem role visible and practical for ministries, municipalities, SMEs, clusters, investors and civil society partners.

(C) Policy alignment and funding pathways. Finally, embed national/EU alignment into implementation mechanics: structure calls, labs, human-capital actions and TT instruments around S3 logic; scale participation in Horizon/COST/EUREKA; and build blended finance pathways by connecting university pipelines to national instruments and reforms (including INOVA and SME finance tools), so promising results can move from PoC to market entry and scaling.

8.3. Recommendations for long-term sustainability and EU integration

1. **Institutionalize culture and incentives (CoARA in practice).** Treat valorisation and societal engagement as “normal academic behaviour” by embedding CoARA-based incentives that recognize prototypes, patents/licenses, data/software outputs, mentoring and engagement—reducing a publication-only logic.
2. **Sustain the UEIC operating model with diversified resources.** Ensure stable core capacity (project support, TTO/IP, lab services, portfolio management) that can survive funding volatility typical for widening contexts.
3. **Make infrastructure usable for the economy (“labs-as-a-service”).** Treat labs and equipment as shared services with clear access rules and service-level agreements so SMEs can validate, prototype and co-develop with the University.

4. **Lock in EU integration through networks, not only projects.** Systematically leverage Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA and connect via ecosystem assets such as the EIT Community RIS Hub to access KIC networks, expertise and market-oriented partnerships; reinforce this through diaspora/alumni bridges for mentoring and investor access.
5. **Digitize delivery and evidence.** Implement digitized workflows for pipeline management and portfolio oversight, and enable open-science/CoARA evidence through repositories and KPI dashboards—reducing administrative burden while improving quality assurance and learning.
6. **Embed green transition across priorities and commercialization.** Prioritize applied R&D and pilot demonstrations in sustainability-relevant areas, strengthen green finance links for PoC and scale-up, and treat sustainability/ethics as performance dimensions reinforcing legitimacy and long-term impact.
7. **Maintain transparency and public trust with annual impact reporting.** Publish an annual public report based on transparent, balanced KPIs (projects, PoCs/prototypes, start-ups/spin-offs and broader CoARA-recognized outputs), demonstrating the University’s anchor role in the national ecosystem and improving stakeholder confidence.

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R&I STRATEGY OF FEUBL, BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA

1. Executive Summary: Purpose and scope of the R&I strategy

The GDP per capita in Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H) amounts to slightly more than one-third of the EU average. The country continues to face significant socioeconomic challenges, further exacerbated by external shocks such as the war in Ukraine and rising global inflation, which have increased the cost of living and placed additional pressure on economic stability (UNICEF, 2025). The share of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in total turnover in B&H is higher than the EU average (17.4% compared to 12.6%), while the share of employment in the manufacturing sector amounts to 19.5%, compared to 15.6% in the EU (European Commission [EC], 2025a).

However, the country records weaker performance in employment within high- and medium-technology sectors, as well as in knowledge-based services, highlighting the low innovation intensity of its economy. B&H shows a similar level of employment in service activities and value added of foreign-owned enterprises as the EU average. These factors point to an attractive economic and fiscal environment that supports SME growth and contributes to improving the overall ease of doing business (EC, 2025a, p.6).

In response to the stagnation and insufficient economic growth in B&H, the academic community is taking on the role of a crucial actor within the entrepreneurial innovation ecosystem, providing strategic approaches to developing its own research capacities. *The Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy for the Development of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the enlargement countries* — Serbia, Albania and North Macedonia — partners in the USE IPM project, focuses on strengthening institutional infrastructure, improving collaboration between science and industry and creating an open, inclusive and sustainable innovation environment. A key role in the implementation of this strategy in B&H is attributed to higher education institutions, particularly the Faculty of Economics, University of Banja Luka (UNIBL) and its development and innovation centers, such as the *Center for Project Management and Entrepreneurship (CPME)* and *eLab*. These centers serve as key mechanisms for strengthening collaboration between academia, the private sector, government and civil society — enabling knowledge transfer and fostering systems of *open and sustainable innovation* in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the region through the Quintuple Helix Model of cooperation (Shkarupeta & Babkin, 2024).

The Strategy is fully aligned with European strategic frameworks, including *Horizon Europe*, the Smart Specialization Strategy (S3), the European Research Area (ERA) and the EU Green Deal. At the national level, it builds upon existing development documents and policies of each partner country, focusing on building a more competitive, digitally capable and innovation-driven entrepreneurial sector. The foundation for developing this Strategy includes a series of four thematic rounds of desk-based needs analysis, Delphi studies, focus groups and quantitative empirical research conducted on a sample of 100 micro, small, medium and large enterprises, implemented within the USE IPM project. It also incorporates insights from five study visits by six CPME researchers to five EU countries, lasting a total of three months, carried out between December 2023 and October 2025.

The strategic objectives of the Strategy include:

1. *Strengthening the role of the University as a catalyst for social progress* – with a special focus on the role of the Faculty of Economics at UNIBL – as an active actor in the regional innovation system through functional development centers and partnerships with the business sector.
2. *Promoting open innovation* through the interaction of academia, the private sector and public institutions, aiming at jointly creating sustainable solutions for societal and market challenges.
3. *Building capacities for knowledge and technology transfer* by creating collaboration instruments (innovation laboratories, University knowledge transfer office, active cooperation with the Science and Technology Park of The Republic of Srpska).

4. *Developing human capital* with an emphasis on transversal competencies, digital skills and entrepreneurial mindset, focusing on empowering youth, marginalised groups and women in the innovation process.
5. *Enhancing regional cooperation* to create an interconnected and functional innovation space in the Western Balkans.

It is expected that the implementation of the strategy will contribute to the creation of a stronger entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina, connected with the European Research Area. Through the active involvement of institutions such as the Faculty of Economics and other organisational units of UNIBL, the strategy will enable better knowledge flow, the development of new business models, increased self-employment rates among students and graduates, enhanced competitiveness of newly established start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and the strengthening of an innovation culture based on collaboration, sustainability and openness to change.

2. Introduction

2.1. Overview of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina¹²

Entrepreneurial ecosystems are defined as a set of interdependent actors and factors coordinated in such a way as to enable productive entrepreneurship within a given territory (Stam & Spigel, 2016). In addition to placing entrepreneurs – rather than existing firms – at the centre of attention (Stam, 2015), the entrepreneurial ecosystem approach considers the broader entrepreneurial context in which entrepreneurship takes place (Brown & Mason, 2014) and examines wide-ranging socio-economic, technological and cultural dimensions and influences (Audretsch et al., 2019). This perspective supports Baumol's (2010) theory, which makes a key distinction between **"routine/systematic innovation"** and **"entrepreneurial innovation"**. Baumol (2010) argued that routine/systematic innovation is predominantly the domain of large multinational corporations, such as IBM, Novartis, GE and Intel, which possess substantial, traditional research laboratories and facilities. In contrast, he considered small entrepreneurial firms – including many originating from universities – as the primary sources of radical or revolutionary breakthrough innovations. Some notable examples of entrepreneurial innovations developed by small firms include the electronic calculator, alternating current, sound film, turbojet engine, biotechnology, the personal computer and internet search engines (Guerrero & Siegel, 2024).

Nascent or potential entrepreneurs require "a tailwind" in the form of strong and modern educational institutions, role models, alternative sources of early-stage start-up financing, supportive fiscal policies, efficient legislative, judicial, and executive authorities, mentoring networks and other entrepreneurial infrastructure institutions. In the entrepreneurial ecosystem of Bosnia and Herzegovina, there is a lack of venture capitalists, angel investors, crowdfunding platforms, science and technology parks, free economic zones, business accelerators and mentoring services for aspiring entrepreneurs (although mentoring services are beginning to appear, primarily on a project basis). Furthermore, there is an insufficient number of role models – globally recognised successful entrepreneurs – universities have not been transformed into entrepreneurial ecosystems, and generally, "other values" prevail in which initiative, proactivity, creativity and the willingness to take reasonable risks are not particularly desirable traits. Entrepreneurial ecosystems are defined as a set

¹² The overview of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina, with the author's permission, has been adapted from Petković, S. (2025). *Entrepreneurial Management of Innovative Start-ups*. Banja Luka: University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Economics.

of interdependent actors and factors coordinated to enable productive entrepreneurship within a given territory (Stam & Spigel, 2016). In addition to focusing on entrepreneurs rather than existing firms (Stam, 2015), the entrepreneurial ecosystem approach examines the broader context in which entrepreneurship occurs (Brown & Mason, 2014) and investigates socio-economic, technological and cultural dimensions and impacts (Audretsch et al., 2018; 2019). This perspective supports Baumol's (2010) theory, which distinguishes between **“routine/systematic innovation”** and **“entrepreneurial innovation”**. Routine/systematic innovation is primarily the domain of large multinational corporations such as IBM, Novartis, GE and Intel, which have substantial traditional research laboratories and facilities. Small entrepreneurial firms – including many university spin-offs – are considered the key sources of radical or breakthrough innovations. Notable examples of entrepreneurial innovations developed by small firms include the electronic calculator, alternating current, sound film, turbojet engine, biotechnology, the personal computer and internet search engines (Guerrero & Siegel, 2024).

In most cities and municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, except for areas where large publicly owned companies were not significantly present, a policy of “dependence” prevails rather than a policy of “independence” that encourages individuality, creativity and innovativeness – all essential predispositions for entrepreneurial activity. In certain smaller local communities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, one can observe a so-called entrepreneurial subculture, typically in towns that either lacked strong industrial facilities during socialist Yugoslavia or had a separately developed entrepreneurial culture, which was more of an exception than the rule (e.g. Kotor Varoš, Tešanj, Laktaši, Gračanica, Široki Brijeg). Therefore, one of the key factors for the development of entrepreneurship in small developing economies – which is clearly missing – is an entrepreneurial culture. Entrepreneurial culture is fostered from an early age, beginning even in the preschool years (Petković & Kisić, 2019). A limiting factor for the development of entrepreneurial culture in Bosnia and Herzegovina has been the long period of the so-called socialist self-managed socio-economic system, as well as the extended post-war recovery period and the continuation of the ongoing transition.

Vidović (2022) investigated the level of development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina using the GEM NES study (National Experts Study). The application of the GEM NES study enables the calculation of the overall NECI score – the National Entrepreneurship Context Index – according to the GEM methodology, derived from the GEM NES study (GEM, 2022). Based on the NECI score, all nine individual elements of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina¹³ can be analysed and the overall and individual scores compared with an identical study conducted in 2021 across 50 countries worldwide. The following chart presents the individual scores for the nine elements of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, measured using Likert scales and ratings from one (1) to ten (10), where ten represents the highest score and five (5) is the threshold score, representing a “satisfactory level” of development for the component or the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem.

¹³ The analysis of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina was conducted as part of the empirical research for the doctoral dissertation of Milica Vidović at the Faculty of Economics, University of Banja Luka, under the supervision of Prof. Dr Saša Petković.

Figure 5: Entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2021

Notes: The chart presents the score for the nine elements of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina, according to the opinions of 36 experts from nine areas shown on the chart. The overall average score is 3.52, which is significantly below the “passing” score of five (5), representing a satisfactory level of development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem. This score represents the NECI score, or the National Entrepreneurial Context Index, according to the GEM methodology, derived from the GEM NES study (Vidović, 2022, p. 192).

According to the experts who participated in the study, the only category to achieve a passing score was physical infrastructure, with a score above five (5), specifically 6.16. However, even this score is questionable, given that the motorway network in Bosnia and Herzegovina is incomplete, the railway system barely functions and the availability of broadband fibre-optic internet and 5G mobile networks remains uncertain. Apart from the airport in Sarajevo, the Banja Luka and Tuzla airports rely on the policies of low-cost carriers from the EU, and Bosnia and Herzegovina lack a national airline. More concerning than the lack of quality physical infrastructure is the extremely low proportion of funds allocated by entities and companies to research and development, while knowledge transfer between the academic and real sectors (in both directions) is negligible. In 2020, **only 0.21% of Bosnia and Herzegovina’s total GDP was allocated to research and development**, whereas during the same period Israel allocated 5.44%, South Korea 4.81%, Sweden 3.53% and the EU an average of 2.36% of total GDP (The World Bank, 2020). Cultural and social norms were also rated poorly, as were government programmes providing concrete support for entrepreneurial development. Funding sources received low scores as well, despite the banking sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina being relatively developed and liquid. Alternative sources of funding for early-stage entrepreneurial ventures, such as angel investors, venture capital funds and crowdfunding, are almost non-existent in Bosnia and Herzegovina, meaning that the overall score for this part of the entrepreneurial ecosystem is below average. **The entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina is at a low level of development**, with an overall NECI score of 3.52. If compared with the NECI scores of the 50 countries that participated in the GEM 2021/2022 study, Bosnia and Herzegovina would rank 49th (Vidović, 2022, p. 194). Only Sudan and Iran scored lower, with 3.3 and 3.2 respectively. The score of 3.52 for Bosnia and Herzegovina is also lower than those of the nearest countries, Croatia and Slovenia, which participated in the GEM 2021/2022 study and received scores of 3.9 and 4.3 respectively. The highest NECI scores were achieved by the United Arab Emirates (6.8), the Netherlands (6.3), Finland (6.2),

Saudi Arabia (6.1) and Lithuania (6.1), while the lowest scores were recorded for Sudan (3.2), Iran (3.3), Belarus (3.6) and Brazil (3.6) (GEM, 2022, p. 90).

Figure 6: NECI – National Entrepreneurship Context Index in 2021

Notes: Adapted and reprinted from GEM, 2022, p. 90 and Vidović, 2022.

To build a thriving entrepreneurial ecosystem, a rational combination of the personal characteristics of potential entrepreneurs and a supportive environment is essential. Encouraging an entrepreneurial culture cannot simply be “copied and pasted” from successful ecosystems, such as Silicon Valley in California, USA. “Personal factors such as intelligence, creativity, insight, motivation and perseverance play a role, but at the same time, the environment either stimulates or suppresses initiative. People can plant the seeds of individual effort on either barren or fertile soil” (Koven, 2021, p. 85). Many cities in the former Yugoslavia that were once leading industrial centres no longer hold that status, having restructured their economic structures to varying degrees of success (e.g. Maribor, Banja Luka). The question arises: can targeted strategic support for entrepreneurship, collaboration between the public and private sectors and the development of an innovative entrepreneurial ecosystem restore the “post-industrial shine” to certain cities and regions and stimulate a wide range of industries from manufacturing to services? We believe this is possible, as will be further elaborated in the remainder of the Strategy.

2.2. Importance of Research and Innovation (R&I) for Ecosystem Development

Research and innovation (R&I) in the contemporary socio-economic environment are key drivers of change and the foundation for building a competitive and resilient economy (European Commission, 2025b). Rapid technological development, digital transformation, accelerated labor market changes,

global connectivity and growing challenges such as climate change emphasise the need for continuous improvement of knowledge, technologies and business models (Eller et al., 2020). Innovations, often resulting from systematic and applied research, enable the transformation of creative ideas into products, services and processes that meet real end-user needs, stimulate economic growth and contribute to social development (Zhang, 2022).

For the Western Balkan countries, which are in the process of European integration, investing in research and innovation capacities represents a strategic tool for overcoming current limitations and developing the economy through the establishment of a dynamic innovation ecosystem (Beaudry et al., 2021). Priorities include increasing competitiveness, modernising the economy, developing promising sectors, and empowering and encouraging entrepreneurs. The development of an entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem cannot be viewed separately from the social context, so sustainable functioning requires coordination between the educational, research, private and public sectors, with universities in the Western Balkans playing a key role as change drivers and facilitators of collaboration between these sectors. It is particularly important that ecosystem development aligns with social and economic needs, as the sustainability of innovations is achieved only when they provide benefits to the wider community and the economy as a whole.

The development of a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem is a broader concept than developing a favorable business environment. A sustainable ecosystem implies the ability of enterprises to create and apply new knowledge, and through research and innovation, develop sustainable products and services that add value to the economy (Beaudry et al., 2021). Investment in R&I brings multiple benefits: improved productivity, economic diversification, creation of new jobs, strengthening export potential, resilience to external shocks and the introduction of green and digital solutions (Delechat et al., 2024). A developed innovation ecosystem should be dynamic, open, inclusive and connected—both nationally and at regional and European levels. This requires collaboration among businesses, academic institutions, civil society organisations and public institutions in jointly creating solutions to market and social challenges. Open innovation is particularly important, involving various stakeholders in the process of knowledge creation and diffusion, which increases the speed, quality and societal impact of innovation solutions.

2.3. Strategic Alignment with EU and National Policies

Several strategic documents form the basis for innovation and economic development policies in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The Directorate for Economic Planning of B&H prepared the Strategic Framework for Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2015 (Direkcija za ekonomsko planiranje B&H, 2015). During its preparation, existing strategic documents adopted by the Council of Ministers of B&H, as well as obligations arising from the Stabilisation and Association Agreement between B&H and the EU, were taken into account. The document is structured in accordance with the European Union 2020 Strategy and the South-East Europe 2020 Strategy, adopted by the Council of Ministers of B&H.

By identifying development areas within the objectives of the South-East Europe 2020 Strategy, which are interrelated, the following goals for B&H were established:

- *Integrated growth* through the promotion of regional trade and mutual investment and development, as well as through non-discriminatory and transparent trade policies;
- *Smart growth*, encompassing innovation, digitalisation and youth mobility, as well as the determination to remain competitive based on quality rather than low labour costs;
- *Sustainable growth*, focusing on balanced regional development and the improvement of efficiency and sustainability in natural resource management, supporting increased economic and social self-sufficiency, and creating better conditions for local development and employment;

- *Inclusive growth*, aimed at increasing employment, developing skills, ensuring inclusive participation in the labour market, providing inclusive and quality healthcare, and reducing poverty;
- *Governance as a function of growth*, entailing the strengthening of administrative capacity to implement the principles of good governance at all levels of authority, reinforcing the rule of law and combating corruption to create the business environment necessary for economic and social development.

In September 2015, Bosnia and Herzegovina, together with 192 United Nations member states, committed to implementing the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which consists of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and 169 targets. B&H recognised the importance and potential of implementing the SDGs and the 2030 Agenda as an opportunity to significantly improve the social, economic and environmental aspects of life in the country, as well as to enhance regional cooperation.

The first step in implementing the 2030 Agenda in B&H was the development of the Framework for Sustainable Development Goals in B&H (UNDP, 2020), a joint document involving all levels of government that defines the broader development directions to which all government levels and society in B&H wish to contribute to achieving the SDGs. Based on an analysis of the state of sustainable development in B&H – i.e. key development trends, opportunities and barriers, particularly in the context of EU accession, and extensive consultations with representatives of institutions at all levels of government and socio-economic stakeholders during 2018–2019 – three broad sustainable development directions were identified for B&H:

1. Good governance and public sector
2. Smart growth
3. Society of equal opportunities
4. Two horizontal themes were also defined:
5. Human capital for the future
6. The principle of “leaving no one behind”

The first initiative to prepare the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) in Bosnia and Herzegovina began in 2020, when the Council of Ministers established a working group to draft the strategy and appointed the Directorate for Economic Planning (DEP) as the coordinator of the S3 process. Adopting a “bottom-up” approach, smart specialisation brings together local authorities, the academic community, the business sector and civil society to implement long-term growth strategies. The concept of smart specialisation is based on detailed analysis and identification of competitive advantages at the national and regional levels, highlighting economic, innovation, scientific and technological potentials. In October 2022, the Final Report on Quantitative Analysis for Smart Specialisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina was prepared (Galić & Hollanders, 2022) to identify potential priority domains for smart specialisation in B&H, based on an analysis of economic, innovation, scientific and technological data. Industries with economic potential were identified using employment and value-added data for 2017–2020 and export data for 2010–2020. One of the main conclusions is that an economy like B&H largely depends on labour-intensive and/or low-technology/less knowledge-intensive industries, which contribute to these potentials, rather than on knowledge-based sectors. Only 18% of the identified industries were classified as medium–high technology or knowledge-intensive. The absence of industries internationally considered research and development-intensive implies that many of the identified industries with economic potential have weak innovation capacity.

The Republic of Srpska has developed a comprehensive Industrial Strategy for the period 2021–2027, as well as a Strategy for the Development of Science and Technology, Higher Education and the ICT Industry for 2023–2029. The latter strategy (Vlada Republike Srpska, 2023) is aligned with the objectives of the Europe 2030 for Sustainable Development document, which recognises education, science, technology, research, innovation and digitalisation as prerequisites for achieving a

sustainable EU economy, contributing to the realisation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals. This strategy is also aligned with the Framework for Achieving the SDGs in B&H, as well as with other sectoral strategies in The Republic of Srpska, such as the Strategy for the Development of SMEs in The Republic of Srpska for 2022–2027, the Industrial Development Strategy of The Republic of Srpska for 2021–2027 and the Employment Strategy of The Republic of Srpska for 2022–2027.

During the preparation of the strategy, recommendations from the European Commission were considered, including the introduction of the smart specialisation concept, the promotion of open access to scientific data (Open Science), improving the quality of education by modernising curricula to better align with domestic labour market needs, and the development and enhancement of e-services and digital skills.

The objectives, priorities and measures of the Industrial Strategy of The Republic of Srpska for 2021–2027 are aligned with EU industrial policies, with the overarching goal of increasing industrial competitiveness. The planned priorities include recovery and revitalisation of industry, development and digitalisation of industry, internationalisation, import substitution, ensuring a skilled workforce, improvement of the business environment, attraction of industrial investments, application of environmental standards in industry and efficient use of industrial resources. Priority 1.2 focuses on the development and digitalisation of industry, recognising that the manufacturing sector currently generates insufficient added value and contributes only a small share to the GDP of The Republic of Srpska. Therefore, restructuring domestic production is necessary by promoting higher value-added production and introducing innovations, modern technologies and equipment into production processes (Ibid).

The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy (CEAP), adopted in 2015, establishes a framework to accelerate Europe’s transition from a linear to a circular economy, with 54 measures designed to “close” the product life cycle, from production and consumption to waste management and secondary raw materials markets.

Based on the objectives of the European Green Deal, the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans was adopted at the Sofia Summit in November 2020 as part of the region’s Economic and Investment Plan (European Commission, 2020). The Green Agenda is a key document for alignment with EU climate and environmental policies.

The five pillars of the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans are:

1. Decarbonisation – energy transition, renewable energy sources (RES), energy efficiency
2. Circular Economy – waste management, sustainable production and consumption
3. Pollution Prevention – air, water, soil
4. Sustainable Mobility – low-carbon transport and infrastructure

Protection of Biodiversity and Ecosystems – conservation of natural resources, forest and land restoration.

Bosnia and Herzegovina is a signatory to the Sofia Declaration and has formally committed to implementing the Green Agenda (Regional Cooperation Council, 2021). However, the implementation of these policies requires a significant strengthening of institutional capacities, legislative harmonisation and investment in green infrastructure.

In this context, the Industrial Strategy of The Republic of Srpska for the period 2021–2027 sets Strategic Objective 5: Reducing harmful environmental impacts. Priority 5.1 relates to the application of environmental standards in industry, representing a transition to a green economy, while Priority 5.2 concerns the efficient use of resources in industry, that is, a transition to a circular economy.

The Digital Agenda is one of the seven pillars of the Europe 2020 strategy, which sets growth targets for the EU up to 2020. The Digital Agenda proposes better utilisation of the potential of information and communication technologies (ICT) to promote innovation, economic growth and societal progress. In 2018, the European Union launched the Digital Agenda for the Western Balkans with the aim of supporting the region’s transition to a digital economy and realising the benefits of

digital transformation, such as faster economic growth, higher employment and improved service quality.

The European Commission document, “Support Measures for the Digital Agenda for the Western Balkans,” identifies the following priorities:

1. Reducing roaming costs through the establishment of a roadmap for the gradual elimination of tariffs;
2. Development of broadband internet;
3. Development of e-government, e-procurement, e-health and digital skills;
4. Strengthening capacities in the areas of security and industrial digitalisation so that all sectors can benefit from digital innovations;
5. Adoption and implementation of EU legislation in the field of the single digital market.

These priorities are also recognised in the context of future industrial development in The Republic of Srpska, with the Industrial Strategy of The Republic of Srpska for 2021–2027 defining Priority 1.2: Development and digitalisation of industry.

The Industrial Strategy of The Republic of Srpska for 2021–2027 notes that collaboration between the scientific research community and the business sector remains insufficient. Existing cooperation between companies and research institutions has not reached a level that enables significant innovation outcomes. Research potential, and therefore investment in innovation, is recognised in a limited number of enterprises, while scientific and research institutions do not sufficiently align their research with companies and the practical application of innovations. To increase the level of research and development (R&D) and innovation activity in companies, it is necessary to provide professional support from the scientific research community.

The Horizon Europe programme (2021–2027) represents the EU’s most important instrument for financing research and innovation, with a budget of €95.5 billion (Consilium – Council of the European Union, 2025).

The main objectives of the programme are:

- Strengthening the scientific and technological base of the EU,
- Addressing global challenges (climate change, sustainable development),
- Promoting the competitiveness and economic growth of the EU, and
- Achieving the EU’s sustainable development goals and political priorities.

The programme is divided into four main parts:

1. Excellence in Science Funding is provided for cutting-edge research through:
 - The European Research Council (ERC),
 - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) – researcher mobility and development,
 - Research infrastructures.
2. Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness
This part is divided into clusters covering areas such as health, digitalisation, climate and energy, food and environment, security, culture and society, as well as industry and space.
3. Innovative Europe
Focused on pioneering innovations and supporting start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) through:
 - The European Innovation Council (EIC),
 - European innovation ecosystems,
 - The European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT).
4. Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (ERA)
The aim is to support Member States and associated countries with lower research capacities to actively participate and benefit from the programme (Ibid).

Bosnia and Herzegovina is an associated country of the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe, and participates on equal terms with EU Member States under an agreement in force from 1 January 2021 to 31 December 2027. The status of an associated country provides the academic and research community, as well as companies in Bosnia and Herzegovina, access to European funding for research and innovation for the period 2021–2027.

2.4. The Role of Universities in Implementing and Sustaining the Strategy

Universities form the foundation of a country's innovation ecosystem. Their primary role is to generate new knowledge, develop skilled human capital and stimulate and support research in collaboration with the business sector. As such, universities serve as the starting point for creating innovations, as well as the final point when knowledge about innovations is transferred. Consequently, the role of universities in implementing and sustaining a research and innovation strategy is multifaceted, encompassing educational, research, developmental and advisory functions (Morawska-Jancelewicz, 2022).

The Faculty of Economics at the University of Banja Luka (UNIBL), as a leading higher education institution in Bosnia and Herzegovina with strong regional partnerships and active development centres (including CPME and eLab), has particular potential to act as a bridge between the academic and business sectors. Its past activities have included actively promoting student internships and involving students in projects, providing mentorship for participation in student competitions and international programmes, engaging academic and administrative staff in international research and development-innovation programmes, and fostering collaboration and networking with the business sector through lectures, workshops and the inclusion of experts in research projects.

In future activities, universities should contribute to improving research infrastructure, where business experts would also play a significant role, through the following actions:

- Enhancing existing research infrastructure, including laboratories, innovation hubs and digital platforms.
- Supporting entrepreneurs through specialised training programmes organised by CPME, eLab and other specialised subunits of UNIBL, including training in innovation and entrepreneurship, the application of generative artificial intelligence tools and the development of transversal skills available to students, faculty and other interested stakeholders.
- Providing training in related fields to strengthen entrepreneurial competencies, such as financial literacy, funding sources, use of digital tools, quantitative analysis and foreign languages.
- Collaborating with foreign universities and organisations to facilitate knowledge mobility, exchange of best practices and joint work on addressing regional challenges.

In this way, universities do not remain merely educational institutions but become key actors in social and economic transformation, directly influencing the innovation capacity of the state and its readiness for integration into the European research and entrepreneurial space.

3. Strategic Vision and Objectives

Our vision is the gradual development of a functional ecosystem for research, innovation and entrepreneurship in Bosnia and Herzegovina, taking into account existing challenges as well as untapped opportunities. We do not aim for a premature “miracle” like Estonia or Israel, but rather a stable, step-by-step development that will enable:

- Better utilisation of existing resources (human, institutional, financial);
- Real connections between the academic community and the private sector;

- Practical innovations that solve local problems (rather than forcing “world-changing revolutionary ideas”).

Our mission is to actively foster the creation and development of an innovative entrepreneurial ecosystem in the broader environment of the University through collaborative engagement of key stakeholders led by the Faculty of Economics at UNIBL. This ecosystem will promote economic growth and development, enhance the competitiveness of both new and existing companies, and accelerate the transition of developing countries toward knowledge-based societies. By encouraging a new paradigm of an open innovation ecosystem, through joint activities in research and development, education, training and active engagement of students and academic staff with the real, governmental and non-governmental sectors, as well as with citizens and the media, we aim to create a sustainable innovative entrepreneurial ecosystem that will guide our country and the region toward prosperity and sustainable development, aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

This vision entails the development of institutional capacities, investment in research infrastructure and human capital, and stronger cooperation between science, industry and government institutions. The strategy must align with the principles of sustainable development, digital transformation and inclusivity.

Strategic objectives include:

- *Strengthening the Role of the University as a Catalyst for Social Progress* – with particular focus on the Faculty of Economics at UNIBL – as an active actor in the regional innovation system through functional development centres and partnerships with the business sector.
 - Enhancing basic research infrastructure
 - Renovating existing laboratories and faculty centres and creating new development centres within UNIBL’s organisational units
 - Functional digitalisation (provision of essential IT equipment for research and teaching processes in collaboration with private companies, institutions and support from European funds; stable broadband optical internet; modern software)
 - Functional student incubators and accelerators with mentors (not necessarily “world-class”, but sufficient to help start-ups survive the first 2–3 years)
 - Focus on applied research (e.g., agriculture, tourism, IT outsourcing – areas where B&H already has certain advantages)
 - Connecting local companies with faculties (e.g., students working on practical innovation projects for companies)
 - Equipping classrooms and laboratories according to modern pedagogical methods of interactive learning in the digital age (smaller functional and flexible labs, projectors, smart boards, audio-visual tools, etc.)
- *Promoting Open Innovation* through interaction between the academic community, private and public sectors, aiming at jointly creating sustainable solutions for social and market challenges.
 - Reducing bureaucracy (e.g. faster company registration, simplified taxes for small businesses)
 - Changing legal regulations to enable active engagement of lecturers – mentors – and students in creating university spin-off companies.
 - Joint applications by academia and private companies for EU co-financing of research and innovation activities.
 - Microcredits and small grants (instead of unrealistic expectations for large investments)
 - Support for existing SMEs (already operating and potential innovation drivers) and start-ups, through subsidies and tax incentives

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- *Building Capacities for Knowledge and Technology Transfer* through creating collaborative instruments (innovation laboratories, knowledge transfer offices, platforms, living labs).
- *Developing Human Capital* with emphasis on transversal competencies, digital skills and entrepreneurial spirit, focusing on empowering youth, marginalised groups and women in the innovation process.
 - Education supporting practical skills (e.g. digital literacy, financial literacy, soft skills)
 - Support for both traditional and innovative businesses
 - Fewer *inspirational stories*, more concrete steps (e.g. workshops on how to launch a business, rather than motivational speeches)
- *Enhancing Regional Cooperation* to create a mutually connected and functional innovation space in the Western Balkans.
 - Preparation of project applications for EU funds, as well as entity and state institutional funding
 - Collaboration with neighbouring countries (e.g. Croatia, Serbia, Montenegro – where existing connections are already established)
 - Cooperation with the diaspora (not necessarily for large-scale returns, but for mentoring and occasional consultancy).

4. Current State of the Entrepreneurial and Research-Innovation Ecosystem in B&H

Entrepreneurship, as a multidimensional concept, has become a cornerstone of economic development and sustainability, as well as a prerequisite for achieving higher rates of economic growth. For the development of entrepreneurship and the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures, continuous promotion of innovation is essential, as it represents a key feature of all entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, entrepreneurship can be viewed as a dynamic process of discovering and evaluating opportunities for introducing new products, services and processes. This definition does not rely solely on creativity, which involves generating new ideas and knowledge, but also emphasises the fact that resources can be used in entirely new ways. The current state of the entrepreneurial and research-innovation ecosystem in B&H is marked by significant progress, but also by numerous challenges that slow down its full development (Bosnia and Herzegovina [B&H], 2011). Positive trends in the entrepreneurial ecosystem include the growth of the start-up sector (accompanied by a significant increase in events, business angel networks and initiatives), regional integration (B&H became a full member of the Horizon Europe program in January 2021, granting researchers and innovators access to significant EU funds), as well as support from international organisations—most often through initiatives aimed at strengthening cooperation between the academic community, the business sector and public institutions (Council of Ministers – Directorate for European Integration [DEI], 2020). Challenges still facing the entrepreneurial sector in B&H include a lack of venture capital (especially in early development stages), weak coordination among different actors and a limited number of qualified mentors and investors (B&H, 2011).

4.1. Research and Innovation Capacity

The research and innovation ecosystem in B&H has shown progress in international collaboration (B&H is actively involved in EU research and innovation programs, particularly in the fields of energy and the environment, which strengthens capacity and competitiveness) and digital transformation (the EU supports B&H's efforts to promote digital trends and market competitiveness, including the development of digital innovation hubs and the promotion of green and digital transitions). However,

to unlock the full potential of the entrepreneurial and research-innovation sector, *it is necessary to address the issues of insufficient investment in research and development, improve cooperation between academia, industry and the public sector, develop innovation infrastructure and create an environment that halts the negative “brain drain” trend* – migration of researchers and experts from various fields.

By implementing these measures, B&H can become a more competitive and innovative actor both regionally and internationally (Ministry of Civil Affairs of Bosnia and Herzegovina [MCP], n.d.).

4.1.1. Status of Academic and Research Institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The status of academic and research institutions in B&H is complex and shaped by a number of factors, including a decentralised governance system, limited investment in science and weak links with industry and international knowledge flows. Strengths and potentials include:

- A respectable network of higher education institutions (B&H has over 40 higher education institutions, including public and private universities, with notable universities in Banja Luka, Sarajevo, Tuzla, Mostar and East Sarajevo) covering a wide range of scientific fields (The Republic of Srpska [RS], 2023);
- Increasing participation in EU programs—the country is associated with Horizon Europe, showing growth in funds accessed and relative advantages in the fields of energy and environmental protection—demonstrating potential for international collaboration and knowledge transfer (European Commission, 2024);
- Initiatives for knowledge and innovation transfer (a number of technology transfer offices have been established, and partnerships exist with UNDP, GIZ, and other actors to strengthen innovation capacity).

Weaknesses and challenges include a decentralised and uneven governance system, a fragmented normative-strategic framework and very limited capacities (no significant progress recorded in the “Science and Research” sector), with low R&D expenditure—around 0.19% of GDP—which significantly limits research and innovation reach (European Commission, 2024). Additional challenges include low international visibility (less than 1,000 scientific publications annually in Scopus/WoS databases), average age of academic and research staff (~50 years), insufficient connection with industry and the labour market, brain drain and low researcher motivation.

4.1.2. Research and Development Financing and Infrastructure

Funding for research and development (R&D) in B&H is statistically monitored through two approaches. One approach concerns the recording of budget allocations, where data are collected, processed and published to track government policy in this area. Reporting units are budgetary institutions that provide the funds for implementing activities. The other approach is the statistical survey *Science, Technology and the Digital Society*, where reporting units are institutions conducting research and development activities. Its aim is to collect and publish data on R&D personnel, expenditures and funding sources, as well as the results of R&D activities.

In 2023, the total number of patent applications in B&H was 52, of which 7 were filed by foreign applicants (individuals and legal entities). In the same year, 3 patents were granted, all to foreign legal entities (Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina [BHAS], 2024).

In 2023, the R&D sector in B&H employed 3,631 persons (full- and part-time), of whom 1,875 or 51.6% were women. Researchers constituted the largest share of total employment (80.2%). The majority of researchers were employed in the higher education sector (83.8%), while only 9.4% were

employed in the business sector (BHAS, 2024). Budget allocations for R&D in B&H in 2023 amounted to BAM 73,881,655 (€37,775,090). By sector, the largest portion of funds was spent in higher education (69.4%), followed by the government sector (15.1%), the business sector (11.4%), the foreign sector (3.4%) and the non-profit sector (0.7%). The largest share of budget funding by socio-economic objective (37.0%) was allocated to general advancement of knowledge—research and development financed from general university funds. Gross domestic expenditure on R&D in B&H in 2023 amounted to BAM 94,115,000 (€48,120,235), or 0.18% of GDP. Of the 99 organisations engaged in R&D activities in 2023, the majority belonged to the higher education sector (61), while 28 were in the business sector. The total number of scientific publications in the same year was 1,533, of which fewer than 1,000 were indexed in Scopus/WoS databases. The largest number of publications (419 papers or 27.3%) was in the field of engineering and technology (BHAS, 2024).

In addition to relatively low percentage investment in R&D, the absolute amount allocated in B&H is extremely low on an annual basis, especially considering the country's low GDP. For comparison, in 2022 Austria allocated 2.2% of GDP to R&D, Belgium 3.4%, the Czech Republic 1.96%, Denmark 2.89%, Israel as much as 6.02%, while in the Western Balkans, Croatia allocated 1.4%, Serbia 0.90%, North Macedonia 0.40%, Montenegro 0.36% and Albania only 0.15% (World Bank Group, 2023).

R&D infrastructure in Bosnia and Herzegovina is largely underdeveloped and fragmented, which directly impacts the country's innovation capacity and its ability to participate in global knowledge and technology flows. Although B&H possesses certain technical and human resources within universities, institutes and some companies, the overall R&D infrastructure system is characterised by low coordination, insufficient funding and a lack of strategic planning.

Research institutions are mostly linked to public universities, while independent institutes and development centres have limited capacities and often operate in isolation. Technical equipment in many research centres is outdated, restricting the implementation of modern research, particularly in natural sciences, engineering and biomedicine. There is a shortage of young researchers and systemic support for their work. Funding comes predominantly from entity government budgets, while resources from international sources and partnerships remain underutilised. There is no dedicated national science fund.

Technology transfer and collaboration with industry are poorly developed. Most universities do not have functional technology transfer offices, nor do they hold patents that are commercially exploited. The use of digital tools is limited, and access to research databases and platforms is extremely poor (Parliament of Bosnia and Herzegovina [Parliament B&H], 2009). Persistent gaps in funding and collaboration also contribute to weak performance in intellectual property, which currently stands at 10.9% of the EU average for 2025. B&H ranks last among EU and neighbouring countries in terms of PCT patent applications and trademark filings. Nevertheless, the country recorded an increase of 7.4 percentage points in patent applications since 2018 (EC, 2025b).

4.1.3. Innovation Performance and University–Industry Collaboration

Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H) consistently rank low on the Global Innovation Index, indicating a weak level of innovation development compared with other countries in the region and Europe. A fundamental challenge is the chronic underinvestment in research and development (R&D), which amounts to less than 0.20% of GDP—well below the EU average and the recommended rate of 3% of GDP. In addition to financial constraints, the absence of coordinated strategies, legal frameworks and institutional support further slows innovation development. Most innovative activities originate from international donors and a few individual initiatives, while a systemic approach is almost non-existent. Although there is nominal connectivity between universities and industry, *collaboration is often*

symbolic and limited to sporadic projects or memoranda of understanding. The educational system is predominantly theory-oriented, often lagging behind global innovations, and the lack of practical training and entrepreneurial education further distances students from the real sector. Conversely, the private sector often lacks trust in the academic community, perceiving it as closed and slow to adapt to market needs. Available data on collaboration metrics indicate weak performance, with joint publications between the public and private sectors at only 29.8% of the EU average for 2025. This reflects an underdeveloped infrastructure for cooperation between the business sector and academia, as well as limited R&D funding (OECD, 2024).

To improve innovation performance and strengthen university–industry collaboration in B&H, the following measures are recommended:

For the academic community:

- ✓ Redesign and accredit study programmes in line with UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), ESG standards and a “student-centred” approach; develop English-language programmes aligned with labour market needs and the latest global scientific and technological advances.
- ✓ Establish partnerships with European universities to develop dual-degree programmes, enhancing knowledge transfer and internationalisation.
- ✓ Form and develop research centres in partnership with the private sector, following the paradigm of responsible open innovation.
- ✓ Embrace digitalisation and the ethical application of generative artificial intelligence tools in research and teaching.
- ✓ Establish technology transfer offices at public universities.
- ✓ Promote student internships, business incubators and accelerators, and mentoring programmes for nascent student entrepreneurs.

For the private sector:

- ✓ Actively participate in educational and research activities through guest lectures, promotion of responsible, green and smart innovations, motivational talks, conferences, round tables, joint projects with higher education institutions, scholarships and hosting students for internships; support the equipping of classrooms and laboratories.
- ✓ Invest in R&D and the development of responsible innovations in collaboration with universities.

For the government sector:

- ✓ ***Local authorities:***
 - In cooperation with entity authorities and EU funds, identify non-viable military and commercial properties and convert them into business incubators and accelerators.
 - Eliminate parafiscal charges under local jurisdiction and reduce or remove local taxes for companies developing responsible and sustainable innovative solutions.
 - *Formalise partnerships via cooperation agreements* between municipalities/cities and universities to enable continuous student internships, industry-requested research and joint projects.
 - *Subsidise start-ups and green businesses* originating in university incubators and accelerators, as well as in newly established science and technology parks, through local innovation and sustainable entrepreneurship funds.
 - *Provide local scholarships and awards* for students and researchers whose work is applicable in the real sector or contributes to sustainable development (e.g. energy efficiency, circular economy, digitalisation).
 - *Implement mentorship programmes* in which local business leaders act as mentors to students and academic teams.

- *Introduce green vouchers for SMEs*: funding for consultancy and research services from universities to enhance sustainable practices.
- ✓ Entity, canton, district and state authorities:
 - Increase R&D allocations through financial and non-financial incentives from 0.20% to a minimum of 1% of GDP by 2030.
 - *Create grant and tax incentive programmes for companies* investing in research projects with universities or engaging students and researchers in practical tasks.
 - Introduce supportive measures, such as the formation of innovation funds, innovation vouchers for purchasing R&D services from universities, tax breaks for SMEs investing in R&D, co-financing grants (matching grants), vouchers for patenting and other intellectual property protection and enabling the formation of university spin-off companies with limited professor involvement (e.g. following the Italian model).
 - Develop and consistently implement strategies for innovation and science–industry collaboration.

All proposed measures should actively involve civil society and the media as partners in promoting the development of sustainable, responsible entrepreneurship.

4.1.4. Insights from the USE IPM Targeted Strategy for Research and Innovation in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) Partnering with the EU

The USE IPM document presents a targeted strategy aimed at enhancing the research and innovation capacities of higher education institutions through collaboration with EU partners. The strategy integrates specific experiences from visits to entrepreneurial innovation ecosystems in France, Italy, Belgium, Croatia, Spain, Portugal and the United Kingdom—countries with diverse practices in supporting innovation development and sustainable entrepreneurship. It constitutes a strategic framework developed within the EU Higher Education Reform Support programme, with a particular focus on strengthening institutional research management, knowledge transfer and private-sector collaboration. The strategy is based on identifying internal weaknesses of universities in candidate countries, including Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H), and transferring best practices from partner institutions in the EU. Key objectives include the development of effective research management mechanisms, promotion of interdisciplinary projects and stimulation of industry collaboration through innovation hubs and joint initiatives. Special emphasis is placed on institutional autonomy, digitalisation of processes and active involvement of students and early-career researchers in international research flows (European Commission [EC], 2024).

USE IPM is recommended as a tool for strategic planning for universities in transition countries and serves as a foundation for alignment with EU frameworks such as the European Research Area (ERA) and Horizon Europe. Its implementation in B&H opens opportunities for systemic modernisation of higher education, particularly regarding research infrastructure, institutional governance and stronger connections with the real sector. Most B&H universities face challenges such as underdeveloped research management capacities, fragmented planning systems and weak links with industry and international research networks.

4.2. Key Challenges in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The USE IPM guidelines provide recommendations for enhancing the existing entrepreneurial ecosystem in Western Balkan enlargement countries—Serbia, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia. These recommendations are based on research conducted through focus groups,

Delphi methodology and needs analyses between September 2023 and November 2024. The guidance highlights critical areas for developing the skills of young people, facilitating their integration into entrepreneurial ecosystems and understanding contemporary entrepreneurship. Four key thematic areas were identified: behavioural (soft) skills, sustainability and sustainability reporting, technology transfer and open innovation, and innovation process management. Since entrepreneurship is directly linked to innovation—used as a tool for market entry and expansion—the management of innovation processes represent the ultimate objective of these recommendations.

4.2.1. Development of Soft Skills for Entrepreneurship

In enlargement countries, education systems continue to prioritise technical competencies over soft skills, which undermines the entrepreneurial capacities of young people. Employers often undervalue communication, teamwork and emotional intelligence. Cultural norms that emphasise hierarchy and formal authority limit openness, negotiation and conflict resolution. Assertive communication is underdeveloped; many employees struggle to articulate ideas clearly or actively listen to colleagues and clients. While technical knowledge remains highly valued, interpersonal competencies are often neglected, despite their potential to enhance team cohesion and client relations (Cimatti, 2016; Cacciolatti et al., 2017).

4.2.2. Technology Transfer and Open Innovation

Technology transfer and the application of open innovation in Bosnia and Herzegovina face deeply rooted structural barriers. Universities, the private sector and public institutions largely operate in a fragmented manner, without established mechanisms of synergy and mutual trust. The regulatory framework is fragmented and burdened by bureaucratic procedures, which complicates the registration of innovations and discourages potential investors. Financial support remains insufficient and often poorly aligned with specific local needs, while capacities for research commercialisation and access to venture capital are extremely limited. Awareness of intellectual property rights is low, leaving many entrepreneurs without adequate protection or means to monetise their ideas. The market's low purchasing power further reduces motivation for innovation, and resistance to digital tools slows the transition towards knowledge-driven sectors (Chesbrough, 2003; Bigliardi & Galati, 2018; Radičić & Petković, 2023).

4.2.3. Sustainability and Sustainability Reporting

Although EU policies emphasise the strategic importance of sustainability and ESG reporting, enlargement countries face serious barriers to implementing these frameworks. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, sustainable development is hindered by regulatory and infrastructural deficiencies. Environmental protection regulations are vague and poorly enforced, while weak waste management systems result in illegal dumpsites, inadequate recycling infrastructure and insufficient wastewater treatment. Although renewable energy projects (such as hydropower plants and solar systems) are being developed, they often cause ecological disturbances in sensitive areas. Financial barriers particularly affect small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which lack resources to adopt green technologies or comply with ESG standards. Public awareness of environmental issues remains low, and cooperation between government, academia and industry is insufficiently coordinated, reducing

the potential for joint responses to sustainability challenges (Rosário et al., 2022; Sreenivasan & Suresh, 2023).

4.2.4. Innovation Process Management

Innovation processes in enlargement countries are weakened by limited resources, inadequate institutional support and a focus on short-term profitability. Universities and research institutions often produce theoretical knowledge with little practical application. The absence of standardised methods for measuring innovation outcomes prevents effective policy monitoring and adaptation. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the innovation ecosystem is fragmented, with weak coordination between universities, research centres, the private sector and government institutions. Companies are frequently risk-averse and resistant to change, preferring routine and stability. There is no legal framework for supporting social enterprises or responsible innovation, and knowledge of innovation methodologies is limited. The lack of support for green innovations further prevents the economy from seizing opportunities within the EU's digital and green transition (Gustina et al., 2024; Leon-Roa et al., 2025).

4.3. Policy recommendations, actions and expected impacts

a) Strengthening Soft Skills for Entrepreneurship

To overcome deficiencies in soft skills, governments should integrate communication, teamwork, negotiation and emotional intelligence into national curricula at both secondary and university levels. Teacher training and professional development for academic staff must include modules on the pedagogy of soft skills to ensure that the education system itself becomes a generator of entrepreneurial culture. Partnerships between universities and industry should provide internship programmes where students gain experience in collaborative environments. Policymakers should also support lifelong learning centres and digital platforms offering affordable programmes that enable young entrepreneurs to continuously improve their competences.

Actions

- Integrate soft skills modules (communication, teamwork, emotional intelligence, negotiation) into curricula and study programmes.
- Train teachers and university staff in the pedagogy of soft skills.
- Establish structured internship programmes with participation from the business sector.
- Support lifelong learning centres and digital platforms offering accessible training programmes.

Expected impacts

- A more adaptable and innovative workforce, better prepared for entrepreneurial ventures.
- Increased employability of graduates through a balanced combination of technical and soft skills.
- Stronger cooperation between the education and business sectors, with improved alignment to labour market needs.

b) Strengthening Technology Transfer and Open Innovation

A stronger innovation ecosystem requires institutional reforms that simplify administrative procedures for intellectual property registration and establish clear legal frameworks for technology transfer. Collaboration between academia and industry should be institutionalised through innovation hubs, incubators and public–private partnerships. Governments should increase access to funding not only for pilot projects but also for the commercialisation of research outcomes. It is necessary to

expand advisory, mentoring and training services on intellectual property so that innovators can protect and market their work.

Actions

- Simplify procedures for the registration and protection of intellectual property.
- Establish innovation hubs and incubators to foster collaboration between academia and business.
- Direct funding towards the commercialisation of research outcomes.
- Develop mentoring, advisory and training programmes in the field of intellectual property law.
- Encourage digital transformation through financial and institutional support.

Expected impacts

- Stronger protection and commercialisation of domestic innovations.
- Increased private sector investment in research and development.
- Closer alignment between research work and industry needs.
- Enhanced competitiveness of SMEs in regional and EU markets.

c) Improving Sustainability and ESG Practices

For Bosnia and Herzegovina and the region, it is essential to strengthen regulatory implementation and alignment with EU standards. Governments should introduce fiscal incentives, such as tax reliefs or grants, for SMEs that adopt green technologies and circular economy models. National strategies should develop waste management infrastructure and support renewable energy projects through transparent environmental impact assessments. Awareness-raising campaigns, in cooperation with academia and civil society, can increase environmental awareness. The state should subsidise the preparation of ESG reports to ensure that small enterprises are not excluded due to associated costs.

Actions

- Align environmental and sustainability regulations with EU standards (CSRD, ESG).
- Introduce fiscal incentives (tax reliefs, grants, favourable loans) for SMEs adopting green technologies.
- Expand infrastructure for recycling and waste management.
- Subsidise ESG reporting and organise related training sessions.
- Launch public awareness campaigns on sustainability, involving academia and civil society.

Expected impacts

- Greater compliance with EU green transition policies.
- Wider adoption of circular economy practices among SMEs.
- Reduced environmental risks (illegal dumpsites, biodiversity loss, poor wastewater management).
- Improved reputation of domestic companies and easier access to EU markets and funds.

d) Enhancing Innovation Process Management

To establish a coherent innovation framework, Bosnia and Herzegovina should develop standardised metrics for evaluating the efficiency of incubators, accelerators and university–industry collaboration projects. Academic institutions should incorporate innovation methodologies such as design thinking and prototyping into study programmes. Public institutions should simplify procedures and direct funding towards market-driven needs. Encouraging a culture of experimentation and rewarding innovative projects will help companies shift from short-term profit orientation towards long-term innovation strategies. It is particularly important to provide financial incentives and support to academic staff engaged in research, thereby strengthening the connection between academia and industry.

USE IPM

Actions

- Develop standardised metrics for evaluating innovation outcomes (e.g. start-up survival rate, commercialisation of research).
- Introduce legal frameworks and fiscal incentives for green business models.
- Integrate innovation methodologies (design thinking, prototyping, agile methods) into education.
- Simplify public programmes and reduce bureaucratic barriers.
- Encourage companies to take risks and innovate through reward schemes.
- Provide incentives and support for academic staff engaged in scientific research.

Expected impacts

- More effective monitoring and evaluation of innovation policies.
- Development of inclusive and sustainable business models.
- Greater integration of universities in addressing practical challenges.
- Transition from short-term to long-term, innovation-driven economic strategies.

Table 8: Key challenges, recommended actions and anticipated impacts on the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Thematic area	Key challenges	Actions	Expected impacts
Soft skills for entrepreneurship	Insufficient integration into education and business; hierarchical cultures; underestimation by employers.	Integrate soft skills into curricula; train teachers; create internship programmes; support lifelong learning.	A workforce more prepared for entrepreneurship; higher employability; stronger collaboration between education and business sector.
Sustainability and ESG practices	Weak implementation of regulations; poor waste management; high costs for SMEs; fragmented institutional cooperation.	Align regulations with EU standards; introduce fiscal incentives; develop recycling infrastructure; subsidise ESG reporting; conduct public awareness campaigns.	Greater alignment with EU policies; wider adoption of the circular economy; reduced environmental risks; improved access to EU markets.
Technology transfer and open innovation	Weak collaboration between academia and industry; fragmented legal frameworks; weak IP protection; limited funding for commercialisation; resistance to digitalisation.	Simplify IP procedures; establish innovation hubs; finance commercialisation; provide mentorship and advisory support; promote digital transformation.	Stronger protection of innovations; increased R&D investment; closer research–industry cooperation; higher SME competitiveness.
Innovation process management	Fragmented ecosystem; risk aversion; absence of legal frameworks for social enterprises; lack of innovation metrics.	Develop innovation performance metrics; introduce legal frameworks for social enterprises; integrate innovation methodologies into	More effective monitoring; development of sustainable business models; universities more aligned with market needs; long-

		education; reduce bureaucracy; encourage risk-taking and innovation.	term, innovation-driven growth.
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Source: Author's elaboration.

4.3.1. Broader Contributions to the Enhancement of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The proposed set of recommendations goes beyond the immediate goal of supporting young entrepreneurs and improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem. Their broader contributions lie in creating systemic, long-term impacts that strengthen innovation capacity, economic resilience and social well-being in Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H).

- **Strengthening Cooperation Between Academia and Industry**

By promoting joint research centres, innovation hubs and structured partnerships between academia and industry, these recommendations contribute to bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. Such collaboration enhances the commercialisation of research results, facilitates knowledge and technology transfer and ensures that educational programmes remain aligned with the dynamic needs of the labour market. The broader impact of these activities lies in building a knowledge-based economy and increasing the employability and competitiveness of graduates.

- **Advancing Entrepreneurial Education and Skills Development**

A key contribution is the transformation of education systems to integrate entrepreneurship, sustainability and innovation into university and vocational curricula. Practical training, interdisciplinary learning and experiential programmes create generations of graduates equipped to handle complex challenges. Such human capital not only drives business development but also embeds principles of sustainability and innovation across various sectors. This fosters a culture of entrepreneurial thinking that gradually reshapes social attitudes towards risk-taking, collaboration and long-term value creation.

- **Establishing Systematic Impact Measurement**

The introduction of standardised indicators and key performance measures for monitoring entrepreneurial and innovation activities has far-reaching policy implications. By enabling authorities and institutions to assess the effectiveness of initiatives in real time, these recommendations promote evidence-based policymaking, more efficient resource allocation and greater accountability. The broader contribution of such systems lies in strengthening institutional transparency and trust among stakeholders — investors, academia and civil society.

- **Promoting Sustainable and Responsible Innovation**

The recommendations offer a vision of entrepreneurship that is not solely profit-driven but also environmentally and socially sustainable. By embedding ESG principles, circular economy models and responsible innovation management into entrepreneurial ecosystems, Bosnia and Herzegovina gains the capacity to align its business practices with EU standards and global development goals. The broader contribution is twofold: it facilitates integration into European markets while ensuring that growth remains inclusive, resilient and environmentally responsible.

- **Enhancing Economic Competitiveness and Stability**

Collectively, these proposals lay the foundation for a more innovative, adaptable and competitive economy. They help mitigate structural weaknesses within B&H's entrepreneurial landscape — such as fragmented stakeholder cooperation, underdeveloped financial mechanisms and low digitalisation — thus creating a favourable environment for long-term competitiveness. In doing

so, they contribute to regional economic stability, social cohesion and the strengthening of B&H's position within the European and global knowledge economy. The recommendations for improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem in B&H are not merely a technical set of measures, but a framework for broader socio-economic transformation. Their true value lies in fostering collaboration among academia, industry, policymakers and civil society — building the foundation for a sustainable and innovation-driven future.

4.3.2. Enhanced Higher Education Strategy for Research and Development at All Levels of Government in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The modernisation of higher education is a key factor in strengthening the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem of Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H). In the context of European integration, aligning the higher education and research system with the European Research Area (ERA) and the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) is essential for building institutional capacities, facilitating knowledge transfer and ensuring that academic outputs are more closely aligned with market and societal needs. Universities in B&H play a central role as drivers of innovation, sustainability and entrepreneurial growth. Strengthening cooperation among academia, industry, and the state is crucial for accelerating the commercialisation of research, fostering technological development and enhancing the resilience of the national economy. By incorporating business engagement into curricula, expanding interdisciplinary education and cultivating a culture of innovation, higher education can produce generations of graduates equipped with entrepreneurial, digital and sustainable skills.

Equally important is the integration of innovation methodologies such as design thinking, prototyping and agile project management into university programmes. These tools enable students and researchers not only to generate new ideas but also to translate them into practical solutions that contribute to economic growth and social development. Universities, in cooperation with innovation hubs and incubators, can stimulate the development of start-ups and strengthen the connection between research and practice.

Strengthening research capacities forms the backbone of higher education modernisation and the innovation system in B&H. It is necessary to systematically develop infrastructure for scientific research within universities and institutes, thereby creating better conditions for scientific and innovation progress. In addition to infrastructure, stable and predictable funding is of crucial importance, allowing for long-term projects rather than reliance on sporadic sources. Such an approach directs research towards strategic goals with a clear contribution to social and economic development. Particular emphasis should be placed on interdisciplinary approaches that combine knowledge from different fields to address the complex challenges facing B&H. At the same time, higher education institutions in B&H should build international links more proactively. Participation in European programmes such as Erasmus+, Horizon Europe and COST Actions increases university visibility, facilitates student and researcher mobility, and strengthens cooperation through joint projects and publications.

The development of human capital remains at the core of this strategy. By improving doctoral and postdoctoral programmes aligned with labour market dynamics, systematically promoting lifelong learning and creating incentive mechanisms for diaspora engagement in domestic research activities, B&H can significantly strengthen its base of highly qualified professionals and enhance its overall research and innovation capacity. Continuous professional development of academic staff—especially in digital skills, pedagogy and research methodologies—further supports the modernisation of the system.

Together, these measures are designed to position B&H's higher education system as a catalyst for innovation, entrepreneurship and sustainable development. By linking academia and industry, integrating universities into global knowledge networks and nurturing an entrepreneurially oriented workforce, B&H can advance its readiness for EU membership and secure a stronger role within the European and regional innovation landscape.

5. Key Pillars of the Research and Innovation Strategy

The research and innovation strategy should rest on several key pillars that guide the development of the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem. In the context of the Republic of Srpska and Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H), these pillars are particularly important given existing challenges such as low investment in research and development (R&D), limited innovation capacity and weak connections between science and industry. Comparative reviews from regional countries (B&H, Serbia, Albania and North Macedonia) and global examples can provide valuable guidance on how to strengthen these pillars and accelerate integration into the European Research Area.

5.1. Research Excellence

The pursuit of research excellence involves improving the quality of scientific research, strengthening research infrastructure and human resources, and increasing participation in international projects. Currently, R&D investment in B&H is among the lowest in Europe—estimated at below 0.3% of GDP (European Commission [EC], 2023). Such low funding, combined with a fragmented legislative framework, limits the country's scientific capacity and contributes to lagging behind the EU average (EC, 2023). This underinvestment is reflected in the modest number of high-impact scientific publications and patents originating from B&H. According to the *European Innovation Scoreboard 2025*, B&H is categorised as an “Emerging Innovator”, achieving only 25.7% of the EU average innovation performance, and particularly underperforming in indicators such as internationally cited publications and the number of new PhD graduates (European Commission [EC], 2025c). In comparison, Albania scores 37.9%, North Macedonia 40% and Serbia 51.5% of the EU's average innovation performance (EC, 2025c).

Enhancing excellence requires systemic reform. It is essential to substantially increase financial support for research—both through public budgets and competitive funds, as well as through private sector engagement (EC, 2023).

The European Commission, in its latest report, recommends that B&H adopt a new *Science Development Strategy 2023–2028* along with an accompanying Action Plan, and that it increases the research budget—particularly in the field of innovation—to stimulate economic recovery. Furthermore, a more efficient, merit-based competitive funding system is needed to encourage quality and results (EC, 2023).

Regional examples show positive trends—for instance, Serbia has recently established a Science Fund and increased R&D allocations, which has been followed by a rise in highly cited publications and participation in international projects. Another dimension of excellence lies in human capital. B&H continues to face limited research capacity alongside ongoing brain drain, as the most talented young researchers often leave for better conditions abroad, particularly in medicine and information technology (EC, 2023). To mitigate this, it is vital to create more attractive opportunities domestically: *introduce incentives for researchers* (scholarships, postdoctoral training, grants for young scientists) and improve career pathways within universities and institutes. *The quality of doctoral programmes and mentorship also needs to be enhanced* to produce highly skilled human resources. *Establishing*

centres of excellence and large-scale joint research infrastructure projects (such as EU-funded laboratories) can help retain talent and boost scientific productivity. As the European Commission notes, integration into the European Research Area and increased international cooperation act as catalysts for reform and can enhance the capacity to achieve scientific excellence (European Commission, 2021). Therefore, B&H at all levels should engage more proactively in programmes such as *Horizon Europe*, *COST* and *EUREKA*, which not only provide funding but also connect local researchers with leading European peers, facilitating the transfer and diffusion of knowledge.

5.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

The transfer of knowledge and technology from academia to industry is one of the key preconditions for creating added value from research. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, this pillar remains weakly developed — university–industry collaboration is limited, as noted by the European Commission, which emphasises the need to strengthen systemic interaction within the *triple helix* model connecting academia, industry and government (EC, 2023). The lack of networking means that research results often remain unutilised in practice. Furthermore, government support for research and development (R&D) in enterprises is virtually non-existent, while private-sector R&D investment remains very low. According to the *European Innovation Scoreboard 2025*, Bosnia and Herzegovina has almost no public investment in R&D for enterprises and lacks developed venture capital, which severely constrains the technological development of its economy (EC, 2025a).

It is therefore essential to establish mechanisms that will stimulate the commercialisation of research. One of the first steps should be *developing the legal and organisational infrastructure for technology transfer* – for example *establishing Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs)* at universities, *business incubators, accelerators and science and technology parks*. A study by Đonlagić Alibegović et al. (2022) on science and technology parks in B&H highlights their potential to play a key role in linking research and business by applying the triple helix model and promoting interaction between universities, industry, and government through joint projects, spin-off companies and innovation initiatives. A positive example is the BIT Centre in Tuzla, which has produced several technology start-ups in collaboration with local faculties (Đonlagić Alibegović et al., 2022). Beyond infrastructure, *policy and legislative adaptation* is also required. Intellectual property (IP) regulations should encourage the patenting and licensing of public research outcomes. Currently, the number of patent applications in B&H is very low.

The Institute for Intellectual Property of Bosnia and Herzegovina reported that in 2024, a total of 47 patent applications were submitted — 34 by domestic applicants and 13 by foreign applicants — marking a 9.6% decrease compared to the previous year. Of the domestic applications, all were submitted by individuals, while among foreign applicants, 46.2% were from individuals and 53.8% from legal entities (Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2025, p. 1).

Incentives for scientists and innovators to protect their results through patents and attract investors are urgently needed. One possible measure is to introduce *Proof of Concept* programmes that finance early stages of research commercialisation. Innovation funds can also play a significant role in stimulating innovation activities. Countries in the region, such as Serbia and North Macedonia, have established dedicated funds that co-finance innovative projects by companies and consortia with researchers, leading to an increase in technology transfers and joint patents (World Bank, 2013).

Institutional culture must also shift towards more open collaboration. The traditionally separate systems of science and industry must be bridged through proactive measures. Organising business–science forums, encouraging research and development consortia, and involving industry in setting research agendas can make research outcomes more relevant to market needs. The European Commission has noted that Bosnia and Herzegovina lacks regular triple-helix interaction and that the

absence of a *Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3)* has further limited the focus of research on commercially viable areas (EC, 2023). Therefore, developing an S3 strategy is a priority — by identifying niche areas (for instance, agri-technology, renewable energy or ICT), Bosnia and Herzegovina can concentrate resources on sectors where it has comparative advantages and facilitate the transfer of innovations into production. Global practice also offers guidance: universities in developed countries have established spin-off programmes and science–technology clusters around them. For example, Silicon Valley emerged through strong interaction between Stanford University and industry, supported by venture capital and an entrepreneurial culture. Although such an ecosystem remains distant for B&H, the country can begin building its own “mini valleys” by networking key actors and positioning technology transfer as a central pillar of its innovation strategy.

5.3. Innovative Entrepreneurship

The culture of *innovative entrepreneurship* reflects a society’s ability to generate new business ventures based on knowledge and innovation, to support the growth of start-up companies and to enable existing small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to become engines of innovation. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the entrepreneurial ecosystem is still developing but demonstrates clear potential. According to the *European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) 2025*, B&H has a relatively high share of SMEs introducing new products and processes – above the EU average for this indicator (EC, 2025a). Moreover, employment in innovative firms is relatively strong for a country of this size (EC, 2025a). These indicators suggest that, despite a challenging institutional and economic environment, the private sector in B&H shows an increasing capacity for innovation. However, a key challenge remains the lack of financial instruments and support mechanisms for start-ups and innovative businesses. The venture capital (VC) market is almost non-existent, institutional investors rarely invest in high-risk projects, and state support in the form of grants or incentives for innovative entrepreneurship is minimal (EC, 2025a).

For the development of innovative entrepreneurship, it is crucial to build a more favourable business environment and a supportive ecosystem. This means simplifying procedures for establishing start-up companies, introducing tax relief for research and development in the private sector and creating a legal framework that enables new financing models (such as crowdfunding platforms, business angels and similar instruments). Business incubators and accelerators are an important part of this ecosystem. Although several exist in B&H (for example, the ICBL business incubator in Banja Luka), their capacity and networking with investors need to be strengthened. Experiences from the region are valuable. *The Innovation Fund of Serbia* through seed funding and mentorship programmes, has supported hundreds of early-stage start-ups, while *The Fund for Innovation and Technical Development (FITD) of North Macedonia* has co-financed numerous innovative SME projects and contributed to building a start-up community in Skopje (EC, 2025a). An interesting programme of the FITD, *The Western Balkans Innovation Vaucher*, supports the development of business ideas and entrepreneurial ventures. Establishing similar institutions in B&H – such as a national innovation fund or agency offering a wide range of support programmes, packages and measures for sustainable innovation management – could accelerate entrepreneurial activities. The Republic of Srpska has made some progress in this respect, adopting the Law on Innovation Activity and planning the establishment of an Innovation Fund, while in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina such institutional initiatives are still absent.

Entrepreneurial education and culture are also important aspects. The formal education system, starting from preschool, should integrate programmes that foster innovative thinking and entrepreneurial and digital skills. Universities can establish start-up centres and organise competitions for the best innovative ideas or prototypes developed by students, thus stimulating the

entrepreneurial spirit during education. Cultural barriers such as fear of failure or resistance to change should be reduced through the promotion of successful domestic entrepreneurial stories. At present, the perception of risk is high and confidence in starting a business is low, so the state and the media can play an important role in affirming innovators and creating a positive image of entrepreneurship. When the role of civil society and citizens in promoting sustainable development, entrepreneurship and environmental protection is added, the Triple Helix Model of development evolves into the Quintuple Helix Innovation Model.

Removing administrative barriers to starting a business is another limiting factor. Regulations should facilitate easier operation of innovative companies – for example through more flexible labour laws for start-ups, better protection of minority investors and faster registration of patents and intellectual property rights for firm-developed innovations. Global experience shows that countries which have introduced so-called “one-stop-shop” systems for start-ups – providing legal, financial and mentoring support in one place – achieve faster growth of innovative businesses.

In the Republic of Srpska and the Federation of B&H, local authorities can further encourage innovative entrepreneurship through public–private initiatives. For example, the establishment of business incubators and technology parks near university centres (such as the existing one in Mostar or the planned Science and Technology Park in the University of Banja Luka campus) in partnership with private companies could create clusters where ideas are more easily turned into businesses. Connecting with the diaspora is also important, as many successful innovators of B&H origin abroad are willing to invest in and mentor domestic start-ups if transparent mechanisms for collaboration are in place.

Finally, digital transformation and the global market enable entrepreneurs from small countries to launch innovative business models, products and services worldwide. Strengthening digital skills and infrastructure – such as high-speed internet and digital platforms for e-commerce – is therefore directly linked to the success of innovative firms. Currently, fewer than 20% of small businesses in B&H are active in e-commerce (EC, 2023), but improving this area will open new opportunities for innovative companies to scale and access global markets. Viewed as a whole, the pillar of innovative entrepreneurship requires a comprehensive approach: financial, mentoring and infrastructural support for start-ups, removal of bureaucratic barriers and the cultivation of a culture that celebrates creativity and accepts controlled risk. Successful implementation of this pillar would lead to an increase in new companies, new jobs and faster innovation-driven economic growth – which is the ultimate goal of the research and innovation strategy.

6. Implementation Framework

The preceding sections of this document have defined the strategic objectives of research and innovation (R&I) in fostering the development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in the enlargement countries, with particular emphasis on the role of universities, alignment with European policies (Horizon Europe, ERA, S3, EU Green Deal) and the need to strengthen cooperation between the academic and business sectors. The implementation framework serves as a bridge between these strategic objectives and the expected outcomes, providing an overview of the key opportunities and mechanisms through which the vision can be operationalised.

Governance

Effective governance of strategy implementation requires the establishment of a coordinated system of leadership, monitoring and evaluation. It is necessary to form national and institutional bodies for R&I, with a clear division of responsibilities and coordination mechanisms among universities, ministries, the private sector and other relevant stakeholders. Transparent, data-driven

decision-making processes, grounded in performance indicators, will ensure long-term sustainability and integration with the European Research Area.

State level (B&H): A Council/coordination body for R&I (chaired by the Council of Ministers or the competent minister) with a small Secretariat (analytics, monitoring, reporting), alongside a network of NCP coordinators for Horizon Europe and an S3 working group (policy alignment).

- Entity level

The Republic of Srpska: A Council for Science and Innovation within the relevant ministries (MNTRVO, MPP), the Innovation Fund acting as an operational body (calls, contracting, M&E) and a university TTO network (technology transfer).

- Federation of B&H: FMRPO (operational SME/innovation calls), FZZPR (planning and monitoring of the FB&H Strategy) and university R&I offices (TTOs/centres).

- Universities: Vice-Rector for Science and Technology Transfer, TTO/Project and Entrepreneurship Centre, Ethics Committee, Open Science Committee and an Industrial Advisory Board.

National Strategy for Research and Innovation

The implementation framework must align with existing national development documents, including smart specialisation strategies and those for green and digital transitions. This ensures horizontal coherence with other policy areas (education, industrial development, climate policy), as well as vertical alignment with European strategic frameworks. The national strategy should also provide stable sources of funding through a combination of public and private funds, in addition to access to European programmes. Given the complex constitutional structure of B&H and the clearly defined division of competences, this strategy will be harmonised with entity-level strategies and those of joint institutions, as presented in the following table.

Table 9: Strategic documents containing elements of support for research and development

Level	Document	Status	Period	Lead institution	Instruments	Implementation	Examples of calls
Joint institutions (state level)	Science Development Strategy in Bosnia and Herzegovina 2017–2022 (revised framework document)	Expired	2017–2022	Ministry of Civil Affairs of Bosnia and Herzegovina (MCP)	Framework measures for science and innovation; since 2022, there has been no valid state-level R&I strategy; S3 has not been adopted at the state level	N/A – document expired; recommendations from the European Commission guide the development of a new strategy and S3	Expired; at the state level, examples include services provided by the Institute for Intellectual Property of B&H (e.g. IP pre-diagnostics) and statistical support by BHAS; no active grant instruments under this strategy

The Republic of Srpska	Strategy for the Development of Science and Technology, Higher Education and the Information Society of The Republic of Srpska 2023–2029	Adopted	2023–2029	Government of The Republic of Srpska / Ministry for Scientific and Technological Development and Higher Education of The Republic of Srpska	Objectives, priorities and measures, including key projects; institutional strengthening (including the establishment of the Innovation Fund)	Detailed measures and projects with indicative budgets; a combination of funding from the RS budget, loans and donors	MNTRVO calls (e.g. international exchange/co-financing of R&D); development of the Innovation Fund; projects on digitalisation and internationalisation
The Republic of Srpska	Action Plan for Innovation in SMEs of The Republic of Srpska 2024–2027	Adopted	2024–2027	Ministry of Economy and Entrepreneurship of The Republic of Srpska	Design and launch of the Innovation Fund; strengthening innovation infrastructure; participation in EU/Western Balkans programmes	Operationalises innovation measures through projects and financing (RS budget + donors/IFIs)	Public calls of the Ministry of Economy and Entrepreneurship of The Republic of Srpska (promotion of SMEs, innovation); planned instruments of the Innovation Fund; participation in EU/Western Balkans programmes
Federation of B&H	Development Strategy of the Federation of B&H 2021–2027	Adopted	2021–2027	Government of the Federation of B&H / Federal Institute for Development	78 measures and approximately 550 activities; accelerator: Innovation and Digitalisation;	Each measure is translated into a programme within annual work plans and further	Annual grant schemes by line ministries; public calls by FMRPO (e.g. Digital Transformation of SMEs)

				Programmi ng (FZZPR)	implementati on through annual and mid-term plans, Public Investment Programme (PIP), and institutional budgets	integrated into the Budget/PIP; funding from institutional budgets and external sources	2021; grant schemes 2025); implementati on through the PIP and annual budget
Federat ion of B&H	Strategy for the Develop ment of Small Enterpris es in the Federati on of B&H 2022– 2027	Adop ted	202 2– 202 7	Federal Ministry of Developme nt, Entreprene urship and Crafts (FMRPO)	Public calls and incentives for SMEs; measures for innovation and digitalisation; support for internationali sation	Operationali sed through FMRPO’s annual programmes (SME grants, innovation measures, vouchers/tec hnical assistance where applicable)	FMRPO public calls supporting SME innovation and digitalisation; non- repayable grants and mentoring schemes; annual grant programmes by priority area

Notes: The table provides an overview of the current status of strategic documents related to research, development and innovation at both the entity level and the level of joint institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The overview was prepared by the authors with the assistance of the ChatGPT-5o model on 8 September 2025.

Universities

As highlighted in the introductory sections of the document, universities are key actors in the innovation ecosystem. Implementing the strategy requires strengthening their research infrastructure, developing innovation centres (laboratories, hubs, “living labs”) and enhancing capacities for knowledge and technology transfer. Universities, through their organisational units—such as the Faculty of Economics at UNIBL with its centres (CPME and eLab)—should act as the primary bridge between the academic and business sectors, fostering collaboration programmes, mentoring support and research internationalisation. The first concrete step is the establishment of the UNIBL Technology Transfer Office. Existing centres and other sub-organisational units should be strategically restructured and adapted to meet the demands of operating in a digital and post-digital era.

Cultural Change

Successful implementation requires a shift in both societal and institutional culture—from administrative inertia towards fostering innovation, collaboration and openness. It is necessary to cultivate a culture based on meritocracy, cross-sector collaboration and a willingness to take risks. Integrating innovation into the education system, promoting entrepreneurial spirit, and recognising research work in society form the foundation for sustainable change.

International Orientation

The implementation framework also emphasises a strong international orientation, particularly through collaboration with universities, research centres, and business actors from the EU and beyond. Regional networking within the Western Balkans, as well as participation in European and global networks, will enhance knowledge exchange, improve access to funding and strengthen competitiveness. Researcher mobility, joint projects and the exchange of good practices will be key tools in this process.

Stakeholder Communication

The success of the strategy depends on active and continuous communication with all relevant actors: the academic community, entrepreneurs, policymakers, civil society, and citizens. Inclusive dialogue mechanisms (forums, advisory bodies, public consultations) must be developed to ensure the legitimacy of the process and encourage co-creation of innovative solutions. Transparent communication fosters trust and a greater willingness to collaborate.

Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is a horizontal priority of the strategy's implementation. This includes developing digital infrastructure, introducing new digital tools and platforms and training human resources in digital skills. Digital solutions enable more efficient knowledge transfer, better collaboration between universities and industry and increase the international visibility and competitiveness of the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Green Transformation

In line with the European Green Deal, green transformation is a key element of the implementation framework. It involves promoting research and innovation in renewable energy, the circular economy and sustainable business models. Involving SMEs and start-ups in this process is particularly important for market development and reducing dependence on traditional resources. Green transformation, combined with digital transformation, allows for the simultaneous enhancement of competitiveness and the preservation of socio-ecological sustainability.

7. Expected Outcomes and Impact

The implementation of the Research & Innovation (R&I) Strategy for the development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina is expected to achieve measurable and sustainable results, contributing to the transformation of the business and innovation environment, strengthening the competitiveness of SMEs, fostering collaboration between the academic community and the private, public and non-governmental sectors, and promoting entrepreneurship and self-employment as a viable career option for students and graduates. It will create conditions for long-term socio-economic progress. The outcomes focus on strengthening institutional capacities, developing human resources, improving innovation infrastructure and enhancing the regulatory framework, while the impact will be visible across the economy, academia and society as a whole.

Expected Outcomes of the Strategy include:

1. *Strengthening institutional and organisational capacities of the academic community and R&I institutions.* This Outcome involves increasing the number of research centres with established mechanisms for knowledge and technology transfer, as well as expanding activities in existing centres. New innovation and development centres will be established at universities that currently lack them, while existing centres will be strengthened, facilitating better collaboration with industry and two-way knowledge transfer.

2. *Increasing investment in research and development.* By enhancing cooperation between industry and universities, as well as promoting international collaboration among universities, the number of joint projects will rise, facilitating access to European and other funding sources. Collaboration on practical problems between academia and business will also attract both public and private investment.
3. *Enhancing collaboration between academia, public, private and non-governmental sectors.* Joint projects create a spillover effect, establishing cooperation beyond formal channels, networking researchers and developing new forms of collaboration. This leads to increased joint research outputs, patents and licensed technologies.
4. *Supporting inclusive and sustainable development.* Innovative solutions will encourage the active participation of vulnerable groups in the innovation process. Innovations will contribute to both the green and digital transformation of society and the economy.

The Strategy's implementation is expected to have multiple impacts, ranging from the immediate strengthening of research capacity and networking of actors to the long-term shaping of an innovation culture in society.

Economic impact would primarily be reflected through the increased competitiveness of entrepreneurs and SMEs. The implementation of the strategy would enable better entrepreneurial education and preparation for starting a business, access to resources and innovations, as well as mentoring support in the early stages of entrepreneurial ventures. Greater support for entrepreneurs would lead to an increase in the number of newly established enterprises and self-employment initiatives, which would diversify the current economic structure of Western Balkan countries and create new jobs, especially in knowledge- and technology-based sectors.

Social impact entails strengthening the culture of innovation and entrepreneurship in society, raising awareness of the importance of entrepreneurship and job creation in modern business conditions, which would ultimately contribute to reducing youth emigration. Cooperation between the academic community, industry and public administration would increase, thereby harmonising the resolution of social challenges. Additionally, the quality of research capacities and innovation outputs would improve, and their transfer into practice would be facilitated.

8. Conclusions and Recommendations

8.1. Summary of Key Strategic Priorities

Based on empirical evidence, comprehensive and sequenced policy packages can be recommended for local, entity/district and state authorities, as well as the management of higher education institutions, through mutually connected lines of action. The next steps for policymakers and practitioners are clear:

1. *Expand SME participation in the system of open sustainable innovation.* Develop and implement inclusive innovation schemes such as SME vouchers, appropriate grants and simplified tax incentives tailored to SMEs. This will reduce barriers for SMEs and broaden the innovation base.
2. *Simplify administration of research and innovation support.* Implement administrative reforms to reduce bureaucratic complexity and accelerate the application and approval processes for research and development incentives, as well as the digitalisation of these services. Introduce digital application portals, standardise requirements and transition to user-oriented, trust-based procedures.
3. *Strengthen links between universities and industry.* Invest in the establishment and professionalisation of Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) at public universities and collaborative

research centres. *Introduce incentives for university-industry consortia, joint laboratories and cluster-based initiatives* to promote sustainable partnerships and knowledge exchange.

4. *Build and strengthen research capacities in academia, companies and research and innovation centres. Provide targeted training and advisory programmes* for SMEs and researchers, focusing on project proposal writing, project management and access to international funds, as well as strengthening transversal skills (soft, entrepreneurial and digital skills) of students, professors, researchers, entrepreneurs and managers. Develop a virtual mentoring scheme for secondary school students, university students and all those interested in starting their own entrepreneurial venture, and in subsequent phases, implement peer mentoring (students who “survived” the first year of running their startup become co-mentors for the next generation of student entrepreneurs).
5. *Ensure transparent governance.* Establish transparent eligibility criteria, digitalised workflows, public registers of allocated funds and measurable performance indicators (e.g. joint patent applications, spin-off companies, co-authored publications). These steps will build trust and credibility in public support programmes.
6. *Sequence policy incentive instruments.* Begin with collaborative grants and quick results in the area of intellectual property to build trust and capacity, and then introduce innovation vouchers, tax incentives and subsidies for the commercialisation of sustainable innovations to support scaling and market entry.

8.2. Next Steps for Policy Implementation and Adoption

Although Bosnia and Herzegovina has initiated the planning process and preparatory steps, the Smart Specialisation Strategy has not yet been formally completed or adopted. Bosnia and Herzegovina remains the only country in the region that has not yet adopted such a strategy. The Smart Specialisation Strategy should identify the country’s developmental potentials and focus on directing resources towards their growth. This will be achieved by connecting research and innovation capacities with the needs of the economy and will serve as a model for establishing the necessary conditions for accessing EU Structural Funds.

The Republic of Srpska, by adopting *Law on Innovation Activity (Official Gazette of RS, No. 31/21)*, has established the normative framework for the development of its innovation ecosystem. The planned construction of the *Science and Technology Park of The Republic of Srpska (STP)* and the establishment of the *Innovation Fund of The Republic of Srpska* represent key instruments for strengthening knowledge transfer, supporting start-up development and connecting universities with industry. The STP of The Republic of Srpska was founded as a result of a partnership between the Government of The Republic of Srpska and the University of Banja Luka, with the vision of becoming a central hub for linking innovative ideas and projects, in close cooperation with key actors in the entrepreneurial, scientific and business sectors. These initiatives reflect a strategic effort to create sustainable institutional mechanisms for supporting research and innovation (European Commission, 2023). In the Federation of B&H, innovation activities have been fragmented and primarily driven by strategic development documents, without the adoption of a specific Law on Innovation Activity. Several innovation centres and technology parks have been developed with the support of international donors, particularly through IPA funds and EU programmes. However, the absence of a coordinated and integrated institutional framework remains a significant obstacle (OECD, 2023; UNESCO, 2021).

8.3. Recommendations for Long-Term Sustainability and EU Integration

1. *Develop a unified, inter-entity coordinated Innovation Strategy at the level of the joint institutions of Bosnia and Herzegovina for research and innovation, aligned with the European Research Area (ERA) and the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3).*
2. *Strengthen R&D infrastructure* through the construction and development of science and technology parks in both entities, as well as digital innovation hubs, business incubators and accelerators under public–private partnership models.
3. *Establish a harmonised network of innovation funds* in The Republic of Srpska and the Federation of B&H to ensure transparent, long-term and sustainable financial support for innovation projects.
4. *Encourage university–industry collaboration (A2B)* by creating and professionalising technology transfer offices (TTOs) and introducing tax incentives and grants for joint projects.
5. *Internationalise the research sector* through greater participation in programmes such as Horizon Europe, Digital Europe and EIT KICs¹⁴, which would enhance competitiveness and accelerate Bosnia and Herzegovina’s integration into the EU Research Area.

8.4. Strategic Directions for CPME for the Period 2025–2035

Department for Artificial Intelligence and Digitalisation

- Training in artificial intelligence for business applications, data-driven decision-making and digital entrepreneurship.
- Establishment of joint laboratories with IT companies for applied student projects.
- Alignment with the Digital Europe Programme and the objectives of the EU Artificial Intelligence Act.

Student Incubator

- Pre-incubation support: idea validation, prototype development, legal counselling.
- Incubation support: mentorship, networking with investors, international mobility.
- Organisation of annual Demo Days.
- Benchmarking against incubation models of EIT Digital.

Training Centre

- Certification programmes:
 - “Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Management”
 - “Innovation and Digital Business Models”
 - “Social Entrepreneurship and Community Impact”
- Short training sessions for SMEs: Lean Start-up methods, Circular Economy in practice, and Green Finance.
- Hybrid delivery (online and in-person).

Mentor Network

- Database of local and international mentors (alumni, entrepreneurs, academics).
- Individual mentoring for incubator participants.
- Cross-border mentor exchange programmes.

¹⁴ EIT KICs marks Knowledge and Innovation Communities that was established by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT), EU body.

8.5. Expected Outcomes and Impacts of the Strategy at the Faculty of Economics Level

Through its proactive engagement, CPME will:

- Strengthen the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina and across the Western Balkans.
- Equip young people with entrepreneurial, soft and digital skills for employment and self-employment.
- Promote innovation with social and environmental responsibility.
- Attract investment and create new jobs, contributing to the EU integration process.
- Position CPME and the University of Banja Luka as a regional centre for innovation, artificial intelligence and digital entrepreneurship.

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ANNEX

Reviews of the D2.3 R&I strategies

Review 1	
Reviewer Name:	Panayiotis Kontakos, PhD, Deputy Head of School of Business and Management, Assistant Professor in International Business, UCLan, Cyprus, SAB member
Date of review:	20/12/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable “D2.3 R&I Strategies” is fully aligned with the objectives defined in Grant Agreement No. 101120390. The document represents a valuable resource for analysing similarities and differences within the R&I ecosystems across the observed region. No additional revisions are required by the author or any other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: None.
Review 2	
Reviewer Name:	Sandra Milanović, PhD, DC, FEUN
Date of review:	20/12/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable “D2.3 R&I Strategies” is fully consistent with the provisions of the Grant Agreement for project No. 101120390. The document provides an important foundation for guiding activities within the USE IPM project. Its overall quality meets the standards required for submission to the European Union through the SyGMa platform. No additional refinements are requested from the author or the consortium partners. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: None.